

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP4 – Building a sustainable Europe-wide collection of breast milk for research with an analytical centre

D4.5 Protocols for 5 approved demonstration studies uploaded on EU-PAS register

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Document History

Version	Date	Description
V1	3/6 2024	D 4.5, Protocols for 5 approved demonstration studies uploaded on EU-PAS register, is based on task 4.3, setting up five demonstration studies.

Abstract

Five demonstration studies has been set up fulfilling regulatory requirements from FDA and EMA regarding lactation studies.

Two were milk-only studies, one for levocetirizine with UOSL as leading partner, one for venlafaxine with ULAUS as leading partner. One study was Mothers milk and plasma study for amoxicilline with CHUT as leading partner. Two studies were Mother-Infant pair study for metformin and prednisolone with UPPS as leading partner.

Protocols were examined and approved by appropriate ethical review boards and regulatory authorities.

After approval the protocols have been made publicly available by uploading on the EU PAS registry, the EudraCT and CTIS (Clinical trial Information System).

Methods

All protocols have been approved by appropriate ethical review boards and regulatory authorities.

Results

The protocol for the levocetirizine study: “Levocetirizine/cetirizine levels in human milk – an observational, clinical study among breastfeeding women”. **EUPAS46213**.

The protocol for the venlafaxine study: “Prediction of venlafaxine exposure trough breastfeeding”. **EUPAS103385**

The protocol for the amoxicilline study: “Evaluation of Amoxicillin diffusion in breast milk according to a population pharmacokinetic approach”. **N°EudraCT 2021-002247-30**

The protocol for the metformin study: « Transfer of metformin into human breast milk and the plasma of breastfeeding children - A low intervention trial with biobanking of breast milk and plasma in Västra Götalandsregionen and Region Örebro”. **EUPAS 105190 , CTIS 2022-501693-19-00**

The protocol for the prednisolone study: “Transfer of prednisolone into human breast milk and plasma of breastfeeding children - A low intervention cohort study with biobanking of breast milk and plasma”. **EUPAS 100000059, CTIS 2023-508913-18-00**

The protocols are submitted with this report as appendices 1-5.

Appendices

See attachments.

(Levo)cetirizine Clinical Lactation Study Protocol

Protocol

Date: 28.04.2021

Levocetirizine/cetirizine levels in human milk – an observational, clinical study among breastfeeding women

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

This study is conducted in partnership with ConcePTION; a project where over 50 public and industry partners in Europe and worldwide are co-operating to build an ecosystem for better monitoring and communicating of medication safety in pregnancy and breastfeeding

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List of Abbreviations

DDD	Defined daily dose
ICF	Informed consent form
MW	Molecular weight
PB	Protein binding
PK	Pharmacokinetics
Pop PK	Population pharmacokinetics
$T_{1/2}$	Half-life
T_{max}	The time needed to reach C_{max}
V_d	Volume of distribution

1. PROTOCOL SUMMARY

1.1 Synopsis:

Protocol Title: Transfer of (levo)cetirizine into human breast milk, and potential adverse effects on nursing infants.

Short title: (Levo)cetirizine clinical lactation study

Primary Objectives	Primary Endpoints
Quantifying (levo)cetirizine excretion into human milk	Variability of concentration of (levo)cetirizine in human milk samples
Secondary Objectives	Secondary Endpoints
Monitor the safety of (levo)cetirizine in breastfed infants of mothers using (levo)cetirizine.	Maternal self-reported adverse events among breastfed infants
Detecting the impact of (levo)cetirizine on milk production.	Maternal self-reported perceived changes in milk production

Overall Design:

Study Phase	Phase IV
Indication	Allergy
Population	Lactating mothers using levocetirizine or cetirizine
Study Type	Observational, non-interventional
Estimated Duration of Study	Three years (2021-2023)

Number of Participants:

25 to 40 lactating women using levocetirizine or cetirizine will be included in the study.

Clinical site: Norway

Sponsor: IMI2 821520 – ConcePTION. This study is conducted in partnership with ConcePTION; a project where over 52 public and industry partners in Europe and worldwide are co-operating to build an ecosystem for better monitoring and communicating of medication safety in pregnancy and breastfeeding:

2. INTRODUCTION

2.1 Background Information

Prospective studies measuring drug concentrations in human milk are necessary to allow an accurate benefit/risk assessment for breastfeeding women in need of medications.

This necessity is clearly stated in the guidelines by the European Medicines Agency “Guideline on good pharmacovigilance practices (GVP) Product- or Population-Specific Considerations III: Pregnant and breastfeeding women”: *“Once a product is placed on the market, if use in pregnancy and/or during breastfeeding is likely to occur, data collection to obtain a better understanding of risks associated with such use and to identify and characterise risks is important even where no safety concerns have arisen in the pre-authorisation phase.”*

These guidelines also state: *“Increased and adequate data collection and data assessment in a timely manner will enable that patients and prescribers have relevant information to make informed decisions about using medicines during pregnancy or breastfeeding and that they are well-informed about uncertainties”*.¹

This study is motivated by these guidelines, and precisely, the statement that *“Medicine concentration levels in breast milk samples should be measured and a relative infant dose calculated, to obtain information for supporting the risk assessment and provision of advice on timing of medicine intake relative to breastfeeding where this may be feasible (e.g. for short-term or single dose treatments). Moreover, data on the effect of the medicine on milk production or composition should be collected, if potentially clinically relevant”*.¹

European regulatory recommendations are in line with those of the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA).²

An expert meeting organized by the FDA in 2016 concluded that for the decision about drug treatment during breastfeeding to be evidence-based, needed information includes at a minimum the amount of drug in human milk, the effect of the drug on milk production, and an understanding of the risks of the drug on the breastfed infant based on expected levels of exposure.³

In summary, clinical lactation studies quantifying drug excretion to milk are rare, despite the call from regulatory, health care professionals, and researchers alike. There is a need to undertake human lactation studies to determine the transfer of drugs to human milk and facilitate an evidence-based decision about drug use in breastfeeding. Updated information is a prerequisite for optimal treatment of breastfeeding women in need of medications.

2.2 Rationale for the study

2.2.1 Allergy in Breastfeeding Women

The benefits of breastfeeding and breast milk for both infants and mothers are established and well known.⁴ At the same time, medication use during breastfeeding is common; the exact percentage of women receiving medications during the post-partum period is challenging to define due to the lack of uniform medication use reporting system during breastfeeding.⁵

Approximately 20-30% of women of reproductive age are diagnosed with allergic disorders.⁷ Second-generation antihistamines, which have fewer sedative effects than first-generation antihistamines, are the first-line therapy in breastfeeding women.⁸ According to the Norwegian Prescription database⁶ around 200,000 women aged 15-39 years filled an antihistamine prescription in 2019. The number of women in childbearing who use antihistamines is probably higher since antihistamines are also available over-the-counter (OTC) in Norway.

Limited data exist about the transfer of some of the commonly used second-generation antihistamines into human milk. Only three clinical lactation studies on second-generation antihistamines were identified.^{9,10,11} More details about relevant clinical studies are found in section 2.3.1.

The high prevalence of allergic diseases, along with the few clinical studies on the use of antihistamines during breastfeeding, creates a necessity for human lactation studies on antihistamines.

No clinical studies have been done on levocetirizine, the pharmacologically active component in cetirizine. Physicochemical properties for (levo)cetirizine suggest that they are transferred to human milk. The amount excreted and the effects of this exposure on a nursing infant are yet to be studied. The label of (levo)cetirizine products states that cetirizine is excreted into human milk¹² (See Table 1 below for examples). One study has been identified on cetirizine¹¹, where only three breastfeeding women were recruited. More details about relevant clinical studies are found in section 2.3.1.

Table 1: Summarizing SmPC text for cetirizine, levocetirizine, and zirtek about breastfeeding (www.medicines.org.uk/emc/).

Example	SmPC text
Levocetirizine (Xyzal 5mg)	Cetirizine, the racemate of levocetirizine, has been shown to be excreted in human. Therefore, the excretion of levocetirizine in human milk is likely. Adverse reactions associated with levocetirizine may be observed in breastfed infants. Therefore, caution should be exercised when prescribing levocetirizine to lactating women. ¹²
Cetirizine (Zirtek 10 mg)	Cetirizine passes into breast milk. A risk of side effects in breastfed infants cannot be excluded. Cetirizine is excreted in human milk at concentrations representing 25% to 90% of those measured in plasma, depending on sampling time after administration. Therefore, caution should be exercised when prescribing cetirizine to lactating women. ^{13,14}

2.2.2 Current Treatment options

Newer antihistamines are preferred in breastfeeding as they generally are thought to have fewer central nervous system adverse effects like drowsiness and fatigue compared to first-generation antihistamines.¹⁵ Studies quantifying second-generation antihistamine excretion in breast milk are limited. Human clinical lactation studies have been conducted for loratadine, terfenadine and its metabolite fexofenadine, and cetirizine; the sample size in these studies was six, four, and three, respectively.^{9,10,11} There is thus a lack of evidence-based treatment recommendations for breastfeeding women in need of treatment with antihistamines.

2.2.3 Pharmaceutical and Therapeutic Background

Levocetirizine is a non-sedating histamine H₁ receptor antagonist. It is the (R)-enantiomer and the principal pharmacologically active component of the racemic mixture cetirizine. Levocetirizine and cetirizine are indicated for the symptomatic treatment of allergic rhinitis and the treatment of uncomplicated skin manifestations of chronic idiopathic urticaria. Compared to cetirizine, levocetirizine has a higher affinity to H₁ receptors than cetirizine.¹⁶

Moreover, levocetirizine has fewer sedating activities than other antihistamines.¹⁶ PK parameters for cetirizine and levocetirizine presented in table 1 indicate that they will be excreted into human milk. In this protocol, (levo)cetirizine will be used to refer to cetirizine and levocetirizine.

The low molecular weight, minimum metabolism, and the long plasma half-life of (levo)cetirizine estimate a high excretion into human milk. Nevertheless, the high plasma protein binding of (levo)cetirizine may decrease its transfer to breast milk.

Table 2: PK parameters for cetirizine and levocetirizine.¹⁷

PK Parameters	Cetirizine	Levocetirizine
T _{1/2}	8.3 hours	8 hours
T _{max}	0.5-1 hour	1 hour
V _d	0.4-0.6 l/kg	0.4 l/kg
PB	93%	92%
MW	389 g/mol	389 g/mol
DDD	10 mg	5 mg

2.3 Relevant Clinical and Preclinical Studies

2.3.1 Lactation Studies

To date, no clinical studies have been conducted to quantify levocetirizine excretion into human milk, and potential side effects on nursing infants below one year of age remain unknown. Milk concentrations have been determined only for fexofenadine, loratadine, and its metabolite descarboethoxyloratadine, also known as desloratadine, and only recently for cetirizine.¹⁸ Moreover, the effect of maternal use of (levo)cetirizine on milk production has not been studied.

One study estimating loratadine excretion into breast milk was identified.⁹ Six breastfeeding women were included in this study. After a single oral dose of 40 mg of loratadine, milk samples were collected. M/P ratio was 1.17. Over 48 hours, the amount of loratadine excreted into milk was 4.2 µg, which was 0.01 of the administered dose, and only 6.0 µg of the active metabolite was transferred to milk. The authors concluded that this dose is unlikely to present infants' hazards.⁹

In another study, milk and blood samples were collected from four lactating mothers after a single administration of 60 mg terfenadine. Samples were collected after reaching steady-state concentration. Terfenadine was not found in milk. However, a low concentration of its active metabolite fexofenadine was transferred to milk. M/P ratio was 0.21. The average milk level of fexofenadine was 41 µg/L, while the average maternal plasma was 309 ng/mL. The study demonstrated that nursing infants are not exposed to more than 0.45% of the recommended maternal weight-adjusted dose. It was concluded that this exposure is unlikely to be associated with untoward effects.¹⁰

Recently, a study including three breastfeeding women has been conducted in the USA. Milk samples were collected after a single administration of 10 mg cetirizine. Measured AUC was 506.8 ng·hr/mL, C_{avg} was 21.1ng/mL, C_{max} was 49 ng/mL. The calculated Infant dose was 0.0031 mg/kg/day, and RID was 1.77%. According to the authors, this minimal excretion of cetirizine into human milk is unlikely to pose a significant risk to nursing infants.¹¹

2.3.2 Safety in the pediatric population

In a double-blinded, placebo-controlled, randomized, multicenter trial of levocetirizine, 5 mg once daily for four weeks was administered to 306 children with allergic rhinitis aged 6 to 12 years.¹⁹ No statistically significant difference in the frequency of adverse events was reported between pediatric patients using levocetirizine and the placebo group.

In another randomized, double-blinded, placebo-controlled trial of 255 children aged 12–24 months who received treatment with (levo)cetirizine, no increase in adverse events frequency has been reported in those treated with levocetirizine than the placebo group. (The frequency was 55.2% in the levocetirizine group compared with 52.6% in the placebo group).²⁰ The most frequent ADRs were headache, upper respiratory tract infection, and influenza.²⁰

Two placebo-controlled studies in 159 pediatric patients aged 6-11 months and aged one year to less than six years exposed to levocetirizine, sleep disorder, somnolence, diarrhea, vomiting, and constipation have been reported.¹²

2.4 Benefit/Risk Assessment

This study is observational and will not impact participant's treatment. Therefore, participation in this study will not expose breastfeeding women to additional risks. This study will provide information that can help health care professionals and breastfeeding women make an informed decision about antihistamines in breastfeeding.

2.4.1 Summary of the known and potential undesirable effects on human subjects.

Reported undesirable effects in levocetirizine¹² and cetirizine¹³ are summarized in table 3.

Table 3: Summary of adverse events as reported in SmPC of levocetirizine and cetirizine

Drug	Age	Reported adverse effects
Levocetirizine	Pediatric patients aged 6-11 months and 1-6 years	Somnolence, sleep disorder, diarrhea, constipation, vomiting
Cetirizine	Children aged from 6 months to 12 years	Somnolence, Rhinitis, Fatigue, Diarrhea

Few colic and irritability cases in infants exposed to antihistamines have been reported.¹⁵

3. OBJECTIVES AND ENDPOINTS

Table 4: Summary of study's objectives and endpoints

Primary Objectives	Primary Endpoints
Quantifying (levo)cetirizine excretion into human milk.	Variability of concentration of (levo)cetirizine in human milk samples.
Assessing the influence of demographics and other co-factors on drug concentrations in human milk.	Variation in mother milk drug levels according to demographics and other co-factors.
Predicting average drug exposure in infants.	Calculation of average and range of simulated relative infant dose (RID).
Secondary Objectives	Secondary Endpoints
Monitor the safety of (levo)cetirizine in breastfed infants of mothers using (levo)cetirizine.	Maternal self-reported adverse events among breastfed infants
Detecting the impact of (levo)cetirizine on milk production.	Maternal self-reported perceived changes in milk production

4. STUDY DESIGN

4.1 Design

This is a phase IV, open-label observational study conducted to detect (levo)cetirizine levels in breastfeeding women and monitor adverse events in nursing infants. No interference with the participants' treatment will be made in this study. In total, 25 to 40 lactating women who meet all inclusion criteria and none of the exclusion criteria will be recruited. The population pharmacokinetics (Pop PK) approach will describe drug concentration in human milk and estimate drug exposure in infants.

Figure 1a. Study procedure: Milk sampling regimen and filling out questionnaire

The study procedures in (levo)cetirizine clinical lactation are illustrated in Figure 1a.

First, participants will be asked to answer several questions to determine their eligibility based on the inclusion/exclusion criteria predetermined in the study. Then, after participants submit the eligibility form, a screening call will be made to recheck that the participant meets all of the inclusion criteria and none of the exclusion criteria and explain the consenting process.

Participants will then be asked to answer the baseline questionnaire. Thereafter, a start-up call with the participants will be scheduled to provide support and information on the practical procedures, including milk sampling and the shipment.

The follow-up questionnaires will be answered on day one, where (6 milk samples) will be provided, and at each consecutive milk sampling day 2, 3, and 4, where one milk sample will be delivered.

Two to three weeks after the start-up call, a follow-up call will be made to answer any potential questions that might have arisen along the process. More details about milk sampling are found in section 6.4.1.

4.2 Study process

The study process is depicted in Figure 1b.

Figure 1b. Study Process

4.3 Scientific Rationale for Study Design

4.3.1 Milk Only Study

FDA recommends milk-only studies unless there is a reason to conduct another type of clinical lactation study (Guidance Document-Clinical Lactation Studies: Considerations for Study Design).²

Pharmacokinetics of (levo)cetirizine in adults is well established, and therefore blood samples from breastfeeding mothers are not needed. FDA recommends a mother-infant pair study when there is evidence that the drug accumulates in human milk.

No lactation studies have been conducted on levocetirizine. The clinical study conducted on cetirizine, the racemic mixture of levocetirizine, showed no accumulation of the drug in human milk.¹¹ Therefore, a mother-infant pair study is probably not required.

4.3.2 Population Pharmacokinetics

Population pharmacokinetics (pop PK) is a method used to describe a given drug's concentration-time profiles within a given population using the measured calculation in individuals' biological fluids.²¹ Pop PK approach is based on non-linear mixed effect modeling techniques that allow estimating both fixed (i.e., invariant) population parameters and random effects (i.e., inter-individual and residual variability).²¹

In clinical lactation studies, the pop PK approach can be used to estimate infants' exposure to drugs in breast milk. The high clinical value of pop PK is due to integrating individual covariates in the model that conventional PK studies may neglect. Therefore, pop PK gives better estimates of pharmacokinetic parameters of real-life patients.²¹

FDA recommends that milk sampling should avoid disruption of the breastfeeding routine. Intensive milk sampling is both inconvenient to breastfeeding mothers and can be a concern in lactation studies. Unlike conventional PK studies where richly sampled data is required, several samples collected from a heterogeneous population are sufficient to build the pop PK model.²¹

Pop PK analysis will be performed by team experts on these analyses.

4.4 Study Duration

The study recruitment period will be one year. Recruitment will start in the allergy season, if possible. Participation in the study will start when the first study informed consent is signed, and end when the follow-up call of the last participant is completed, or six months after the last participant is recruited, whichever comes last.

The study will be completed by the end of the IMI ConcePTION project period in 2024.

4.5 Beginning and End of Study Definition

The study begins when the first participant signs the informed consent form. The study recruitment period ends when the last participant delivers the milk sample(s), withdraws from the study, or is lost to follow-up.

4.6 Criteria for the termination of the study

The study recruitment will be stopped when 25 participants providing 9 milk samples each have fully participated in the study. Additionally, recruitment may be stopped due to procedure related problems or if the number of discontinuations for administrative reasons is too high.

5. STUDY POPULATION

5.1 Inclusion Criteria

The participant will be eligible for inclusion in the study if the participant:

- I. Mother > 18 years, with well-established breastfeeding, and their infant is at least eight weeks old.
- II. Is using (levo)cetirizine during breastfeeding, and is at a steady-state, i.e., has used the drug daily for at least two days before sampling.
- III. Provides written informed consent for the study and can sign with an electronic ID.

5.2 Exclusion Criteria

The participant will be excluded from the study if the participant:

1. Mothers <18 years
2. Mother's with preterm infants (gestational age < 34 weeks)
3. Mothers to twins
4. Mothers to infants with malformations or severe illness
5. Inability to communicate due to language barriers for the mother.

5.3 Sample Size

A total of 20 to 25 breastfeeding women is considered sufficient to quantify the transfer of (levo)cetirizine excretion into human milk (2). This is also bearing in mind that levocetirizine/cetirizine is expected to show relatively little variability between participants due to its pharmacological and pharmacokinetic properties (standard dosing regimen, no active metabolites, no genetic polymorphism, similar bioavailability between administration forms, no food interactions). Therefore, we will aim for up to 40 participants to allow for a few dropouts.

5.4 Rationale for Study Population

Lactating women who are at least 18 years of age treated with (levo)cetirizine. Infants ≥ 8 weeks will be included in the study. Lactation studies should favorably be initiated six weeks after delivery. This period will give the mother time to rest after delivery and breastfeeding to be well established. Additionally, Infants under two months of age are most vulnerable to adverse drug reactions.²²

The FDA recommends that milk sampling occurs after mature milk development (approximately ten days post-partum). Colostrum or transitional milk collection may overestimate drug transfer in mature milk. Leaky gap-junctions between the mammary alveolar cells in early post-partum may allow for increased drug passage into milk. These junctions close by the second week of lactation.²³

5.5 Recruitment Strategy

Several patient organizations will be used to advertise for this clinical study. Examples are The Norwegian Asthma and Allergy Association, Tryggmammamedisin, Ammehjelpen, and The Norwegian Women's Public Health Association. Social media websites like Facebook will also be used to recruit potential participants.

Advertisements and an informative video will be distributed through appropriate channels.

All online recruitment methods will direct participants to the study website to register by signing an online consent form with an electronic ID. Prior to consenting, each participant will be asked to confirm their eligibility to participate in the study electronically (electronic confirmation on the study website). Participants will then be asked to fill an online baseline questionnaire before being enrolled in the study.

Study participants will be contacted for a start-up call where detailed information about the study procedures will be provided. Moreover, instructions will be sent to the participants along with the study equipment.

5.6 Discontinuation of Study Drug and Participant Withdrawal

5.6.1 Participant Withdrawal from Study

A participant is withdrawn from the study if the participant withdraws consent from the study. Participants can withdraw from the study at any time without specifying a reason. All dropouts will be adequately recorded.

The participant's data will be used in analyses that are in progress at the time of the withdrawal request, or that have been performed before the request being received by the sponsor. The participant's data will not be used in any new analyses started after the request is received.

Participants who withdraw should be encouraged to continue to be followed for reporting potential adverse events, and when possible, deliver a final milk sample.

Study personnel contact details to be used if participants want to withdraw from the study will be provided in the consent form.

5.6.2 Lost to Follow Up

If a participant/potential participant is not reachable, three attempts will be made to contact the participants. A participant is considered lost to follow-up if the participant is non-responsive after three attempts from the last established contact.

STUDY ASSESSMENTS AND PROCEDURES

6.1 Analysis of Drug Levels

Measurement of levocetirizine and cetirizine levels in milk will be carried out using a validated method consisting of liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS). The method will be developed and validated prior to the analysis by the Department of Pharmacy, Drug Delivery, Uppsala University (UPPS), Sweden.

The samples will be analysed by team members at the Department of Pharmacy, Drug Delivery, Uppsala University (UPPS), Sweden.

6.2 Pharmacokinetics Assessments

Measured milk drug concentrations will be analyzed using the pop PK approach and summarized to obtain a mean concentration-time profile. The pop PK model then allows retrieving individual pharmacokinetic parameters, and thus the most probable concentration-time profile for each patient included in the population.

Pharmacokinetic characterization of each participant will be carried out using population PK/PD parameter estimation programs such as NONMEN.

Pop PK will then be used to define the main pharmacokinetic parameters of the selected drugs along with their variability in milk, and to study the influence of co-factors on drug disposition in lactating mothers.

The obtained concentration-time profiles will be used to estimate the infant's exposure to the drug by simulating drug levels in milk under various conditions that encompass variability among mothers, as well as parameters linked to milk consumption.

The existing equilibrium between plasma and milk concentrations will allow estimating drug disposition in plasma, and the fraction of passage in the milk from the collected milk samples.²⁴

Therefore, the built model will estimate drug passage to human milk and retrieve the expected milk concentration-time profiles under the appropriate dosage regimen. The pharmacokinetic modeling procedure will be as follows:

First, a population pharmacokinetic model will be created from the data collected in milk. Several single and multi-compartment models will be compared to depict the drug while identifying the parameters responsible for the observed variations in the population of interest (i.e., statistical models).

The covariates will then be sequentially incorporated into the base model (i.e., structural plus error models) and retained in the model only if they reach statistical significance. The latter factors will then be combined, and only the most significant ones included to obtain the final covariate model.

The model will be validated using standard statistical techniques in pop PK and the results compared to the literature to detect and quantify the differences in drug disposition between lactating women and the general adult population.

Finally, concentration-time profiles of drugs in milk will be simulated according to different dosage regimens.

Milk concentration will be used to estimate the amount of the drug ingested by nursing infants according to the following equation²⁴:

^a**Note:** Dosing units [e.g., mcg, units, grams] may be changed as appropriate in the following equations:

Estimated daily infant dose via breast milk (mg/kg/day) = drug concentration in breast milk (mg/mL) x volume breast milk ingested (mL/kg/day)^a

^aWhen the actual volume of milk ingested by the infant is not known, 150 mL/kg/day will be used in the calculation (the amount assumed to be ingested by an exclusively breastfed infant)

Besides, the two following variables will be calculated:

Infant dose relative to the weight-adjusted maternal dose:

Relative infant dose (%) = estimated daily infant dose via breast milk (mg/kg/day) / maternal dose (mg/kg^b/day) x 100

^b**Note:** Calculation uses maternal dose per kg, not fixed dose; if maternal weight is unknown, 70 kg is being used in the calculations.

Infant dose relative to the used therapeutically for an infant of the same age (Hale, T. W., 2012):
Relative infant dose (%) = estimated daily infant dose via breast milk (mg/kg/day) / infant therapeutic dose (mg/kg/day) x 100

6.3 Study Assessments

6.3.1 Adverse Events Reporting

Potential adverse events in breastfed infants will be collected retrospectively by the mother once during the four days of milk sampling. The mother will specifically be asked close-ended questions about the following symptoms in the breastfed child the last three days: Drowsiness, sedation, poor feeding or refusal of the breast, rash, bruising or bleeding, constipation, diarrhea, stools with blood or abnormal color, fever.

6.4 Study Related Procedures

6.4.1 Milk Sampling

Milk sampling will be carried out at the study participant's home by the breastfeeding woman herself. Each participant will be asked to provide milk samples on four different days (Figure 1a). On day 1, participants will be asked to donate 6 milk samples at the following time points: 0t, 2t, 4t, 8t, 12t, 24t. Participants will also be asked to donate 1 milk sample on 3 other different days. It is up to each participant when the 3 other milk samples are taken, as long as the drug is taken for 2 consecutive days prior to milk sampling, and the whole process doesn't exceed 3 months due to study logistic reasons.

Each milk sample will be 20 ml collected in appropriate containers. It is required that the participant has been using the cetirizine/levocetirizine for at least two consecutive days before milk sampling to ensure steady-state. Although it is preferential that participants provide all requested milk samples, it is not a requirement. Delivering the first 6 milk samples from day 1 is sufficient for participants to be included in the study.

The participant will be provided with the milk collection kit and all the necessary equipment for the collection. Electric pumps of the same brand will be used for all participants. Sampling can be made irrespective of the time of drug intake for (levo)cetirizine.

6.4.2 Processing and Shipments of Milk Samples

Milk samples will be stored in a plastic container in the woman's freezer until all samples have been collected, then shipped in ice packs to the Uppsala Biobank, Uppsala, Sweden

(Registration number 827 at the Swedish Health and Social Care Inspectorate). Sample preparation and storage will be done at the Uppsala Biobank.

6.5 Administrative and General Procedures

6.5.1 Informed Consents

Informed consent will be obtained from each potential participant prior to participation in this clinical study. Informed consent forms (ICF) will be signed using an electronic ID. All ICFs and any other written patient material will be approved by the Regional Committees for Medical Research Ethics (REC) in advance of use. Three consent forms will be used in this study, one for the main study, which will be signed by the mother, one for the collection of health information about infants where both parents will sign on, and the third one is for storage of milk samples in the Uppsala Biobank for future biomedical research where the mother will sign on.

6.5.2 Collection of Health-Related Information

Participants will be asked to provide background and health-related information needed to develop the Pop PK model and calculate the RID.

Sociodemographic characteristics, breastfeeding practices, medical history, information about (levo)cetirizine intake, concomitant medication use, and infant's health information will be collected via the baseline questionnaire. The baseline questionnaire will be filled after the participant has consented to participate in the study.

General information about the drug's impact on the nursing infant and milk production will be collected via a follow-up questionnaire. The baseline questionnaire and the follow-up questionnaires will include the participants' full identity and represent the study's primary source document.

The collected health related information is in accordance to the FDA recommendation on the design of clinical lactation studies (2). FDA recommends collecting data about several groups of variables. Those variables can be classified into maternal factors (maternal weight, age, gestational age at delivery, stage of lactation, length of time postpartum, smoking, alcohol intake, concomitant drugs, ethnicity, race, and existing medical conditions), infant factors (age, weight, history of prematurity, drugs, existing medical conditions, ethnicity, and race), the exclusivity of breastfeeding, timing of milk sample in relation to the dose and days postpartum.² Moreover, two new assessments were recently recommended to be included in clinical lactation studies, collecting drug's effect on milk production and safety information in the nursing infants.

Collected data will be stored securely in the study database; Services for sensitive data (TSD) allow further analyses. TSD is a platform used by researchers at UiO. The database records will be identified only with the patient study number and initials.

7. REGULATORY, ETHICAL, AND STUDY OVERSIGHT CONSIDERATION

7.1 Code of Conduct

This clinical study will be conducted in compliance with local and national regulations, the International Council for Harmonization Good Clinical Practice (ICH-GCP), and the ethical principles in the Declaration of Helsinki.

Prior to starting the study, approval from the Regional Ethics Committee and Data Protection Officer at the University of Oslo (UiO) will be obtained. A Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) will be performed by UIO/study PI.

As confirmed by The Norwegian Medicines Agency (NoMA), the study is exempted from submission to NoMA, as no invasive interventional procedures will be performed in the study.

7.2 Direct Access to Source Data/Documents

The primary investigator will permit audits, REC review, and regulatory inspections, providing direct access to source data/documents.

7.3 Data Handling and Record-Keeping

Data collected will be processed, stored, and utilized in compliance with the EU general data protection regulation (GDPR)²⁵. Participants will be assigned a unique study ID. Personal information that can make participants identifiable will be stored at TSD, UIOs server for sensitive data. Only anonymous data will be shared with researched outside UIO.

Participants will be informed that the sponsor (ConcePTION) will use personal study-related data in accordance with local data protection law. Participants will also be oriented that collected data can be subject to audits and inspection from regulatory authorities, as needed.

Records and documents, including ICF will be retained for five years after study completion.

All data collected through the questionnaires will be stored at TSD, UIOs server for sensitive data.

Anonymous information from the analysis of (levo)cetirizine in breast milk will be stored at the bioanalytical center in Uppsala, and shared with the pop PK expert group in ConcePTION for pop PK analysis. Information that can make participants identifiable will not be shared the researched outside UiO. Processed anonymous, aggregated data, i.e., bioanalysis results, PopPK modeling, will be stored at the central ConcePTION database in Utrecht.

Breast milk samples will not be used for other purposes than stated in this study without agreement with UIO, approval from the ethics committee, and informed consent from the patients.

7.4 Source Documents

Source documents in this study are the electronic questionnaires that will be stored at TSD, UIOs server for sensitive data.

Source documents should be contemporaneous, original, accurate, and complete. Changes to source data should be traceable.

7.5. Insurances

All patients in Norway are entitled to compensation for patient injury in accordance with the Patient Injuries Act.

8. PUBLICATION POLICY

The Sponsor commits to publishing the study's results according to the pre-specified plans for data analysis.

The study will be registered in the Clinical Trials Register prior to its start (clinicaltrials.gov.) The results of the study will be published as scientific papers in peer-reviewed journals. Preparation of such manuscripts will be prepared independently by the investigators and in accordance with International Council for Harmonization Good Clinical Practice (ICH-GCP), and the ethical principles in the Declaration of Helsinki.

The following funding disclosure will be used:

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Prediction of venlafaxine exposure trough breastfeeding

Research legislation:	Ordinance on human research with the exception of Clinical trials (HRO) [1].
Type of Research Project:	Research project involving human subjects
Risk Categorisation:	Provide Risk category A acc. to ordinance HRO Art.7
Sponsor:	Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Vaudois, CHUV (BPR@CHUV.CH)
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The project leader is a qualified individual by education and training (HRO Art.4), who is responsible for the whole project.

PROTOCOL SIGNATURE FORM

Study Title Prediction of venlafaxine exposure trough breastfeeding

The project leader has approved the protocol version **05, 09th july 2021**, and confirms hereby to conduct the project according to the protocol, the Swiss legal requirements [1, 2], current version of the World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki [3] and the principles and procedures for integrity in scientific research involving human beings.

Project leader and Sponsor representative:

Docteure Alice Panchaud

Département des centres interdisciplinaires, Service de Pharmacie, CHUV, Rte Bugnon 17, 1011 Lausanne-CHUV.

Date:

09.07.2021

Signature :

Sponsor: Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Vaudois (CHUV)

DOCUMENT HISTORY

PROTOCOL SUBMISSION AND AMENDMENTS

Version	Change to previous version	Effective Date
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2.0	Revisions by <i>Bureau promoteur CHUV</i>	31/03/2021
3.0	Modifications based on comments from <i>Bureau promoteur CHUV</i>	12/04/2021
4.0	Modifications based on the comments of the CER-VD	03/06/2021
5.0	Modifications based on the comments of the CER-VD	09/07/2021

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GLOSSARY OF ABBREVIATIONS

CRF	Case report form
ESPGHAN	European Society of Paediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology and Nutrition
FDA	U.S. Food and Drug Administration
GDPR	EU general data protection regulation
HRA	Human Research Act
HRO	Ordinance on Human
PopPK	Population pharmacokinetic
SNRIs	Serotonin and norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors
SSRIs	Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors
WHO	World Health Organization

1 BACKGROUND AND PROJECT RATIONALE

1.1 Background

Several women may need to take medication while breastfeeding for acute or chronic diseases. The information on the milk transfer and safety of drugs in breastfed infants is however still largely missing for a majority of compounds [1,2,3]. Lack of information regarding milk transfer and safety of drugs in breastfed infants and the related fear of adverse events for the breastfed infant are some of the factors responsible for stopping prematurely breast-feeding or avoiding drug therapy [4]. Human milk represents the ideal primary source of nutrients, immunologic defences, and growth-promoting factors for term and preterm new-borns and provides the mother-infant dyad with major short- and long-term benefits [5,6,7]. Epidemiologic research shows that human milk and breastfeeding of infants provide advantages with regard to general health, growth, and development, while significantly decreasing the risk for a large number of acute and chronic diseases [1,8]. Therefore, the World Health Organization (WHO) recommend exclusive breastfeeding up to 6 months of age and its continuation for 2 years and beyond [2,9]. The European Society of Paediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology and Nutrition (ESPGHAN) has also concluded that exclusive breastfeeding for about 6 months is a desirable goal [10]. Estimates of the prevalence of breastfeeding in Europe are highly variable, partly due to the lack of a standardized method of data collection [10]. Nevertheless, the data show that breastfeeding rates and practices are lower than those suggested by many professional organizations and scientific societies [10]. One of the reasons for not starting or stopping breastfeeding prematurely is the consumption of a drug therapy.

Pregnancy and postpartum are periods of increased psychological fragility [11]. It is reported in the literature that between 10 and 15% of mothers have postpartum depression, which can appear in the days following childbirth and up to one year later [12,13,14]. According to several studies, these depressed women tend to breastfeed their babies for shorter periods of time than those without depressive symptoms [15,16,17]. It has also been observed that maternal depression can affect the child's mental health and the mother-child bond [18]. It therefore appears necessary to manage and treat maternal depression during this particularly vulnerable period.

All antidepressants pass into breast milk, and most drug monographs advise against the use of this class of drugs during breastfeeding, but in practice these drugs are still often prescribed. Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) are the first choice of antidepressant treatment for pregnant and breastfeeding women [19,20]. Venlafaxine (antidepressant from the group of serotonin and norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (SNRIs)) may be an alternative to SSRIs, although its use is less well documented than SSRIs [19].

Any consumption of medication during breastfeeding requires an assessment of the benefit/risk ratio which takes into consideration the quantity of medication excreted in the milk, related to the degree of exposure in the child, among other criteria. Published evidence of safety of drugs during breastfeeding is rare. Current data and recommendations are limited by the lack of clinical studies conducted in lactating women, and very few studies have quantitatively measured the excretion of drugs into human milk [3]. Some studies have been published in recent years showing the transfer of antidepressants into breast milk [21]. However, it is difficult to compare their results because of the heterogeneity of the data [21]. The transfer of venlafaxine into breast milk has been little studied. The data collected on venlafaxine indicate that it appears to pose little risk during breastfeeding, although it is estimated that the child will be exposed to a slightly higher amount than for the majority of SSRIs [22].

Rational to use population pharmacokinetic

To allow the quantification of the excretion of venlafaxine into breastmilk on a population level, a population pharmacokinetic (PopPK) approach will be used to describe the drug and its active metabolite concentrations measured in breastmilk, and to predict the overall exposure of breastfed infants. Indeed, PopPK analyses are best suited for PK characterization in particular in vulnerable subjects (e.g. pregnant or breastfeeding women, infants) than traditional pharmacokinetic approaches, as they work even with few observations per individual collected in very heterogeneous settings (Figure 1) [23,38,39]. In addition, they allow for simple pharmacokinetic simulations and predictions, and they are less expensive than the traditional individual approach. This approach has already shown to be perfectly appropriate in describing milk drug levels in breastfeeding women and in simulating infant drug exposure [23,38,39].

As the figure below shows, the popPK methodology combines mathematical and statistical modelling to characterise the concentration-time profiles of drugs and, if available, their active metabolites together with the variability of the study population and allows the identification of the underlying factors responsible for the latter. In practice, all the available observations are pooled together (step A) and summarized by a typical concentration-time profile (i.e. the curve obtained with the population pharmacokinetic parameters) surrounded by a certain variability (step B). The approach helps identifying the individual characteristics contributing to the latter, and allows retrieving individual pharmacokinetic parameters, and thus the most probable concentration-time profile, of each patient included in the population (step C) [23,38,39].

Figure1: Schematic representation of the principles of a population pharmacokinetic analysis.

As blood is the usual biological matrix collected for PopPK studies, the pharmacokinetic behaviour of a drug is usually documented in plasma. However, if other biological matrices (i.e. milk, cerebrospinal fluid, sperm...) are accessible, the pharmacokinetic behaviour can also be documented in these compartments. This information can be particularly important to (i) define and understand the relationship between blood and some specific tissues and (ii) to determine the quantity of drug accumulated in these tissues during a predefined period. In our study, milk is an accessible matrix bringing information on infant's exposure to drug through breast milk.

In a second step, the developed PopPK model is used to simulate various conditions (e.g. change in mother's physiological characteristics, mother's drug doses, infant's milk consumption), making it possible to predict the median drug level in milk and its associated variability for each new condition.

Status of knowledge

The table below summarises the relevant information currently available in the literature on exposure to venlafaxine through breastfeeding.

Table 1: State of knowledge on the exposure of infants to venlafaxine during breastfeeding.

	Breast milk concentrations	Infant serum levels	Side effects in infants
Venlafaxine	Exposure of new-borns can change according to the dose and the galenic form used. In eleven women taking venlafaxine (1 immediate-release and 10 extended-release) the average RID ¹ was	The active metabolite of venlafaxine (O-demethylvenlafaxine) has often been found in the serum of breastfed infants ² . The venlafaxine concentrations found	Adverse effects on growth, sedation, weight gain, mental or psychomotor development have rarely been reported in the literature.

	8.1% (range 3.2-13.3%) [24,25,26,27,28,29].	in the literature are highly variable and depend on the maternal dose.	There was a reported case of a breastfed infant also exposed to venlafaxine in utero, who showed signs of restlessness, colic, drowsiness and insomnia [22]. One reported case of lethargy in the infant, the authors concluded that this could be due to venlafaxine in milk [30].
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¹ Estimation of the relative weight-adjusted infant dose (RID): RID is the infant's weight-adjusted relative dose, expressed as a percentage of the weight-adjusted maternal dose [31]. With low doses (RID values < 2-3%), breastfeeding is generally considered to be safe, with the exception of highly toxic agents, such as cytostatics, or psychotropics with long half-lives because of the risk of accumulation [31].

² Transfer of drug into breast milk does not necessarily present a health risk for the breastfed infant.

1.2 Project Rationale

The exposure of infants to drugs through breastmilk can be highly variable and depends on the dose ingested by the child along with the absorption, the distribution, the metabolism and the elimination of the drug by the child. Characterisation of this exposure is essential to provide recommendations for preventing toxicity in breastfed infants and assuring mother's adequate treatment. This can be achieved by assessing the physicochemical and pharmacokinetic properties of the drugs and inter-individual variability due to characteristics of the mothers and breastfed infants.

This study will allow supplying a European biobank located in Uppsala with samples of breast milk, from breastfeeding women taking venlafaxine provided by participants in Switzerland.

The table below summaries the collection procedure use for venlafaxine (Table 2).

Table 2: Summary of the approach used for venlafaxine

Drug	Sample collection centre	Type of matrices collected	Storage	Location of drug dosing	Location of population pharmacokinetic analysis
Venlafaxine	Lausanne/Switzerland	breast milk	Uppsala/Sweden	Uppsala/Sweden	Lausanne/Switzerland

An assessment of the feasibility of this approach will be performed to provide recommendations for future projects.

1.3 Risk Categorization

The patients included in the study will be followed for their pathologies by their prescribing physician. There will be no intervention on their ongoing treatment by design. Participants and their infants will not be exposed to any additional risk. The risk for this research project according to Art. 7 (ORH) is category A.

2 PROJECT OBJECTIVES AND DESIGN

2.1 Objectives

2.1.1 Primary objective

PopPK

The objective of this study is, using a PopPK modelling approach, to characterize the pharmacokinetics of venlafaxine and its active metabolite in breastfeeding women during the postpartum period in order to:

- determine, (i) the concentration-time profiles in milk and its associated variability and (ii) identify the factors explaining some of the inter-individual variability of the concentration-time profiles into breast milk;
- predict the daily dose ingested by the infant and its associated inter-individual variability in various simulated conditions (e.g. full or mixed breastfeeding; factors influencing infant drug exposure).

Feasibility and sustainability of milk studies on a European level

On the top of the PopPK oriented objectives, barriers and facilitators encountered during the enrolment, sampling and shipping phases of the study will be monitored.

2.1.2 Secondary objectives

Most studies focus on the measure of pharmacokinetic indices rather than their clinical relevance (i.e. pharmacokinetic-pharmacodynamic relationship). The secondary objective of this study is to monitor (i) the occurrence of predefined side effects in infants during the breastfeeding period, and (ii) the impact of mother's drug consumption on breast milk production.

In this study, the mother will be asked to complete two telephone questionnaires on infant health and breast milk production, the first during the sampling period and the second after two months (appendix 2). The monitoring will mainly concern infant drowsiness, lethargy, poor suckling ability, signs of dehydration, withdrawal symptoms, restlessness, infant colic, insomnia and decrease in milk production.

2.2 Endpoints

2.2.1 Primary Endpoint

PopPK

As previously mentioned, PopPK approach allows to characterise the typical concentration-time profile of venlafaxine and O-demethylvenlafaxine in milk and to identify the factors of variability between individuals. Based on this approach, it will be possible to determine:

- the typical concentration-time profiles in the milk for venlafaxine and its active metabolite and percentage of change in mother milk drug levels according to demographics and other co-factors (e.g. co-medications).
- the median dose ingested by the infant during breastfeeding as well as the associated inter-individual variability.

Feasibility and sustainability of milk studies on a European level

- Descriptive report on barriers and facilitators encountered during the enrolment, sampling and shipping phases of the study.

2.2.2 Secondary Endpoints

- Occurrence of predefined side effects in infants and of decrease of breast milk production recorded at sampling and 2 months later.

2.3 Project design

Prospective monocentre open-label observational study.

3 PROJECT POPULATION AND STUDY PROCEDURES

3.1 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

3.1.1 Inclusion Criteria

- Mothers \geq 18 years, under treatment by venlafaxine who breastfeed their child,

- Participation requires that the infant is > 4 weeks old,
- Ability to understand and willingness to sign a written informed consent document for milk withdrawal.

3.1.2 Exclusion Criteria

- Mothers <18 years of age,
- Mothers of infants with gestational age < 34 weeks,
- Mothers giving birth to twins,
- Mothers giving birth to infants with major malformations,
- Inability to communicate due to language problems for the mother,
- Participants with a socio-economic context making close monitoring of the child by the mother or a relative not possible.

3.2 Recruitment and informed consent procedure

Participants eligible for inclusion will be recruited through social media, selected websites directed towards pregnant and breastfeeding women and through advertisements on the website of patient organization. Patients wishing to participate in the study can contact us by phone or email (mentioned in the study participation announcement). An initial telephone meeting will be arranged with the patient to provide detailed information about the study. For eligible patients wishing to participate, the information letter and two copies of the informed consent (appendix 1) with a stamped envelope will be sent by post. The mother will be given time to reflect and if she is still interested in participating in the study, she will be asked to return the 2 signed copies of the consent form. We will then send back a copy of the consent after it has been signed by the principal investigator of the study.

3.3 Study procedures

3.3.1 Time frame of the study

After agreement of the ethic committee and informed consent of the patients, the inclusion of eligible subjects will be made over a period of 12 months.

3.3.2 Milk sampling

Milk sampling will be carried out by the participant herself with a breast pump and should take place after the development of mature milk (about two weeks after delivery, so guaranteed by the enrolment of mothers with infants > 4 weeks). Sampling and infant health details will be collected through telephone questionnaire. The participant will be asked to provide between 1 and 4 samples of 20 ml of breast milk. Precise and detailed instructions will be given to the mother prior to collection. The participant is advised to contact the study contact person if she encounters any problems during collection. She will be given a telephone number for prompt assistance. The participant will be provided with the milk collection kit and all the necessary equipment for the collection. Electric pumps of the same brand will be used for all participants. These pumps will be offered to participants.

This sampling can be made irrespective of time of drug intake, as a popPK approach will be used for data processing [34].

Table 3: Summary of pattern of use and sampling type of study drug

	half-life	pattern of use	sparse sampling
Venlafaxine	5h parent drug; 11h active metabolite ; 15-16h slow release form	chronic for 6 months and more	Sampling independent of timing of drug intake

3.3.3 Clinical information collection

Information relative to breastfeeding model (exclusive or mixed), drug intake (i.e. dosage, frequency of intake, treatment start or last change of dosage), maternal status (i.e. age, bodyweight, smoking, alcohol), weeks postpartum, and concomitant medications will be carefully recorded.

Clinical information regarding the infant will be gathered through a telephone questionnaire (presence of congenital malformations, body weight, numbers of stools, sleeping patterns, crying patterns).

In total, the patient will be asked to complete:

- A telephone form containing basic information, after confirming inclusion in the study and signing the informed consent.
- A sampling form the day of the milk sampling (between 1 and 4 forms depending on the number of samples taken). A telephone appointment will be arranged in advance depending on the participant's availability. The mother will receive a call on the day of the milk sampling (after the sampling).
- 2 follow-up forms on child's health, the first on the period of sampling and the second two months later.

All this information will be given to the participant during the first telephone contact (prior to inclusion), which will provide the patient with detailed information about the study.

3.3.4 Procedures for processing and shipping milk samples

The plastic bag containing the milk sample will be placed in the participant's freezer and stored at -20 C° until all samples have been collected and are then transported to Uppsala Biobank on ice. The patient will be asked not to store the milk samples in her freezer for more than 2 weeks.

Milk samples will be shipped to Uppsala according to the shipment procedure. All shipping materials will be provided to the mother and no personal data will appear in the shipping information. The only data that will appear in the samples received by the biobank will be the participant's code, the date and time of sampling, the date and time of the last venlafaxine intake and freezing time.

Sample preparation will be done at the Uppsala biobank.

3.3.5 Drug levels measurements

The measurement of drug levels in milk will be carried out by the team at the Uppsala bio-analytical center using a validated method of high-performance liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS/MS).

3.3.6 Flow chart / table of procedures and assessments

The flow chart of this study is described in the figure below.

Figure 2: The study's flowchart.

Steps 1 and 2 are detailed in the table below.

Table 4: Details of inclusion, sampling, data collection stages.

Step	procedure
Step 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Publication of announcements of participation in the study. - Interested parties contact us via telephone or email (provided in the advertisement). - Initial telephone contact will be made with the patient to explain the study in detail (transparent and detailed information will be provided). - If the person is interested, the letter of information and informed consent and a stamped envelope will be sent to her by post. - If the person still agrees to participate in the study after a reflection period, she will be asked to sign the 2 copies of the informed consent and return them by post.
Step 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - After confirmation of the inclusion criteria, a copy of the informed consent signed by the principal investigator of the study will be returned by post to the participant. This shipment will contain all the necessary materials for sampling and shipping the milk samples. Detailed instructions about sampling will be provided to the patient to perform the milk sampling herself, and a help number will be also provided. A paper allowing the participant to note the time of sampling and placing in the freezer and the time of the last medication taken will be added to this shipment. - The basic information questionnaire will be completed by telephone (during this communication a telephone appointment will be arranged for the day of sampling depending on the participant's availability). - Sampling will be done by the participant using the equipment provided. The participant will be asked to provide between 1 and 4 milk samples on different days. For each sample, the participant will be called during the day, according to her availability, to answer the sampling questionnaire. The participant will be asked to put the samples in her freezer (for a maximum of two weeks) and then proceed to send all the collected milk samples using the shipping kit provided (no personal information will be included on the shipping material. Only the participant's code, the time and date of sampling, the time of placing in the freezer, and the time and date of the last medication taken will be transmitted to the biobank. - The participant will also be asked to complete 2 telephone questionnaires regarding the health status of her baby (the first on the period of sampling and the second 2 months later).

3.4 Withdrawal and discontinuation

The subjects may withdraw from the study if they decide to do so, at any time and irrespective of the reason, or this may be the investigator's decision. All dropouts will be adequately recorded by the investigator when considered as confirmed.

Subjects who have been withdrawn from the study cannot be re-included in the study. Their inclusion and study number must not be reused. All data that have been previously collected for these subjects will be kept and used for the evaluation of relevant endpoints.

The only criterion for discontinuation of the study is the discontinuation of the treatment prior completing the milk sampling time. In this case, the participant will be asked to inform the study contact person in order to withdraw from the study. If one or more samples have been collected before the end of the treatment, the mother will be asked to send them to the biobank. The clinical data collected before the end of the treatment will be stored in the secure network of the CHUV. All this information will be reminded to the participants at the time of withdrawal from the study.

4 STATISTICS AND METHODOLOGY

4.1 Statistical analysis plan

The population pharmacokinetic approach will be used, this analysis is described in section 4.3.

4.2 Determination of sample size

There is no precise rule in PopPK analysis regarding the calculation of the number of individuals and the number of samples needed per individual. This number can be very variable and depends on several factors such as: the available information on the pharmacokinetic behaviour of the molecule (single compartment or bi-compartmental model...), the route of administration ...

The figure below is a mathematical representation of a PopPK model (Figure 3). The construction of a good model requires the construction of a structural model that describes the median kinetic profile of the molecule and a statistical model that describes the variability around this median profile (weight, sex, age, renal and hepatic function...) [33].

$$\begin{cases} Y_{ij} = f(t_{ij}, \psi_i) + f(t_{ij}, \psi_i)\varepsilon_{ij} \\ \psi_i = g(X_i, \theta) + \eta_i \end{cases}$$

Structural model (red arrow)
Statistical model (intra-individual variability) (blue arrow)
Statistical model (inter-individual variability) (green arrow)

Y_{ij} : jth concentration measured on the ith individual at the instant t_{ij}
 ψ_i : pharmacokinetic parameters of the ith individual
 ε_{ij} : standard Gaussian random variables
 X_i : covariates explaining the variation in ψ_i from one individual to another

Figure 3: mathematical description of a PopPK model [33]

For venlafaxine and all marketed drugs, we have all the information concerning the pharmacokinetic profile of the molecule, which is why we consider that a limited number of sparse samples per person (between 1 and 4 milk samples), collected on a medium population (about 20 individuals) is sufficient to build a good population pharmacokinetic model.

4.3 Data analysis

As already mentioned, the pharmacokinetic characterisation of the lactating women population, will be achieved through PopPK approach, that is based on non-linear mixed effect modelling techniques. These analyses will be carried out using population PK/PD parameter estimation programs such as NONMEN, MONOLIX [34,35]. PopPK allows estimating both fixed (i.e. invariant) population parameters and random effects (i.e. inter-individual and residual variability) [23,36] by grouping all the samples collected in the study population, according to a schedule that can be very flexible, as previously mentioned [37,38,39].

Figure 4: Schematic representation of the pharmacokinetic disposition of a drug and its active metabolites in plasma and breast milk after oral administration.

PopPK will then be used to define the main pharmacokinetic parameters of venlafaxine and its active metabolite along with their variability in milk, and to study the influence of co-factors on drugs disposition in the population of lactating mothers. This approach will combine drug and O-demethylvenlafaxine data collected in milk, while integrating clinical, demographic and environmental aspects and quantifying variability between individuals, with the aim of estimating the exposure of infants to drug and the inter-individual variability.

The kinetic of venlafaxine will be characterised in milk. Because of the existing equilibrium between plasma and milk concentrations, we can consider that the concentrations of the drug and its active metabolite in milk is a fraction of their plasma concentrations, as previously reported [38,39] and illustrated in figure 2. In addition, the concentrations collected in milk will allow getting information on drugs dispositions also in plasma by estimation of drug and metabolite clearances.

The analysis will consist first in building the model using data collected in milk and second in using this model to retrieve the expected milk concentration-time profiles under several dosage regimens. Pharmacokinetic modelling will be done as follows:

A population pharmacokinetic model will be created from the data collected in milk following the same strategy presented by E. Weisskopf et al [39]. First, many single and multi-compartment models will be compared to predict the disposition of venlafaxine and its active metabolite, while identifying the parameters responsible for the observed variations in the population of interest (i.e. statistical models). This model will also provide information on the disposition of medicinal products in plasma due to the assumed proportionality between the quantities of medicinal products in milk and plasma. The covariates will then be sequentially incorporated into the base model (i.e. structural plus error models) and will only be retained if they reach statistical significance. The latter factors will then be combined and only the most significant ones will be retained to obtain the final covariates model. In the case where the data collected do not allow us to establish our own model, there will be a rigorous selection from the literature of a model built with a population similar to that of this study (i.e. healthy women). This model will then be exploited using a Bayesian approach in order to deduce the individual pharmacokinetic parameters of each breastfeeding woman in plasma, and then extended to characterize milk concentrations. It should be noted that the ratio between the concentration of the venlafaxine metabolite and that of the parent drug will identify the CYP2D6 metabolism of the patients. This information will also be integrated in the model to assess the differences in venlafaxine PK due to CYP2D6.

This model will be validated using standard statistical techniques in PopPK and the results compared to the literature to detect and quantify the differences in drugs disposition between lactating women and general adult population.

Finally, concentration-time profiles of drug/metabolite in milk will be simulated according to different dosage regimens. This will allow us to calculate the daily dose for the infant that is equivalent to the dose of drug ingested by an exclusively breastfed infant for each mother-infant pair and expressed in mg/k/d using the following equation [38,39]:

$$\text{daily infant dosage} = \sum_{i=1}^n C_{\text{milk}}^i \times V_{\text{milk}}$$

Where C_{milk}^i is the simulated drug concentration in milk at the i^{th} feeding time, n is the daily feeding frequency and V_{milk} is the ingested milk volume by a suckling child during a feeding occasion [39].

5 REGULATORY ASPECTS AND SAFETY

5.1 Local regulations / Declaration of Helsinki

This research project will be conducted in accordance with the protocol, the Declaration of Helsinki [3], the principles of Good Clinical Practice, the Human Research Act (HRA) and the Human Research Ordinance (HRO) [1] as well as other locally relevant regulations.

The Project Leader acknowledges his responsibilities as both the Project Leader and the sponsor.

5.2 Notification of safety and protective measures (HRO Art. 20)

The project leader is promptly notified (within 24 hours) if immediate safety and protective measures have to be taken during the conduct of the research project. The Ethics Committee will be notified via BASEC of these measures and of the circumstances necessitating them within 7 days.

5.3 Serious events (HRO Art. 21)

If a serious event occurs, the research project will be interrupted and the Ethics Committee notified on the circumstances via BASEC within 7 days according to HRO Art. 21¹.

5.4 Amendments

Substantial changes to the project set-up, the protocol and relevant project documents will be submitted to the Ethics Committee for approval according to HRO Art. 18 before implementation. Exceptions are measures that have to be taken immediately in order to protect the participants.

5.5 End of project

Upon project completion or discontinuation, the Ethics Committee is notified within 90 days.

5.6 Insurance

In the event of project-related damage or injuries, the CHUV will be liable, except for damages that are only slight and temporary; and for which the extent of the damage is no greater than would be expected in the current state of scientific knowledge (Art. 12 HRO).

¹ A serious event is defined as any adverse event where it cannot be excluded, that the event is attributable to the sampling of biological material or the collection of health-related personal data, and which:

- requires inpatient treatment not envisaged in the protocol or extends a current hospital stay;
- results in permanent or significant incapacity or disability; or
- is life-threatening or results in death.

6 FURTHER ASPECTS

This study will be conducted in accordance with the principles laid down by the 18th World Medical Assembly (Helsinki, 1964), the ICH Recommendations for Good Clinical Practice (GCP). The informed consent must be obtained from each potential participant prior to participation.

This study has no influence on the therapeutic care of children and their mothers. No invasive interventions will be carried out. The risks for the child are no higher than those generally incurred when introducing treatment to a breastfeeding patient.

The protocol will be registered in EudraCT.

6.1 Benefit/risk assessment

There will be no remuneration of participants in this study. The milk pumps used by the participants will be offered to them. There are some risks associated with the use of breast pumps: Sensation of pain during use, possible nipple lesions (cracking, bruising or bleeding), occurrence of breast milk confusion syndrome (this syndrome occurs when a bottle of milk is given to a breastfed baby and the baby no longer wants to suck).

All this information will be clearly stated in the patient information letter and remind the person by telephone.

7 QUALITY CONTROL AND DATA PROTECTION

7.1 Quality measures

For quality assurance the Ethics Committee may visit the research sites. Direct access to the source data and all project related files and documents must be granted on such occasions.

7.2 Data recording and source data

Sampling details and health related details of the mother and child (co-medication taken by the patient and relevant information such as side effects) are collected by telephone (Appendix 2, 3, 5).

All data collected by telephone will be entered directly into REDcap and will be hosted in the secure network of the CHUV. The database records will be identified only with the patient study number using following pattern *ven01, ven02, ven03, ..., venxx*.

7.3 Confidentiality and coding

Project data will be handled with uttermost discretion and is only accessible to authorized personnel who require the data to fulfil their duties within the scope of the research project. On the CRFs and other project specific documents, participants are only identified by a unique participant number. The investigators will take the necessary measures to maintain confidentiality and prevent access to the data by any other unauthorised person. Patients will be informed that their inclusion in this study will mean that coded data concerning them and their child will be seen by other person than those involved in primary care. Personal information that can make participants identifiable will be stored in a password-protected folder on the CHUV's secure server for ten years (locally). this subject identification log will be the only document that links the patient's identity to the code used in the study. this document will contain the patient's name and telephone number. This document can only be consulted by the principal investigator of the study. Participants will be assigned a unique code.

Biological material in this project is not identified by participant name but by a unique participant number. Biological material is appropriately stored in a restricted area only accessible to authorized personnel (Biobanking regulations).

7.4 Retention and destruction of study data and biological material

Records and documents will be retained for ten years after study completion password-protected folder on the CHUV's secure server for ten years (locally).

Information from the analysis of venlafaxine in breast milk will be stored at the bioanalytical center in Uppsala and shared with the project group for PopPK analysis.

The biological material will be stored for ten (10) years in the Biobank and any use of the material during this period for other research will be subject to prior authorisation by the Vaud Ethics Commission (CER-VD). After ten years, the material will be destroyed. If the participant has not given permission for further use, the milk will only be used for this study and then destroyed.

8 FUNDING / DATA SHARING / PUBLICATION / DECLARATION OF INTEREST

Funding for this project is provided by H2020-Grant - *Innovative medicine initiative call 13 topic 9* « ConcePTION ». The cost of the pumps provided to the mothers is included in this budget.

Authorship (including that of registry committee members) in scientific publications will have to satisfy the conditions of the Uniform Requirements for Manuscripts Submitted to Biomedical Journals (www.icmje.org/icmje-recommendations.pdf).

We declare no potential conflicts of interest.

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10 APPENDIX

10.1 Appendix 1: Invitation to participate and Informed consent

10.2 Appendix 2: Patient baseline information form

PREDICTION OF VENLAFAXINE EXPOSURE THROUGH BREASTFEEDING
FORMULAIRE: INFORMATIONS DE BASE

Code de la participante:

Date:

MERE

Age:ans

 Niveau de formation:

 Scolarité obligatoire

 Degré secondaire

 Degré tertiaire (haute école, université)

Ethnie:

 Taille: cm

 Poids: Kg

 Tabac: cigarettes/jour

 Alcool: unités*/jour *unité=1 verre de vin ou 2.5dl de bière

Diagnostic

Indication pour le traitement de venlafaxine (Efexor ER ou générique)?

- Troubles anxieux
 Dépression
 Troubles de panique
 Phobie sociale
 Autre, précisez svp:

 Diagnostic fait le:

 Réponse au traitement médicamenteux:

 satisfaisante

 partielle

 absente

 Date du dernier contrôle médical: Ex:03.03.2019

 Autres problèmes de santé ? oui non

Si oui, lesquels:

Traitement venlafaxine (Efexor ER® ou générique)

 Début du traitement (Efexor ER®/générique)? Ex:03.03.2020

Si prise de générique, lequel:

 Quel dosage ?

 37.5 mg

 75 mg

 150 mg

 Nombre de gélules par prise: gélules

Merci d'indiquer la date et l'heure de la dernière prise médicamenteuse

 Ex:03.03.2020 Ex:10:15

Autres traitements

 Autres traitement? oui non

Si oui, nom, dose et durée de traitement:

 Consommation de médicaments naturels / compléments alimentaires? oui non

Si oui, préciser le nom du produit et la fréquence de consommation:.....

Enfant

 L'enfant est né à la ^{ème} semaine de grossesse

 Sexe de l'enfant: masculin féminin

 Accouchement de jumeaux? oui non

 Poids de l'enfant à la naissance: gr

Présence de malformation congénitale? oui Précisez:
 non

Présence de problèmes de santé? oui Précisez:
 non

L'enfant consomme-t-il des médicaments?

oui nom du produit et dose journalière:.....
 non

Alimentation de l'enfant

Premier enfant allaité A déjà allaité un/des enfant(s) précédemment

Combien de fois par jour l'enfant est-il allaité ? x/jour

Type d'allaitement Exclusif
 Mixte

Allaitement exclusif jusqu'au:

Lait matéernisé: Ex: Aptamil

Problèmes d'allaitement?

oui Précisez:
 non

problèmes d'alimentation chez l'enfant ?

oui Précisez:
 non

10.3 Appendix 3: Sampling form

Centre hospitalier
universitaire vaudois

PREDICTION OF VENLAFAXINE EXPOSURE THROUGH BREASTFEEDING

FORMULAIRE D'ECHANTILLONAGE DE LAIT (1x20ml)

Code de la participante:

Date:

MERE

Age:ans

Alimentation de l'enfant

Type d'allaitement Exclusif

Mixte

Allaitement exclusif jusqu'au:

Lait matéernisé: Ex: Aptamil

Traitement venlafaxine (Efexor ER® / générique)

Dose journalière: mg/jour

Merci d'indiquer la date et l'heure de la dernière prise du médicament

Ex:03.03.2020

Ex:10:15

Historique de prises du traitement de venlafaxine (Efexor ER® / générique) dans les 10 jours précédant l'échantillonnage:

	j-10	j-9	j-8	j-7	j-6	J-5	J-4	J-3	J-2	J-1	j0 Jour du prélèvement
Nombre de gélules par jour											
Date de la prise (Ex:03.03.2020)											
Heure de prise (Ex:10:15)											

Date et heure de l'échantillonnage de lait:

Ex:03.03.2021

Ex:10:15

Autres médicaments pris durant les 15 derniers jours:

oui Précisez:

non

10.4 Appendix 4: Milk sampling instruction

X

PREDICTION OF VENLAFAXINE EXPOSURE THROUGH BREASTFEEDING

Instructions : Echantillonnage et expédition des échantillons de lait

Liste du matériel fourni nécessaire pour le prélèvement et l'envoi des échantillons de lait maternel:

- Un tire-lait électrique (avec toutes les instructions nécessaires à l'assemblage et la désinfection du tire lait).
- Kit d'échantillonnage de lait :
 - Un sac de conservation de lait de 100 ml étiqueté avec votre code de participation.
 - Des compresses stériles
 - Une solution stérile de NaCl
 - Un paquet de serviettes en papier
 - Une solution désinfectante pour les mains
 - Un flacon de savon pour les mains
- Documents d'expédition et matériel nécessaire au transport

Veillez lire attentivement les instructions ci-dessous avant de prélever l'échantillon de lait.

1. Bien nettoyer le tire lait avant de procéder à l'échantillonnage.

2. Lavez-vous les mains à l'eau et au savon et séchez-les avec une serviette en papier

3. Utilisez les compresses stériles et la solution désinfectante fournies pour essuyer et nettoyer le sein dont vous allez pomper le lait en mouvements circulaires de l'intérieur vers l'extérieur en commençant par le mamelon.

4. Procédez au montage du tire-lait électronique conformément au manuel d'instructions fourni par le fabricant (Si vous avez besoin d'aide pour le montage veuillez contacter le numéro d'assistance que vous trouverez en bas de cette fiche).

5. Placez le tire lait de façon à ce que le mamelon soit au centre et tirez le lait du sein jusqu'à ce qu'il commence à se vider. Cela prend généralement 10 à 20 minutes.

6. Débranchez le récipient fourni avec le tire-lait.

7. Fermez le récipient et retourner doucement une dizaine de fois afin d'homogénéiser le lait.

8. Prélevez 20 ml de lait à partir du récipient à l'aide de la pipette graduée fournie.

9. Versez la quantité de lait maternel prélevée dans le sac de conservation de lait de 100 ml fourni, étiqueté avec votre code de participation. Si la vidange complète du sein a donné moins de 20 ml, versez ce lait dans le récipient. Il est important que le récipient ne soit pas rempli de plus de 60 ml car le lait se dilate lorsqu'il est congelé. Vous décidez de ce que vous voulez faire avec le lait restant.

10. Placez le sac de conservation de lait dans le congélateur (pendant maximum 2 semaines).

11. N'oubliez pas de noter l'heure d'échantillonnage et de mise dans le congélateur, ainsi que l'heure et la date de la dernière prise médicamenteuse.

12. Nettoyez et désinfectez le tire-lait selon les instructions.

13. Répondez aux questions du formulaire d'échantillonnage de lait: vous serez contacté par téléphone selon vos disponibilités dans la journée.

14. Le lait est stocké dans le congélateur jusqu'à ce que tous les échantillons aient été prélevés (entre 1 et 4 échantillons sont demandés).

15. Les échantillons seront envoyés sur glace au centre de recherche clinique d'Uppsala, en utilisant les sacs de glace, le matériel d'expédition et les documents d'expédition fournis au préalable. Tous les échantillons seront expédiés dans un même envoi.

Si vous avez besoin d'assistance appelez le

Pour toute autre question veuillez contacterau

10.5 Appendix 5: Infant health status questionnaire

PREDICTION OF VENLAFAXINE EXPOSURE THROUGH BREASTFEEDING
Formulaire de suivi de l'état de santé de l'enfant

Code de la participante:

Date:

Ce formulaire doit ainsi être rempli lors de du premier échantillonnage de lait et 2 mois après.

Pédiatre

Nom, prénom:

Adresse:

Tel:

Mère

Age: ans

 Tabac: cigarettes/jour

 Alcool: unités*/jour

*unité=1 verre de vin ou 2.5dl de bière

Dosage actuel de venlafaxine (Efexor ER/ générique) ?

 37.5 mg

 75mg

 150mg

 Combien de gélules par jour: gélules

Merci d'indiquer la date et l'heure de la dernière prise du médicament

Ex:03.03.2020

Ex:10:15

Combien de fois par jour l'enfant est-il allaité ?

 x/jour

 Type d'allaitement Exclusif

 Mixte

Allaitement exclusif jusqu'au:

Lait matérnisé: Ex: Aptamil

Baisse perçue de la production de lait maternel?

 oui Précisez:

 non

Enfant

 Taille: cm

 Poids: Kg

L'enfant consomme-t-il des médicaments/compléments/phytothérapie?

 oui si oui, nom du produit et dose journalière:

 non

Observation de l'état de santé de l'enfant au cours de ces 14 derniers jours

 Agitation

 Pleurs excessifs

 Irritabilité

 La somnolence

 Insomnie

 Changements dans la fréquence et la consistance des selles

 Symptômes de coliques

 Régurgitation/vomissement

 Difficultés d'alimentation

 Faible capacité d'allaitement

 Perte de poids

 Prise de poids

 Signes de déshydratation

 Éruption cutanée

 Fourrure de la langue

- Apparition d'infections chez l'enfant
 - Autre, précisez :
-

**Evaluation of amoxicillin diffusion in breast milk
according to a population pharmacokinetic approach**

CONCEPTION-AMOX

Sponsor code: RC31/21/0217

**INTERVENTIONAL RESEARCH PROTOCOL INVOLVING THE
HUMAN PERSON (*category 1*)**

Version no. 1.1 of August 16th, 2021

Number EudraCT: 2021-002247-30

This interventional research obtained funding from IMI (Innovative Medicines Initiative).

Sponsor:

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**This protocol was designed and written from version 3.0 of 01/02/2017
of the GIRCI SOHO model protocol**

HISTORY OF PROTOCOL UPDATES

VERSION	DATE	REASON FOR UPDATE
1.0	07/04/2021	Submission for CPP and ANSM
1.1	16/08/2021	Responses to CPP questions

PROTOCOL SIGNATURE PAGE

**Evaluation of amoxicillin diffusion in breast milk
according to a population pharmacokinetic approach
CONCEPTION-AMOX
Sponsor code: RC31/21/0217**

Sponsor

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ANSM	French National Agency for Medicines and Health Products Safety
CPP	Committee for the Protection of Persons
AE	Adverse Event
SAE	Serious Adverse Event
SAR	Serious Adverse Reaction
SUSAR	Suspected Unexpected Serious Adverse Reaction
PK	Pharmacokinetic
PopPK	Population pharmacokinetic

1. SUMMARY OF THE RESEARCH

SPONSOR	University Hospital Toulouse FRANCE
COORDINATING INVESTIGATOR	Pr. Peggy GANDIA - Head of the Pharmacokinetics and Toxicology Laboratory, Federal Institute of Biology 330-avenue de Grande Bretagne 31059 Toulouse, France Phone: 05 67 69 03 83 E-mail: gandia.p@chu-toulouse.fr - UMR 1436-INTHERES, Toulouse Veterinary School
TITLE	CONCEPTION-AMOX Evaluation of amoxicillin diffusion in breast milk according to a population pharmacokinetic approach
JUSTIFICATION/ CONTEXT	<p>Current knowledge in terms of the use of authorized drugs during breastfeeding although very reassuring, are limited by the lack of clinical studies conducted in breastfeeding women. As a consequence, this absence of certainties leads to premature discontinuation of breastfeeding in a large population of breastfeeding women. Nevertheless, the latter has well-known benefits in terms of growth and development, while considerably reducing the risk of emergence of acute and/or chronic pathologies. It is for all these reasons that the World Health Organization (WHO) and the European Society of Pediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology And Nutrition (ESPGHAN) recommend exclusive breastfeeding up to the age of 6 months and its maintenance 1 to 2 years.</p> <p>However, any drug consumption during breastfeeding requires an evaluation of the benefit/risk ratio which takes into account an evaluation of the degree of exposure of the child (i.e., quantity ingested by the infant) and the associated clinical manifestations. Thereby current available data and recommendations deserve to be further documented in order to optimize the management of amoxicillin intake and breastfeeding to avoid any exposure, even minimal, which could have a role in the future development of allergy, intolerances or imbalance of the microbiota.</p>
OBJECTIVES	<p>The main objective of this study is to describe the pharmacokinetics of amoxicillin in lactating women, through the use of a population pharmacokinetic model, in order to (i) determine the kinetic profile of amoxicillin in milk and its variability, (ii) identify the factors explaining this variability and (iii) predict the daily dose ingested by the infant and its associated variability according to different dosage regimens applied to the mother.</p> <p>The secondary objectives are to monitor (i) the occurrence of predefined adverse reactions in infants during the lactation period, and (ii) the impact of amoxicillin consumption on breast milk production.</p>
EVALUATION CRITERIA	<p>As previously mentioned, PopPK approach allow to characterise the median concentration-time profile of a drug in different matrices (i.e., plasma, milk) and to identify the factors of variability between individuals. Based on this approach, it will be possible to determine (i) the median area under the plasma drug concentration-time curve in mother milk for amoxicillin and percentage of change in mother milk drug levels according to demographics and other co-factors (e.g. co-medications) as well as (ii) the median dose of amoxicillin ingested during breastfeeding by the new-born as well as the associated inter-individual variability, in various simulated conditions (e.g., full or mixed breastfeeding; factors influencing infant drug exposure).</p>

<p>OUTLINE OF THE RESEARCH</p>	<p>Communications will be available on the <i>Leche League</i> website, in Toulouse university hospital center and Paris Necker milk bank (Appendix 2) to inform nursing mothers about our study. If interested, the breastfeeding mother taking amoxicillin will be put in touch with a doctor investigator participating to the study in order to explain our study, its objectives, to check the inclusion criteria and to provide the Patient Information and Informed Consent form that must be signed before any examination. The investigator doctor could also propose his/her own patients to participate to the study if the inclusion criteria are checked and if the latter is voluntary. During the study, 2 types of samples will be taken over the same time slots in breastfeeding mothers treated with amoxicillin for at least 2 days:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 breast milk collections of about 20 ml each made using an electric breast pump provided to the participant. - 3 blood samples of approximately 5 ml each. <p>These collections/samples must be taken 3 times in order to be able to follow the evolution of the concentrations of amoxicillin in the milk and blood over a single day during the interval between two intakes. As the drug in the breast compartment (i.e., milk) is in instantaneous equilibrium with the mother's blood compartment as previously described in mammal animals, same time slots are applied for both matrices:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 15-30 min after taking amoxicillin. - 1-2 hours after taking amoxicillin. - 3-4 hours after taking amoxicillin. <p>From the concentrations measured in plasma and milk, a population pharmacokinetic model will be developed.</p> <p>Adverse effects related to amoxicillin in infants will be sought in the form of a paper questionnaire submitted to mothers the day of the sampling and in the form of telephone follow-up a week later.</p>
<p>INCLUSION CRITERIA</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mothers over 18, orally treated with amoxicillin alone or associated with clavulanic acid according to a dosing regimen depending on the infection and in accordance with the recommendations of the Marketing Authorization (i.e., a dose ranging from 750 mg to 6 g per day) for at least 2 days, breastfeeding their child, - Participation requires that breastfeeding has been started for at least 2 weeks after childbirth (in order to sample mature milk) and that the infant is more than 4 weeks old, - Affiliation to the social security scheme or equivalent, - Ability to understand and willingness to sign a written Informed Consent document.
<p>EXCLUSION CRITERIA</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Infants born prematurely (i.e., gestational age of less than 34 weeks) or requiring appropriate medical supervision or the support of a team of social workers, - Mothers who have given birth to twins, - Inability to communicate with mother due to language problems, - Patient subject to a legal protection order (curatorship or tutorship)
<p>RESEARCH TREATMENT/ STRATEGIES/ PROCEDURES</p>	<p>Amoxicillin is usually prescribed as part of routine care by a general practitioner, alone or in combination with clavulanic acid, to mainly treat β-hemolytic strep throat, infections of the genitourinary tract as well as ear, nose and throat infections. In current practice, the most frequently found oral dosing regimen is 2 to 3g per day for 7 days including in lactating women.</p>
<p>STUDY SIZE</p>	<p>25 breastfeeding women will be included both in Toulouse and Paris. The repartition between centers won't necessarily be homogeneous and will depend on the inclusion rate in each center.</p>
<p>DURATION OF THE RESEARCH</p>	<p>Duration of the inclusion period: 1 year. Participation duration of each participant: 1 week. Total duration of the research: 1 year + 1 week.</p>

<p>STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF THE DATA</p>	<p>A PopPK model will be created based on plasma and milk concentrations of amoxicillin. This model will be validated taking into consideration the usual criteria in PK modelling (objective function, AIC, BIC, bootstrap, visual predictive check).</p>
<p>EXPECTED BENEFITS</p>	<p>Based on the plasma and milk concentrations, a PopPK model will be performed (i) to document the average and individual exposure to amoxicillin in milk, (ii) to identify the factors explaining the inter-individual pharmacokinetic variability in milk and (iii) to estimate exposure to amoxicillin in milk according to different dosage schedules. This study will complement the clinical data on amoxicillin in breastfed new-borns.</p>

ABSTRACT

This research has been registered at <http://www.clinicaltrials.gov/>.

Evaluation of amoxicillin diffusion in breast milk according to a population pharmacokinetic approach CONCEPTION-AMOX

University Hospital Toulouse is the sponsor of this research

Brief summary: Based on plasma and milk concentrations, a PopPK model will be performed (i) to document the average and individual exposure to amoxicillin in milk, (ii) to identify the factors explaining the inter-individual pharmacokinetic variability and (iii) to determine the daily dose ingested by the infant and its variability for different dosage regimens applied to the mother. The secondary objectives are to monitor (i) predefined adverse reactions in infants and (ii) the impact on milk production.

Detailed description: This study will complement the clinical data on amoxicillin in breastfed new-borns considering that current knowledge in terms of authorized drugs use during breastfeeding is not sufficient to guarantee the child absence of exposure, even minimal. As a consequence, this lack of certainties leads to premature discontinuation of breastfeeding, well known to be beneficial for the breastfed new-borns. Amoxicillin, prescribed alone or with clavulanic acid at 2 to 3g per day for 7 days, including in lactating women, is mainly used to treat β -hemolytic strep throat, infections of the genitourinary tract as well as ear, nose and throat infections.

Outcomes: PopPK approach allow to characterise the median concentration-time profile of a drug in different matrices (i.e., plasma, milk) and to identify the factors of variability between individuals. Based on this approach, it will be possible to determine (i) the median area under the plasma drug concentration-time curve in mother milk for amoxicillin and percentage of change according to demographics and other co-factors as well as (ii) the median dose of amoxicillin ingested during breastfeeding by the new-born and its inter-individual variability, in various simulated conditions.

Study design: During the study, 2 types of samples (blood and milk) will be taken in breastfeeding mothers treated with amoxicillin for at least 2 days. These samples must be taken 3 times in order to be able to follow the evolution of the amoxicillin concentrations in the milk and blood over a single day during the interval between 2 intakes. As the drug in milk is in instantaneous equilibrium with the mother's blood compartment as previously described in mammal animals, same time slots are applied for both matrices. Adverse effects related to amoxicillin in infants will be sought in the form of a paper questionnaire submitted to mothers the day of the sampling and in the form of telephone follow-up a week later.

Eligibility criteria:

- Inclusion criteria: mother over 18, orally treated with amoxicillin alone or associated with clavulanic acid according to a dosing regimen depending on the infection and in accordance with the recommendations of the Marketing Authorization (i.e., a dose ranging from 750 mg to 6 g per day) for at least 2 days and breastfeeding their child, breastfeeding started for at least 2 weeks after childbirth (mature milk) and the infant is more than 4 weeks old, affiliation to the social security scheme or equivalent and ability to understand and willingness to sign a written Informed Consent document.
- Exclusion criteria: infants born prematurely (i.e., gestational age of less than 34 weeks) or requiring appropriate medical supervision or the support of a team of social workers, mothers who have given birth to twins and inability to communicate with mother due to language problems.

Number of subjects: 25 breastfeeding women will be included both in Toulouse and Paris. The repartition between centers won't necessarily be homogeneous and will depend on the inclusion rate in each center.

Statistical analysis: To answer the principal objective, a PopPK model will be created based on plasma and milk concentrations of amoxicillin. This model will be validated taking into consideration the usual criteria in PK modelling (objective function, AIC, BIC, bootstrap, visual predictive check). To answer the secondary objectives, the number, the mean and the standard deviation of (i) predefined side effects in infants' occurrence and (ii) decrease of breast milk production recorded at sampling and a week later.

Keywords: *amoxicillin, population pharmacokinetic model, breastfeeding.*

2. SCIENTIFIC JUSTIFICATION AND GENERAL DESCRIPTION

2.1. CURRENT STATE OF KNOWLEDGE

2.1.1. ON THE MILK TRANSFER OF DRUGS

Several women may need to take medication while breastfeeding for acute or chronic diseases. The information on the milk transfer and safety of drugs in breastfed infants is however still largely missing for a majority of compounds [1][2][3]. Lack of information regarding milk transfer, safety of drugs and the related fear of adverse events for the breastfed infant are some of the factors responsible for stopping prematurely breastfeeding or avoiding drug therapy [4]. Human milk represents the ideal primary source of nutrients, immunologic defences, and growth-promoting factors for term and preterm new-borns and provides the mother-infant dyad with major short- and long-term benefits [5][6][7]. Epidemiologic research shows that human milk and breastfeeding of infants provide advantages with regard to general health, growth, and development, while significantly decreasing the risk for a large number of acute and chronic diseases [1][8]. Therefore, the World Health Organization (WHO) recommend exclusive breastfeeding up to 6 months of age and its continuation 1 to 2 years thereafter [2][9]. The European Society of Paediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology And Nutrition (ESPGHAN) has also concluded that exclusive breastfeeding for about 6 months is a desirable goal [10]. Estimates of the prevalence of breastfeeding in Europe are highly variable, partly due to the lack of a standardized method of data collection [10]. Nevertheless, the data show that breastfeeding rates and practices are lower than those suggested by many professional organizations and scientific societies [10]. One of the reasons for premature breastfeeding interruption is the introduction of a drug therapy. Any consumption of medication during breastfeeding requires an assessment of the benefit/risk ratio, which takes into consideration the quantity of medication excreted in the milk, an evaluation of the degree of exposure in the child, among other criteria. Published evidence of drugs safety during breastfeeding is rare. Current data and recommendations are limited by the lack of clinical studies conducted in lactating women, and very few studies have quantitatively measured the excretion of drugs into human milk [3]. To overcome this lack of evidence, the European innovative medicine initiative has launched ConcePTION, a private public project aiming to gather scientific evidence on the effect of drug use during pregnancy and lactation. To fulfil this aim, one of the tasks is to set up a European wide milk biobank and conduct five demonstration projects, including amoxicillin, to assess the feasibility of the platform including our study concerning amoxicillin. This demonstration study aims at better quantifying the excretion into milk of amoxicillin, along with its variability and to identify the factors (e.g., demographics, co-medications), that might affect the infant drug exposure. This study will offer new information regarding the safety of the treatment in lactating women. In addition, that study will offer the possibility to assess the facilities and standardized procedures of the new established Europe wide milk biobank.

2.1.2. ON THE TREATMENTS/STRATEGIES/REFERENCE PROCEDURES AND THE STUDY

Amoxicillin (class of β -lactam antimicrobials) is one of the most frequently used antibiotics in the primary care setting. This amino-penicillin generally targeting gram-positive bacteria is approved by FDA to treat mainly β -hemolytic streptococcal sore throat, genitourinary tract infections along with ear, nose and throat infections [11]. Amoxicillin could be used alone if the germ targeted is sensitive to the molecule or associated with clavulanic acid (β -lactamases inhibitor) in order to broaden the spectrum of Amoxicillin to usually resistant bacteria [12]. Due to this wide use and to those various indications, the possibility of the breastfeeding woman using amoxicillin is sizeable. Nowadays, few studies have investigated the risks of amoxicillin consumption for the infant while breastfeeding. In that aim, researchers evaluated the theoretical infant dose (TID) estimated as the dose per kilogram per day that an infant would ingest via milk (a fully breastfed infant is assumed to ingest 0.15 L of milk per kilogram bodyweight per day) and the relative weight-adjusted infant dose (RID) as the infant's weight-adjusted relative dose, expressed as a percentage of the weight-adjusted maternal dose [13]. With low doses (RID values < 2-3%), breastfeeding is generally considered to be safe, excepted for highly toxic agents, such as cytostatic, or psychotropic with a long half-life, because of the risk of accumulation. After a single 1g oral dose in 6 women, peak concentrations are reached approximately at 5 hours, the average concentrations in milk were 0.69 mg/L (0.46-0.88 mg/L) at 4h and 0.82 mg/L (0.39-1.3mg/L) at 5h.

Using these data, the mean TDI (for a usual maternal dose of 500 mg three times daily) was 0.1% mg/kg/day, which corresponds to a mean RID of 0.25-0.5% [13]. Nevertheless, transfer of drug into breast milk does not necessarily present a health risk for the breastfed infant in term of side effects. Indeed, in the literature some cases of diarrhoea, skin rashes and candidiasis in infants [14][15][16] are reported among with one case of generalized urticaria was reported in a 2-month-old infant after maternal use of amoxicillin [17]. Lastly, there is no relevant information in the literature regarding the infant drugs serum levels.

2.2. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES AND EXPECTED RESULTS

The exposure of infants to drugs through breastmilk can be highly variable and depends on the dose ingested by the child along with the absorption, the distribution, the metabolism and the elimination of the drug by the child. Characterisation of this exposure is essential to provide recommendations for preventing toxicity in breastfed infants and assuring mother's adequate treatment. This can be achieved by assessing the PK properties of the drug and inter-individual variability due to characteristics of the mothers and breastfed infants. In France, amoxicillin will be studied in order to evaluate the potential risks of the consumption while breastfeeding. To fulfil that aim, samples (e.g., maternal plasma and breast milk) will be collected from lactating women with infection treated with amoxicillin in various centers (e.g., Toulouse and Paris) and stored in Toulouse to be dosed thereafter. Based on plasma and milk concentrations, a PopPK model will be performed (i) to document mean and individual amoxicillin exposure in milk, (ii) to identify factors explaining the inter-individual PK variability in milk and (iii) to estimate amoxicillin exposure in milk with different drug dosing regimens.

2.3. JUSTIFICATION OF THE METHODOLOGICAL CHOICES

To allow the quantification of the excretion of the selected drugs into breastmilk on a population level, a PopPK approach will be used to describe the drug concentrations measured in plasma and milk and to predict the exposure of breastfed infants. Indeed, PopPK analyses are best suited for PK characterization in vulnerable subjects (e.g. pregnant or breastfeeding women, infants) than traditional pharmacokinetic approaches, as they work even with few observations *per* individual collected in very heterogeneous settings (Figure 1) [18]. In addition, they allow for simple pharmacokinetic simulations and predictions, and they are less expensive than the traditional individual approach [18]. This approach has already shown to be perfectly appropriate in describing drug in milk and plasma levels in breastfeeding women and in simulating infant drug exposure [19][20]. PopPK methodology combines mathematical and statistical modelling to characterise the concentration-time profiles of drugs together with the variability of the study population and allows the identification of the underlying factors responsible for the latter [18]. In practice, all the available observations are pooled together (step A) and summarized by a median concentration-time profile (i.e., the curve obtained with the population pharmacokinetic parameters) surrounded by a certain variability (step B). The PopPK model then allows retrieving individual pharmacokinetic parameters, and thus the most probable concentration-time profile, of each patient included in the population (step C) [18].

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the main steps of a population pharmacokinetic analysis.

As blood is the usual biological matrix collected for PopPK studies, the pharmacokinetic behaviour of a drug is usually documented in plasma. However, if other biological matrices (i.e., milk, cerebrospinal fluid, sperm...) are accessible, the pharmacokinetic behaviour can also be documented in these compartments. This information can be particularly important to (i) define and understand the relationship between blood and some specific tissues and (ii) to determine the quantity of drug accumulated in these tissues during a predefined period. In our study, milk is an accessible matrix bringing information on infant's exposure to drug through breast milk. For this study on amoxicillin, milk and plasma samples will be provided by the same participating women. The aforementioned PopPK approach will allow us to document the median concentration-time profile in milk as well as the median ingested drug dose with its inter-individual variability. In a second step, using the same PopPK approach to simulate various conditions (e.g., change in mother's physiological characteristics, mother's drug doses, infant's milk consumption), it will be possible to estimate the median drug level in milk and its associated variability for each new condition.

2.4. RISK/BENEFIT RATIO

Blood sample risks

During the blood test, the nursing mother may feel a slight twinge as well as slight pain and numbness. A few days later a bruise can also appear.

Milk sample risks

No serious risk to the sampling except local and non-serious irritation or pain in the nipple.

2.5. EXPECTED BENEFITS

Benefits for patients

Patients are not expected to benefit for the participants directly from participating.

Expected benefits in terms of improving knowledge

The private public project, ConcePTION, aim to gather scientific evidence on the effect of drug use during pregnancy and breast-feeding. To fulfil this purpose, one of the tasks is to set up a European wide milk biobank and conduct demonstration projects to assess the feasibility of the platform. This study will offer the possibility to assess the facilities and standardized procedures of the new established Europe wide milk biobank.

Amoxicillin will be studied in order to obtain a better quantification of its excretion into milk, along with its variability and to identify the factors (e.g., demographics, co-medications), that might affect the infant drug exposure. This study aims to complement the clinical data on the safety of amoxicillin in lactating women by predicting the amount of amoxicillin transferred to the breastfed new-borns.

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

3.1. MAIN OBJECTIVE

The objective of this study is, using a PopPK modelling approach, to characterize the pharmacokinetics of amoxicillin in breastfeeding women during the perinatal period in order to:

- Determine the kinetic profile of amoxicillin in milk and its associated variability and to identify the factors explaining some of the inter-individual variability of the concentration-time profiles into breast milk,
- Predict the daily dose ingested by the infant and its associated inter-individual variability in various simulated conditions (e.g., full or mixed breastfeeding, factors influencing infant drug exposure).

3.2. SECONDARY OBJECTIVES

Most studies focus on the measure of pharmacokinetic indices rather than their clinical relevance (i.e., pharmacokinetic-pharmacodynamic relationship). The secondary objectives of this study are to monitor (i) the occurrence of predefined side effects in infants during the breastfeeding period, and (ii) the impact of mother's drug consumption on breast milk production. A form on the infant's health status and breastmilk production will be completed by the mother/parent at the time of samplings and a week later as amoxicillin is administered for one week usually.

For amoxicillin, the list of the drug-specific side effects reported in children considered by the occurrence of diarrhoea, nausea, vomiting, feeding difficulties, skin rashes, urticaria and candidiasis will be monitored [21].

4. EVALUATION CRITERIA

4.1. MAIN EVALUATION CRITERION

As previously mentioned, PopPK approach allow to characterise the median concentration-time profile of a drug in different matrices (i.e., plasma, milk) and to identify the factors of variability between individuals. Based on this approach, it will be possible to determine:

- The median area under the plasma drug concentration-time curve in the mother milk for amoxicillin and percentage of change in mother milk drug levels according to demographics and other co-factors (e.g., co-medications).
- The median dose ingested during breastfeeding by the new-born as well as the associated inter-individual variability, in various simulated conditions (e.g., full or mixed breastfeeding; factors influencing infant drug exposure).

4.2. SECONDARY EVALUATION CRITERIA

Occurrence of predefined side effects in infants and decrease in breast milk production recorded at sampling and a week later.

5. RESEARCH DESIGN

5.1. OUTLINE OF THE RESEARCH

Type of study

Prospective multicenter open-label interventional study conducted in 2 hospitals in France (Toulouse and Paris Necker).

Time frame of the study

After agreement of the ethics committee and Informed Consent of the patients, the inclusion of eligible subjects will be made over a period of 12 months.

5.2. METHODS FOR RANDOMISATION

No randomisation due to the recruitment procedure.

6. ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

6.1. INCLUSION CRITERIA

- Mothers over 18 years, orally treated by amoxicillin according to a dosing regimen depending on the infection and in accordance with the recommendations of the Marketing Authorization (i.e., a dose ranging from 750 mg to 6 g per day) for at least 2 days who breastfeed their child,
- Participation requires that breastfeeding is already well established (i.e., at least 2 weeks after giving birth) and that the infant is over 4 weeks old,
- Affiliation to the social security scheme or equivalent,
- Ability to understand and willingness to sign a written Informed Consent document.

6.2. EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- Mothers under 18 years old,
- Infants born prematurely (i.e., gestational age under 34 weeks) or requiring appropriate medical supervision or support from a team of social workers,
- Mothers who gave birth to twins,
- Inability to communicate due to language problems for the mother,
- Patient subject to a legal protection order (curatorship or tutorship).

The only criterion for discontinuation of the study is the discontinuation of the treatment prior completing plasma and milk, sampling time.

6.3. FEASIBILITY AND RECRUITMENT PROCEDURES

Communications will be available on the *Leche League* website, in Toulouse university hospital center and Paris Necker milk bank (Appendix 2) to inform nursing mothers about our study. If interested, the breastfeeding mother taking amoxicillin will be put in touch with a doctor investigator participating to the study in order to explain our study, its objectives, to check the inclusion criteria and to provide the Patient Information and Informed Consent form. The investigator doctor could also propose his/her own patients, during a scheduled hospital consultation as part of the treatment, to participate to the study if the inclusion criteria are checked and if the latter is voluntary.

After a period of time to consider her decision, the investigating doctor must obtain the patient's written Informed Consent before any clinical or para-clinical examination and an appointment will be schedule for the inclusion visit.

Breastfeeding women inclusion will be similar in Toulouse and Paris.

7. TREATMENT/STRATEGY(IES)/PROCEDURE(S) OF THE RESEARCH

7.1. EXPERIMENTAL TREATMENT/STRATEGY/PROCEDURE

Amoxicillin can be prescribed alone or in combination with clavulanic acid, either orally or by injection, the dosage depends on the patient's age, body weight, kidney function, the severity of the infection and the sensitivity of the germ involved (usually 375-750 mg 3 to 4 times a day). In this study, only the oral route will be applied usually associated with a 2 or 3g per day dosing regimen [21]. The amoxicillin (Appendix III [22]) or clavulanic acid (Appendix IV [23]) will be used as in standard care in accordance with his marketing authorisation.

7.2. COMPARISON TREATMENT/STRATEGY/PROCEDURE

Not applicable (no comparison group).

7.3. PRODUCT CIRCUITS

Provision of treatments

Amoxicillin alone or associated with clavulanic acid treatment takes place as part of the routine care management, so treatment is provided as part of the care.

8. BLINDING

Not applicable (open-label interventional study)

9. ASSOCIATED TREATMENTS AND PROCEDURES

9.1. AUTHORISED ASSOCIATED TREATMENTS AND PROCEDURES

No treatments and/or procedures are prohibited during this study as the main diffusion mechanism of amoxicillin is transcellular passive diffusion [24].

9.2. PROHIBITED ASSOCIATED TREATMENTS AND PROCEDURES

No treatments and/or procedures are prohibited during this study as the main diffusion mechanism of amoxicillin is transcellular passive diffusion [24].

10. CONDUCTING THE RESEARCH

10.1. THE RESEARCH SCHEDULE

Expected participation period of individuals and description of the chronology and duration of all research periods:

- Duration of the inclusion period: 1 year.
- Participation duration of each participant: 1 week.
- Total duration of the research (*duration of the inclusion period + duration of participation*): 1 year + 1 week.

10.2. SUMMARY TABLE OF THE PARTICIPANT FOLLOW-UP

Summary table of the participant follow-up:

	Screening visit T0	Inclusion visit 24H	End of research visit by telephone 1W
Inclusion criteria	✓		
Patient Information form	✓		
Informed Consent form	✓	✓	
Physical examination ¹		✓	
Blood sampling		✓	
Milk collection		✓	
Research on adverse events		✓	✓

¹Physical examination: *weight, height*

10.3. SCREENING VISIT

Obtaining consent

During the screening visit, the investigating doctor provides the patient with information and answers all her questions about the objective, the nature of constraints, foreseeable risks and benefits expected from the study. Investigator also explains the patient's rights in relation to a biomedical research study and checks her eligibility criteria. A copy of the Patient Information and Informed Consent form is then given to the patient by the investigating doctor.

The patient will have sufficient time to make her decision and sign the Informed Consent with the investigator during the screening visit. Once the Informed Consent has been signed, the investigating doctor will schedule the collection/sampling of the milk and blood to determine the pharmacokinetic parameters. These should be carried out immediately or within 24 hours (due to the short duration of the treatment), after the signature of the Informed Consent, over a maximum of 1 day by a hospital nurse either at the reference CHU of Toulouse/Paris Necker milk bank or at home.

The investigating doctor is responsible for obtaining the patient's written Informed Consent. The consent form must be signed **BEFORE ANY CLINICAL OR PARACLINICAL EXAMINATION NEEDED FOR THE STUDY IS PERFORMED**. If the patient agrees to participate, she and the investigator clearly write their names and first names, date and sign the consent form.

The various copies of the Patient Information and Informed Consent form are then distributed as follows:

- A copy of the Patient Information and signed Informed Consent form is given to the patient.
- The original copy is kept by the investigating doctor (even if the patient moves to a new house during the period of the study) in a safe place inaccessible to third parties.

10.4. INCLUSION VISIT

Prior to any research-related examination, the investigator will collect the participant's free, informed and written consent. After the mother acceptance and the Informed Consent form signature, an appointment will be schedule within the following day (due to the short duration of treatment) at the breastfeeding mother's house or at a clinical site (Toulouse university hospital center or Paris Necker milk bank) according to the mother's preferences and availabilities. In both cases, a hospital nurse will collect/sample blood and milk following the protocol instructions and a paper questionnaire will be completed by the nurse and the mother.

Two types of collections/samples will be requested at the same time following the consent signing:

- 3 collections of breast milk.
- 3 blood samples.

The samples/collections will be taken at a clinical site or in the participant's home over a single day during the interval between 2 doses within a 2 half-time period (no later than 4 hours after taking the medication) at least 2 days after the first take of amoxicillin. As the drug in the breast compartment (i.e., milk) is in instantaneous equilibrium with the mother's blood compartment as previously described in mammal animals [25][26][27] [28][29][30][31][32], same time slots are applied for both matrices (the exact times of the samples will be noted on the paper questionnaire completed with the help of the nurse):

- 15-30 min after taking amoxicillin.
- 1-2 hours after taking amoxicillin.
- 3-4 hours after taking amoxicillin.

Those samples/collections must be taken 3 times in order to be able to follow the evolution of the blood and milk concentrations of amoxicillin over an approximately large half-day (i.e., 4-5 hours at most of your time).

10.5. FOLLOW-UP VISITS

The follow-up visit will be scheduled a week after the sampling as amoxicillin is administered for one week usually, under the form of a phone appointment, to ensure the good health of the participants:

- Mother: (i) no hematoma after the blood sample, (ii) no irritation or pain in the nipple after the milk collection and (iii) no modification of milk production following amoxicillin use.
- Infant: (i) no disruption of his/her usual behaviour and (ii) no adverse events (e.g., diarrhoea, nausea, vomiting, feeding difficulties, skin rashes, urticaria, candidiasis) noted by the mother.

Every adverse event will be collected in the questionnaire by the investigator doctor or the hospital nurse. Then, the investigator doctor will validate the imputability of amoxicillin on the observed effect. The investigator must immediately notify the sponsor of the occurrence of serious side effects. An emergency phone number and e-mail address will be given to the mother to contact the investigator if a serious adverse event occurs. Immediately after the patient notification, the investigator must inform the sponsor for the declaration of this serious adverse event.

10.6. END OF RESEARCH VISIT

The patient's participation will end once the last questionnaire has been completed.

10.7. RULES FOR STOPPING A PERSON FROM PARTICIPATING IN THE RESEARCH

The subjects may withdraw from the study if they decide to do so, at any time and irrespective of the reason, or this may be the practitioners in charge or the investigator's decision. All dropouts will be adequately recorded by the investigator when considered as confirmed. The subjects who have been withdrawn from the study cannot be re-included in the study. Their inclusion and study number must not be reused. All data that have been previously collected for these subjects will be kept and used for the evaluation of relevant endpoints unless the patient refuses such exploitation. If accepted a final plasma sample and milk collection will be asked from the patient.

10.8. CONSTRAINTS RELATED TO THE RESEARCH AND POSSIBLE COMPENSATION OF PARTICIPANTS

A compensation in the form of an amount of 150 € in addition to an offered electric breast pump, is provided to compensate for the constraints suffered by the visits made as part of our study. They will be registered in the national file of people participating in biomedical research studies (VRB).

Participants must not participate simultaneously in another study but could take part in another study after this one ends (no exclusion period).

10.9. COLLECTION OF BIOLOGICAL SAMPLES

Two types of collections/samples will be requested at the same time following the consent signing:

- 3 breast milk collections.
- 3 blood samples.

The samples/collections will be taken by a hospital nurse at a clinical site or in the participant's home over a single day during the interval between 2 doses within a 2 half-time period (no later than 4 hours after taking the medication) at least 2 days after the first take of amoxicillin. As the drug in the breast compartment (i.e., milk) is in instantaneous equilibrium with the mother's blood compartment as previously described in mammal animals [25][26][27][28][29][30][31][32], same time slots are applied for both matrices (the exact times of the samples will be noted on the paper questionnaire completed with the help of the nurse):

- 15-30 min after taking amoxicillin.
- 1-2 hours after taking amoxicillin.
- 3-4 hours after taking amoxicillin.

Those samples/collections must be taken 3 times in order to be able to follow the evolution of the blood and milk concentrations of amoxicillin over an approximately large half-day (i.e., 4-5 hours at most of your time).

Milk sampling

Milk sampling can be carried out at a clinical site or in the participant's home using an electric breast pump provided for the needs of the study and should take place after the development of mature milk (about 2 weeks after delivery). The sampling times, as described previously, will be drawn according to the study schedule. The amount of milk withdrawn is approximately 20 ml (just over a tablespoon) per draw, or 60 ml in total. Milk samples will be:

- Drawn in Toulouse university hospital center, placed at +4°C, transferred to the Pharmacokinetics and Toxicology Laboratory of Toulouse within the day, thanks to the shuttle bus already in place between the buildings in Toulouse, aliquoted in two equal volume (one for Toulouse and one for Uppsala– if the mother has agreed on the use and the transfer of the samples to constitute the biocollection) and placed in the clinical site freezer (to specify once the stability at -20°C could have been evaluated).
- Drawn in Paris Necker milk bank, aliquoted in two equal volume (one for Toulouse and one for Uppsala), placed in the clinical site freezer (to specify once the stability at -20°C could have been evaluated) and transferred thanks to a courier employed by the Toulouse university hospital center at a predefined maximum period of 3 shipments, depending on the time needed for the recruitment of mothers. Dr SERREAU will be responsible for organizing the shipment of samples to Toulouse.
- Drawn home and transported by the hospital nurse at +4°C (amoxicillin is stable 24 hours at ambient temperature and 7 days at +5°C according to the dosage method in breastmilk, Appendix V) to the Pharmacokinetics and Toxicology Laboratory of Toulouse within a day by the nurse.

Sampling details and health related details of the mother and child (co-medication taken by the patient and relevant information such as side effects) are collected by the nurse or the investigator doctor using both a paper questionnaire (collected by the hospital nurse) while collecting the samples and by telephone a week later. This form will represent the main source document of the study. The data will be stored in the study database to allow further analyses. The database records will be identified only with the patient study number and initials. Milk samples will be analysed by a validated chromatography (LC-MS/MS) method (Appendix V) in Pharmacokinetics and Toxicology Laboratory of Toulouse.

Blood sampling

Blood drawings will be carried out by trained hospital nurse used to draw blood and may be taken at the participant's home or at a clinical site. The sampling times will be as described previously and will be drawn for patients according to the study schedule. The amount of blood withdrawn is approximately 5 ml (just over a teaspoon) per draw, or 15 ml in total. Blood samples will be:

- Drawn in Toulouse university hospital center, placed at +4°C and transferred to the Pharmacokinetics and Toxicology Laboratory of Toulouse within the day, thanks to the shuttle bus already in place between the buildings in Toulouse. Then, blood samples will be centrifuged at 2 400g for 7 min and plasma will be frozen at -20°C.
- Drawn in Paris Necker milk bank, eventually placed +4°C but inevitably centrifuged at 2 400g for 7 min in order to freeze plasma at -20°C before transportation thanks to a courier employed by the Toulouse university hospital center at a predefined maximum period of 3 shipments, depending on the time needed for the recruitment of mothers. Dr SERREAU will be responsible for organizing the shipment of samples to Toulouse.
- Drawn home and transported by the hospital nurse at +4°C (amoxicillin is stable 24 hours at ambient temperature and 5 days at +5°C according to the dosage method in blood, Appendix VI) to the Pharmacokinetics and Toxicology Laboratory of Toulouse within a day by the nurse. Then, blood samples will be centrifuged at 2 400g for 7 min and plasma will be frozen at -20°C.

Sampling details and health related details of the mother and child (co-medication taken by the patient and relevant information such as side effects) are collected by the nurse or the investigator doctor using both a paper questionnaire (collected by the hospital nurse) while collecting the samples and by telephone a week later. This form will represent the main source document of the study. The data will be stored in the study database to allow further analyses. The database records will be identified only with the patient study number and initials. Plasma samples will be analysed by a validated chromatography (LC-MS/MS) method (Appendix VI) in Pharmacokinetics and Toxicology Laboratory of Toulouse.

Fate of the samples

After analysis of the plasma and milk samples, they will be kept approximately 2 years in the Pharmacokinetics and Toxicology Laboratory of Toulouse, under Pr. GANDIA responsibility, until the report is edited, and the results are published. Indeed, these collections/samples will be analysed again if the reviewers request additional information (dosages in the same theme) in relation to the main objective of this study. The storage methods will be in line with those recommended by the Laboratory of Pharmacology and Toxicology of Toulouse.

If the patient consent to the preservation of her biological milk samples for the establishment of a biobank, following the completion of the analyses, the aliquoted samples will be sent all at once to Uppsala, Sweden in order to generate an EU breast milk biobank enabling research on medication concentrations in human milk. A contract between the CHU of Toulouse and Uppsala will be signed to regulate this transfer, the use of the biological material and to guarantee the rights of the patients. If the patient does not consent, her biological milk samples will not be sent to Uppsala and will be destroyed.

11. MANAGEMENT OF ADVERSE EVENTS AND NEW DEVELOPMENTS

11.1. DEFINITIONS

Adverse Event (Article R1123-46 of the Public Health Code)

Any harmful manifestation occurring in a participant in a research study that involves the human person, whether or not the event is related to the research or product to which the research relates.

Adverse reaction (Article R1123-46 of the Public Health Code)

Any adverse event occurring in a participant in a research study that involves the human person, when this event is related to the research or product to which the research relates.

Serious adverse reaction or event (Article R1123-46 of the Public Health Code and ICH-E2B guideline)

Any adverse reaction or event that:

- ✓ results in death,
- ✓ endangers the life of the participant,
- ✓ requires hospitalisation or prolongation of hospitalisation,
- ✓ causes an inability or significant or long-term disability,
- ✓ results in an abnormality or congenital malformation,
- ✓ or any event considered to be medically serious,

and with respect to the drug, regardless of the dose administered.

The expression "life-threatening" is reserved for an immediate life threat at the time of the adverse event.

Unexpected adverse reaction (Article R1123-46 of the Public Health Code)

- For research on drugs, an unexpected adverse reaction is any adverse reaction to the product including the nature, severity, frequency or outcome of the drug which is inconsistent with the safety reference information referred to in the Summary of Product Characteristics or in the investigator's brochure when the product is not authorised.

New development (Article R1123-46 of the Public Health Code)

- Any new data that may lead to a reassessment of the risk to benefit ratio of the research or of the product being researched, changes in the use of this product, in the conduct of the research, or to the documents relating to the research, or data that may lead to the suspension, discontinuation or modification of the research protocol or similar research.

11.2. DESCRIPTION OF EXPECTED SERIOUS ADVERSE EVENTS

Exhaustively list the serious adverse events expected within the framework of the protocol:

- ***related to experimental procedures:***
 - No serious adverse reactions are expected with the investigational procedures (blood and milk collection). Only moderate and non-serious adverse events are expected (pain, numbness and bruise for blood collection / local irritation or pain in the nipple after milk collection).
 - In this protocol, the study drug amoxicillin is used as standard care according to his marketing authorisation. According to his SmPC, some adverse drug reactions are expected, and the most commonly reported ones are diarrhoea, nausea, skin rash, urticarial, pruritus and vomiting. Other Adverse reactions (uncommon, rare or very rare) are described in his SmPC.
- ***related to the evolution of the disease (death due to the disease, relapse, etc.):*** not applicable.

11.3. CONDUCT TO BE MAINTAINED BY THE INVESTIGATOR IN THE EVENT OF AN ADVERSE EVENT, A NEW DEVELOPMENT OR PREGNANCY

11.3.1. COLLECTION OF ADVERSE EVENTS (AE)

Upon signing the consent form, the investigator is responsible for collecting all adverse events. He/she reports all serious and non-serious adverse events (biological and clinical AEs) that occur between the signing of the consent form and the end of the patient's participation in the case report form.

These adverse events will be assessed at each visit during the study by questioning and during the clinical examination of the patient.

Exception to collection:

The following circumstances will not be collected:

- Admission for social or administrative reasons,
- Hospitalisation predefined by the protocol,
- Hospitalisation for scheduled medical or surgical treatment prior to the research,

11.3.2. NOTIFICATION OF SERIOUS ADVERSE EVENTS (SAEs), ADVERSE EVENTS OF INTEREST AND NEW DEVELOPMENTS

The investigator evaluates each adverse event in terms of its seriousness.

The investigator shall notify the sponsor, without delay, on the day on which he/she becomes aware, of any serious adverse event (SAE), if it occurs:

- From the date of signature of the consent form,
- During the entire patient follow-up period planned by the research (2 weeks),

The investigator should document the event as best as possible, giving a medical diagnosis if possible.

The investigator must ensure that the relevant follow-up information is communicated to the sponsor as soon as possible. The investigator must submit, in addition to the SAE notification form, copies of laboratory results or reports of examinations or hospitalisation that document the serious adverse event, including any relevant adverse findings, **without forgetting to make these documents anonymous** and to enter the patient's number and code.

The investigator must follow the patient who has presented with a SAE until its resolution, stabilisation to a level deemed medically acceptable or to the return to the previous state, even if the patient has discontinued the research procedure. Further information regarding the evolution of the event, if not mentioned in the first report, will be sent to the sponsor by the investigator.

The investigator and the sponsor should evaluate, independently of each other, the causal relationship between the serious adverse event and the experimental procedures (*blood or milk collection and/or amoxicillin intake*). If the SAE seems not to be related to the experimental procedure or amoxicillin, an alternative causality must be provided (e.g., concomitant treatments, complication of a pre-existing disease...).

All serious adverse events for which the investigator or sponsor believes a causal relationship can be reasonably considered are considered suspected serious adverse reactions.

The investigator must notify the sponsor of any new developments of which he/she has knowledge.

11.3.3. NOTIFICATION OF PREGNANCIES

The occurrence of a pregnancy during or towards the end of a study, does not constitute an SAE. However, if a woman falls pregnant within the framework of the research the pregnancy must be notified in the same way as an SAE because its outcome will be subject to a particular follow-up.

For this purpose, the investigator informs the sponsor's vigilance department through the pregnancy declaration form.

The investigator must follow the patient until the end of the pregnancy or its interruption and notify the outcome to the sponsor. Any abnormalities noted on the foetus or the child must be notified. Any voluntary termination of pregnancy, medical termination of pregnancy or miscarriage must be the subject of a pregnancy notification, and if a severity criterion is present, it must be the subject of a SAE notification.

11.3.4. SUMMARY TABLE OF THE NOTIFICATION CIRCUIT BY TYPE OF EVENT

TYPE OF EVENT	METHOD OF NOTIFICATION	DEADLINE FOR NOTIFICATION TO THE SPONSOR
Adverse event	In the case report form	No notification without delay
Serious adverse event	Collection in the case report form + Initial SAE declaration form + Follow up if necessary	Notification without delay to the sponsor
New development	Written report	Notification without delay to the sponsor
Pregnancy	Pregnancy declaration form	Upon confirmation of pregnancy

Contact details for the sponsor's vigilance unit for notifications

<p><i>Sponsor's Name/ Vigilance unit: Toulouse University Hospital / Dr Pascale OLIVIER</i> <i>Fax: +33 (0)5 61 77 84 11</i> <i>E-mail: vigilance.essaiscliniques@chu-toulouse.fr</i></p>

11.4. DECLARATION BY THE SPONSOR OF UNEXPECTED SERIOUS ADVERSE REACTIONS, NEW DEVELOPMENTS AND OTHER EVENTS

The sponsor assesses whether the serious adverse reaction is expected or unexpected based on the list of expected serious adverse events described in section 9.2 of the protocol and on the reference, document as defined in the protocol.

The vigilance unit specifies that the reference document for the analysis of the unexpected nature of the event is the section 9.2 of the protocol and amoxicillin SmPC.

The sponsor/ vigilance unit shall report the safety information to the competent authorities and the CPP in accordance with the applicable deadlines, in accordance with the regulatory requirements specific to each type of trial.

In the case of a drug study, the sponsor/vigilance unit records any suspected unexpected serious adverse reactions (SUSAR) in the EudraVigilance database.

Summary table of declarations by type of study

Type of study and type of AE	Declaration to		Initial declaration period	Follow-up period
	Competent authority (ANSM, etc.)	CPP		
Drug: SUSAR	X		- death or life-threatening: without delay - other criteria: max. 15 days	Max. 8 days

The sponsor/vigilance unit shall declare without delay new facts that have arisen during the research to:

- The ANSM,
- The Committee for the Protection of Persons,

The sponsor and the investigator will take the appropriate urgent measures. The sponsor will inform the competent authority and the committee for the protection of persons.

11.5. ANNUAL SAFETY REPORT

For “study drug” category 1 research, on the anniversary date of the *research authorisation*, the sponsor will write a safety report including:

- The list of serious adverse reactions that may be related to the experimental treatment(s) of the research, including expected and unexpected serious reactions, that occurred in the relevant study during the reporting period,
- A concise and critical analysis of the safety of the research participants.
- Summary tables of all serious adverse reactions that have occurred in the study since the beginning of the research.

This report is sent to the ANSM and the CPP within 60 days of the anniversary date of *the research authorisation*.

12. STATISTICAL ASPECTS

12.1. CALCULATION OF STUDY SIZE

In PopPK approach, two options are generally accepted:

- A complete PK profile is performed on few patients to build the structural model (i.e., one, two or three compartment-model depending on the drug, Figure 2) and very sparse samples *per* patient are collected on a large population (most often 1 sample collected in a clinical routine activity on > 30 patients) to build the statistical model (i.e. models that document the inter- and the intra-individual variabilities, Figure 2),
- Sparse samples *per* patient (i.e., 2 or 3 samples) are collected on a medium or large population to build both structural and statistical models.

The mathematical equations of a PopPK model are represented in Figure 2.

$$\begin{cases} Y_{ij} = f(t_{ij}, \psi_i) + f(t_{ij}, \psi_i)\epsilon_{ij} \\ \psi_i = g(X_i, \theta) + \eta_i \end{cases}$$

Structural model Statistical model (intra-individual variability)
Statistical model (inter-individual variability)

Y_{ij} : jth concentration measured on the ith individual at the instant t_{ij}
 ψ_i : pharmacokinetic parameters of the ith individual
 ϵ_{ij} : standard Gaussian random variables
 X_i : covariates explaining the variation in ψ_i from one individual to another

Figure 2: mathematical description of a PopPK model.

However, there is no clear rule on the number of samples, the number of patients or both, as the construction of the structural and the statistical models depends on the drug. For example, if a drug is described by a one-compartment model (Figure 3A), the kinetic profile presents two phases (i.e., absorption and elimination as distribution is instantaneous after drug administration). In this case, one sample (i.e., red ball) randomly collected in the absorption phase and one (i.e. green ball) in the elimination phase for 25 patients would be enough to correctly describe the kinetic profile based on a PopPK approach (Figure 3B).

Figure 3: Representation of a one-compartment model (A) with the associated kinetic profile (B).

Indeed, specifying only the sampling periods (e.g., between 0 and 2h then between 2h and 5h) leaves the possibility of covering both the absorption and elimination phases with all the samples taken on 25 individuals. In this case, the estimated parameters of the structural and the statistical models are precise (i.e. the imprecision so-called RSE is < 30% [33][34]).

As the mammillary blood flow is particularly important during lactation and as most drugs are excreted into milk by passive diffusion, (i) drug in the breast compartment (i.e. milk) is instantaneously in equilibrium with the mother's blood compartment and (ii) drug concentration in milk is directly proportional to the corresponding concentration in maternal plasma [25][26][27][28][29][30][31][32]. Therefore, “when you have got the plasma concentration, we can easily deduce the milk concentration and vice versa” (Figure 4). Consequently, it is not aberrant to create a PopPK model from milk samples correctly distributed between two drug administrations, to describe both the PK behaviour in blood and breast milk.

Figure 4: Representation of a one-compartment model including blood and milk sub-compartments in instantaneous equilibrium

12.2. STATISTICAL METHODS EMPLOYED

Interim analyses

No interim analysis is planned in this project.

Final analyses

All the analyses listed in this protocol will be carried out only after:

- The last subject has completed the study,
- The study database has been locked,
- The detailed analysis plan has been approved by the whole team involved in the project.

The reasons for withdrawal from the study will be assessed from the data recorded at the last visit. Reasons for early withdrawal may include:

- Adverse events, whether serious or otherwise (decision of the investigator),
- Personal reasons (decision of the subject),
- Other reasons.

A table of the numbers and percentages of subjects leaving the study early, the reasons for their withdrawal and the visit at which the decision was taken will be noted. Fisher's exact tests or χ^2 tests will be performed to compare the proportions of patients withdrawing from the study and the included population. The numbers and percentages of subjects for whom deviations from the protocol are noted and the reasons for major deviations will be noted for the study population.

The distribution of the missing data for each parameter collected will be described in order to get an idea of the quality of the observations.

The characteristics of the population at inclusion will be described. The quantitative variables will be described with the following indicators: number, mean and standard deviation or median and interquartile range according to the distribution of the variable, minimum and maximum. The qualitative variables will be presented for each modality with the number and the corresponding percentage.

To answer the principal objective, a population pharmacokinetic model will be created based on plasma and milk concentrations of amoxicillin. This model will be validated taking into consideration the usual criteria in PK modelling (objective function, AIC, BIC, bootstrap, visual predictive check).

To answer the secondary objectives, the number, the mean and the standard deviation of (i) predefined side effects in infants' occurrence and (ii) decrease of breast milk production recorded at sampling and a week later.

13. MONITORING OF THE RESEARCH

In this protocol, an independent monitoring committee will not be set up and it can be justified by:

- The absence of serious risks related to experimental procedures (blood and milk samples collection).
- The use of amoxicillin as in standard care with a long history of use and known good safety profile (favourable benefit-risk balance).
- Continuous collection of AE/reporting of SAE.
- The fact that women will be advised to contact the study contact person if she encounters any problems at home.

14. RIGHTS OF ACCESS TO DATA AND SOURCE DOCUMENTS

14.1. ACCESS TO DATA

Agreeing to participate in the protocol implies that the investigators will make the documents and personal data that are strictly necessary for the monitoring, quality control and auditing of the research, available in accordance with the laws and regulations in force.

14.2. SOURCE DATA

All information contained in original documents, or in authenticated copies of these documents, relating to clinical examinations, observations or other activities conducted as part of a research study and necessary for the reconstitution and evaluation of the research. The documents in which the source data are saved are called the source documents.

14.3. DATA CONFIDENTIALITY

In accordance with the legislative provisions in force, persons having direct access to source data will take all the necessary precautions to ensure the confidentiality of information relating to investigational medicinal products, research, participants, especially as regards their identity and the results obtained. These people, like the investigators, are subject to professional secrecy.

During or at the end of the research, the data collected on the participants and sent to the sponsor by the investigators (or any other specialised contributor) will be made anonymous. The data must never explicitly mention the names of the persons concerned or their addresses.

Patients will be codified: only the first letter of the subject's last name and first name will be recorded, together with a coded number specific to the research indicating the order of inclusion of the subjects in each center.

The sponsor will ensure that each participant has given his/her written agreement for access to the individual data concerning them and strictly necessary for the quality control of the research.

Patients will have to be registered in the French national file of research participants.

15. QUALITY CONTROL AND QUALITY ASSURANCE

15.1. GUIDELINES FOR COLLECTING DATA

All the information required by the protocol must be recorded in case report forms and an explanation must be provided for any missing data. The data must be collected as and when they are obtained and transcribed in these notebooks in a clear and legible way.

15.2. QUALITY CONTROL

A clinical researcher appointed by the sponsor will regularly visit each center investigator, during the implementation of the research, one or more times during research according to the frequency of the inclusions and at the end of the research. During these visits, and in accordance with the risk-based monitoring plan (participant, logistics, impact, resources), the following elements will be reviewed:

- informed consent,
- compliance with the research protocol and the procedures defined therein,
- quality of the data collected in the case report form: accuracy, missing data, consistency of the data with the source documents (medical records, appointment books, originals of laboratory results, etc.).
- management of potential products.

All visits will be the subject of a monitoring report by written report.

15.3. DATA MANAGEMENT

Clinical data will be collected on case report forms and then reviewed by a CRA, directly on site, before transmission to the data management section for entry into the database.

All the data management activities will be under the supervision of Toulouse MéDatAS-CIC.

Data entry is supervised by the Data Manager responsible for this project. The rules for data entry will be defined in collaboration with the Clinical Project Leader.

The data management steps will be handled with Capture System software, from Clinsight-ennov, version V5.5.41 or higher. SAS software may also be used as an additional tool if necessary. A data validation plan will be generated to define the checks to be programmed by the Data Manager with the dedicated Capture System module, CS TEST. The document will be reviewed and approved by the clinical team and the statistician. Data will be validated on a regular basis.

Once all case report forms have been entered into the database and the data have been validated and all data management steps checked, the Data Manager will lock the database. A certificate confirming this locking of the database will be delivered to the clinical team.

15.4. AUDIT AND INSPECTION

An audit may be conducted at any time by persons appointed by the sponsor and independent of the persons conducting the research. Its purpose is to verify the participants' safety and respect for their rights, compliance with applicable regulations and the reliability of data.

An inspection can also be carried out by a competent authority (ANSM for France or EMA in the context of a European study, for example).

The audit, as well as the inspection, can be applied at all stages of the research, from the development of the protocol to the publication of the results and the classification of the data used or produced as part of the research.

Investigators agree to comply with the sponsor's requirements as regards an audit and the competent authority for a research inspection.

16. ETHICAL AND REGULATORY CONSIDERATIONS

The sponsor and the investigator(s) undertake to ensure that this research is carried out in accordance with law no. 2012-300 of 5 March 2012 on research involving the human person, as well as in agreement with Good Clinical Practices (ICH version 4 of 9 November 2016 and the decision of 24 November 2006) and the Declaration of Helsinki (which can be found in full at <http://www.wma.net>).

The research is conducted in accordance with this protocol. Except in emergency situations that require the implementation of specific therapeutic acts, the investigator(s) undertake(s) to respect the protocol in all points especially with regard to the collection of consent and notification and follow-up of serious adverse events.

This research received a favourable opinion from the Committee for the Protection of Persons (CPP) by **name from the CPP** and authorisation from the ANSM

The University Hospital of Toulouse, sponsor of this research, has taken out a civil liability insurance contract with *Lloyd's Insurance Company S.A* in accordance with the provisions of the Public Health Code.

The data recorded during this research are the subject of a computerised processing by University Hospital of Toulouse in accordance with the law no. 78-17 of 6 January 1978 on data processing, files and liberties as amended by Law 2004-801 of 6 August 2004.

This research falls within the framework of the "Reference Methodology" (MR-001) in application of the provisions of Article 54 paragraph 5 of the amended law of 6 January 1978 relating to information, files and liberties. This change was approved by the decision of 5 January 2006, updated on 21 July 2016. The *name of the data processing organisation* has signed a compliance commitment to this "Reference Methodology".

- This research is registered in the European database EudraCT under number 2021-002247-30
- This research has been registered on the site <http://clinicaltrials.gov/>
- After the research, the conservation of the collection of biological samples will be declared to the Minister in charge of research and to the director of the French Regional Health Agency (and submitted to the CPP for an opinion if there was a change of research purpose).

CHANGES TO THE PROTOCOL

Any substantial change, i.e. any change that is likely to have a significant impact on the protection of persons, on the conditions of validity and on the results of the research, on the quality and safety of the products tested, on the interpretation of scientific documents that support the conduct of the research or the way in which the research is conducted, is subject to a written amendment submitted to the sponsor. The latter must obtain, prior to its implementation, a favourable opinion from the CPP, and, where applicable, authorisation from the French National Agency for Medicines and Health Products Safety (ANSM).

Non-substantial changes, i.e., those that do not have a significant impact on any aspect of the research, are communicated to the CPP for information.

All changes are validated by the sponsor, and by all research stakeholders involved in the change, before submission to the CPP, and, where applicable, to the ANSM. This validation may require the meeting of all committees formed for the research.

All changes to the protocol must be made known to investigators, who are participating in the research. The investigators undertake to respect the content.

Any modification that modifies participant care or the benefits, risks and constraints of the research is the subject of a new information note and a new consent form whose collection follows the same procedure above.

17. PRESERVATION OF RESEARCH DOCUMENTS AND DATA

The following documents related to this research are archived by the investigator in accordance with Good Clinical Practices *for a period of 15 years following the end of the research* (research on drugs, medical devices or in vitro diagnostic medical devices or research not related to a product mentioned in Article L.5311-1 of the Public Health Code),

- The protocol and any modifications to the protocol,
- Case report forms (copies),
- Source records of participants who have signed a consent form,
- All other documents and correspondence related to research,
- The original copy of the informed consent forms signed by the participants

All of these documents are the responsibility of the investigator during the regulatory archiving period. No displacement or destruction can be made without the agreement of the sponsor. At the end of the regulatory archiving period, the sponsor will be consulted for destruction. All data, documents and reports may be subject to audit or inspection.

18. FINAL REPORT

Within one year after the end of the research or its interruption, a final report will be prepared and signed by the sponsor and the investigator. This report will be kept at the disposal of the competent authority. The sponsor will transmit to the CPP and, where applicable, to the ANSM, the results of the research in the form of a summary of the final report within one year after the end of the research.

19. RULES FOR PUBLICATION

19.1. SCIENTIFIC COMMUNICATIONS

The data analysis provided by the investigating centers is carried out by Toulouse University Hospital. This analysis gives rise to a written report which is submitted to the sponsor, who will forward it to the Committee for the Protection of Persons and to the competent authority.

Any written or oral communication of the results of the research must have the prior consent of the coordinating investigator and, where appropriate, of all committees that were established for the research.

The coordinating investigator undertakes to make available to the public both negative and inconclusive and positive research results.

The publication of the main results must mention the name of the sponsor, all the persons who helped in the inclusion or follow-up of participants in the research, methodologists, biostatisticians and data managers who participated in the research, health vigilance personnel who participated in the safety analysis of the participants, members of the committee(s) constituted for the research and the possible involvement of the source of funding. International rules of writing and publication will be taken into account (*The Uniform Requirements for Manuscripts* of the ICMJE, April 2010).

19.2. COMMUNICATION OF RESULTS TO PARTICIPANTS

In accordance with law no. 2002-303 of 4 March 2002, the participants are informed, at their request, of the overall results of the research.

19.3. TRANSFER OF DATA

Data management is provided by Toulouse University Hospital. The conditions for the transfer of all or part of the research database are decided by the research sponsor are the subject of a written contract.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX I: List of investigators

APPENDIX II: Communication made available on the *Leche League* website, in Toulouse university hospital center and Paris Necker milk bank

APPENDIX III: Amoxicillin Summary of Product Characteristics

APPENDIX IV: Amoxicillin and clavulanic acid Summary of Product Characteristics

APPENDIX V: Amoxicillin milk dosage with a validated chromatography (LC-MS/MS) method

APPENDIX VI: Amoxicillin blood dosage with a validated chromatography (LC-MS/MS) method

Version No: 5.1
Date: 2023-12-08
EU Trial Number: 2023-508913-18-00

CLINICAL TRIAL PROTOCOL

Transfer of prednisolone into human breast milk and plasma of breastfeeding children - A low intervention cohort study with biobanking of breast milk and plasma

EU Trial number: 2023-508913-18-00

Version number: 5.1

Date: 2023-12-08

Sponsor: Uppsala University
Centre for Research Ethics & Bioethics,
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Description of changes in the trial protocol

Protocol version	Summary of changes <i>Describe all changes since the first final protocol.</i>
5.0	Komplettering i avsnitten 5.4, 9 och 11 visavi version 4.0
5.0	Bifogade attachments under punkt 16

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Signature page

Sponsor

I am responsible for ensuring that this protocol includes all essential information to be able to conduct this trial. I will submit the protocol and all other important trial-related information to the responsible investigator(s) so that they can conduct the trial correctly. I am aware that it is my responsibility to hold the staff members who work with this trial informed and trained.

Sponsor's signature

Date

Mats Hansson
Senior Professor

Principal Investigator

I have read this protocol and agree that it includes all essential information to be able to conduct the trial. By signing my name below, I agree to conduct the trial in compliance with this clinical trial protocol, the EU Regulation on clinical trials of medicinal products for human use (EU 536/2014), the Declaration of Helsinki, ICH-GCP (Good Clinical Practice) guidelines and the current national regulations governing the conduct of this clinical trial.

I will submit this protocol and all other important trial-related information to the staff members and investigators who participate in this trial, so that they can conduct the trial correctly. I am aware of my responsibility to continuously keep the staff members and investigators who work with this trial informed and trained.

I am aware that quality control of this trial will be performed in the form of monitoring and eventual audit and inspection.

Principal Investigator's signature

Date

Jenny Svedenkrans,
Senior Consultant of Neonatology, Pediatrician,

Contact information

Responsibility in the clinical trial	
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Biobank	Uppsala Biobank, Dag Hammarskjölds väg 38, 5tr., UCR, Uppsala Science Park, Hubben 751 85 Uppsala

List of used acronyms and abbreviations

Abbreviation	Term/Explanation
ADID	Average Daily Infant Dose
Adverse Event (AE)	Any untoward medical occurrence in a subject to whom a medicinal product is administered and which does not necessarily have a causal relationship with this treatment.
AR	Adverse Reaction = any unfavorable and unexpected reaction to an investigational medicinal product, regardless of dose
ASR	Annual Safety Report = the annual safety report for reporting to authorities. In Sweden this is the Swedish Medical Products Agency via CTIS.
BLQ	Below the limit of quantification
CA	Competent Authorities
CRF	Case Report Form
CTIS	Clinical Trials Information System = Centralized EU database/portal for application and communication with authorities concerning clinical trials. In Sweden this includes the Swedish Medical Products Agency and the Swedish Ethical Review Authority.
ENTIS	the European Network of Teratology Information Services
ICH-GCP	International Council for Harmonization Good Clinical Practice
LLOQ	lower limit of quantification
NMBR	the National Medical Birth Register
NPDR	the National Prescribed Drug Register
REDCAP	Research Electronic Data Capture
RID	Relative infant dose

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Serious Adverse Event (SAE)	Any untoward medical occurrence that at any dose requires inpatient hospitalisation or prolongation of existing hospitalisation, results in persistent or significant disability or incapacity, results in a congenital anomaly or birth defect, is life-threatening, or results in death
SD	Standard deviation
SUSAR	Suspected Unexpected Serious Adverse Reaction. This is an event that is likely related to the investigational medicinal product but with unexpected occurrence. An adverse reaction is unexpected if its nature or seriousness is not consistent with the information on the product in the RSI.

1. Swedish synopsis

EU prövningsnummer:	2023508913-18-00
Titel:	Överföring av prednisolon till bröstmjolk och blodplasma från ammande barn - En låginterventionsstudie med biobankning av bröstmjolk och blodplasma
Kort bakgrund/ Rational/Syfte:	För många läkemedel saknas idag tillräckliga underlag för hur läkemedlet kan påverka barnet som ammas. Det har i många fall inneburit att man av försiktighetsskäl sätter ut läkemedlet eller rekommenderar mamman att inte amma. Samtidigt har mamman bäst nytta av det förskrivna läkemedlet och man vet att amning är bra både för det nyfödda barnet och för mamman. Syftet med studien är att undersöka om och hur mycket av prednisolon som går över via bröstmjölken till barnet från mamman som har fått läkemedlet förskrivet.
Primärt syfte:	Det primära syftet är att bestämma koncentrationen av prednisolon i plasman hos ammade spädbarn till ammande kvinnor som behandlats med prednisolon för att minska inflammation.
Sekundärt syfte:	Sekundärt mål är att bestämma koncentrationen av prednisolon/prednison i bröstmjölken och moderns plasma och mjölk-till-plasmaförhållandet hos mödrarna och att beräkna den genomsnittliga dagliga spädbarnsdosen (ADID) och relativ spädbarnsdos (RID).
Primärt utfallsmått:	Det primära utfallsmåttet är koncentrationen av prednisolon i det ammande barnets plasma 2 timmar efter att ett spädbarn matats med bröstmjolk, med utfodringen 1 timme efter moderns dosintag.
Sekundärt utfallsmått:	De sekundära effektmåtten är koncentrationen av prednisolon och prednison i bröstmjolk 1 timme efter moderns dosintag och moderns plasmakoncentration av prednisolon och prednison 1 timme efter prednisolonintag.
Prövningsdesign:	Studien har en låg interventionell design i den meningen att bröstmjolk och blod samlas in enbart för

	att studera utsöndringen av prednisolon i bröstmjölken och överförning till det ammade barnet.
Prövningspopulation:	Ammande kvinnor över 18 år som behandlas med prednisolon och deras nyfödda barn (6-8 veckor efter födseln)
Antal försökspersoner:	30
Inklusionskriterier:	Ammande kvinnor som behandlas med prednisolon med doser upp till 50 mg/dag för alla tillstånd. Endast kvinnor från 18 år och äldre kommer att tillfrågas om att delta. Ammande barn till kvinnor som har samtyckt till att delta i studien. Vårdnadshavare till barnet tillfrågas och informerat samtycke inhämtas också från fadern
Exklusionskriterier:	Kvinnor som inte kan läsa och kommunicera på svenska eller engelska. Kvinnor med spädbarn födda före 37 veckors graviditet (för tidig). Kvinnor med flerbörd.
Intervention:	Ingen behandling förekommer i studien, se ovan.
Prövningsläkemedel, dosering, administrering:	Prednisolon med doser upp till 50mg/dag i enlighet med förskrivning av läkare.
Etiska överväganden, nytta/risk:	Risk-nytta-balansen avseende prednisolon påverkas inte av att delta i studien. Provtagningen görs enligt etablerade kliniska rutiner. Man känner ett lätt stick när man tar ett blodprov. Man kan få ett blåmärke och det finns alltid en liten risk att påverka en nerv, vilket kan uttryckas som smärta eller domningar. Vid blodprov tas totalt 14 ml blod vid ett tillfälle. Detta kan jämföras med de 450 ml blod som tas under en normal blodgivning. Försökspersonerna förväntas inte ha någon direkt nytta av att delta i studien. Studieresultaten kommer dock att kunna bidra med information som i framtiden kan hjälpa ammande kvinnor att fatta ett välgrundat beslut om användning prednisolon i samband med amning. Sådan information kommer också att hjälpa vårdpersonal att ge evidensbaserade råd till ammande kvinnor om användningen av prednisolon.
Prövningsperiod:	Q1 2024-Q4 2024, Publicering inom ett år efter studiens avslut.

2. Background and rationale

More than 5 million women get pregnant in the EU every year and a majority take at least one medication during pregnancy. As few as 5% of available medications have been adequately monitored, tested and labelled with safety information for use in pregnant and breastfeeding women. The field, while inherently difficult to study, has suffered from a lack of systematically gathered insights that could lead to more effective data generation methodologies. Fragmentation and misinformation results in confusing and contradictory communication and perception of risks by both health professionals and women and their families.

In clinical settings doctors often take a precautionary approach and discontinue the prescription of a given drug during pregnancy and breast feeding, or recommend to stop breast feeding. There is a cost of this approach, both for the woman and for her child. The woman is in need of the drug, which may not be replaceable by another drug, and one knows that breast feeding is good, both for the mother and for the child. The lack of evidence regarding transfer of drug to the breastfeeding infant may thus impose both women and their children to increased risks.

Anecdotal evidence from doctors in Sweden indicate that clinical practice differs, some withdraw the drug, others continue. In order to get reliable data on prescription, we asked The National Board of Health and Welfare to do a cross match of the National Prescribed Drug Register (NPDR) and the National Medical Birth Register (NMBR) for 45 different drugs that according to the European Network of Teratology Information Services (ENTIS) lacked sufficient scientific evidence for use during pregnancy and breastfeeding. A threshold of 500 prescriptions/year for entire Sweden was set. Among the 12 drugs that so were identified was *prednisolone*. The uptake of the drug is spread all over Sweden so women taking *prednisolone* live in different parts throughout Sweden.

When treating lactating women who continue to breastfeed, not only the mother is exposed to the risks of treatment but potentially also the breastfeeding child. Hence, it is important to fully understand any risks that the breastfeeding child is exposed to due to maternal medical treatment. This is essential in order to be able to weigh the benefits of treatment against its risks, and for clinicians and women to make well-informed decisions concerning treatment and breastfeeding.

Until today, only a handful of publications have studied how maternal prednisolone treatment affects breastfeeding and the breastfeeding child. To better understand any risks that the breastfeeding child is exposed to, it is important to not only study the concentration of prednisolone in breast milk but also the levels of prednisolone in the plasma of the breastfeeding child. The previous studies that have studied excretion of prednisolone in breast milk and in blood mainly consist of case studies involving few lactating women and generally a smaller number of infants. There is a need for additional studies involving larger numbers of study participants, with systematically collected data.

3. Benefit-risk evaluation

Prednisolone is prescribed by the treating physician prior to subject enrollment in the trial. There is no change regarding the prescription or dosing of prednisolone after enrollment and the risk-benefit balance regarding prednisolone is thus not affected by participating in the trial.

Summary of benefits and risks in accordance with the Assessment Report from EMA (CHMP) 13 October 2016, EM/867221/2016:

The benefits of prednisolone when used to lower the activity of the immune system and prevent the release of substances in the body that cause inflammation and swelling have been demonstrated.

The most common side-effects observed in association with prednisolone use include fluid retention, dizziness, headache, muscle pain or weakness, bloating, weight gain, heartburn, insomnia, hunger, nausea or thrush. Prednisolone can weaken the immune system, making it easier to get an infection. Steroids can also worsen a current infection, or reactivate a recent infection.

The sampling during the trial is done according to established clinical routines. As stated in the research subject information, one usually feels a slight sting when taking a blood sample. One can get a bruise and there is always a small risk of affecting a nerve, which can be expressed as pain or numbness. When taking a blood sample, a total of 14 ml of blood will be collected at one occasion. This can be compared to the 450 ml of blood taken during a normal blood donation.

The research subjects are not expected to benefit directly from participating in the study. However, the study results will be able to contribute information that in the future can help breastfeeding women make an informed decision about using prednisolone in connection with breastfeeding. Such information will also help healthcare professionals provide evidence-based advice to breastfeeding women about the use of prednisolone.

An alternative to obtain data regarding the transfer of drugs during breastfeeding is to only collect breast milk. However, it is only when one also takes a blood sample from the breastfed child that one will get reliable data on how much of the medicine is actually transferred to the child. This is also the "golden standard" that applies to lactation studies internationally. Blood sampling in children is associated with a pain problem. The clinical scientifically supported routine that the project follows is to take a venous blood sample on the back of the hand. In connection with this, emla and/or sugar solution is given. This blood sampling is done by experienced and specially trained healthcare personnel. Only data associated with the sampling procedure and which other drugs the woman is on are documented. Privacy risks are further minimized by pseudonymisation.

4. Trial objectives

4.1. Primary objective

The primary objective is to determine the concentration of prednisolone in the plasma of breast-fed infants of lactating women treated with prednisolone to reduce inflammation in a variety of conditions.

4.2. Secondary objective(s)

Secondary objectives are to:

1. Determine concentration of prednisolone/prednisone in the breast milk and maternal plasma and the milk-to-plasma ratio in the mothers and to calculate the average daily infant dose (ADID) and relative infant dose (RID).
2. Evaluate the cortisol levels in the infants.

4.3. Primary endpoint

The primary endpoint is the concentration of prednisolone in the breastfeeding child's plasma 2h after feeding an infant breast milk, with the feeding taking place at 1h following maternal dose intake.

4.4. Secondary endpoint

The secondary endpoints are:

1. The concentration of prednisolone and prednisone in breast milk at 1h after maternal dose intake and the maternal plasma concentration of prednisolone and prednisone at 1h after prednisolone intake.
2. The concentration of cortisol in the infant blood.

5. Trial design and procedures

5.1. Overall trial design

Low intervention trial with collection and biobanking of breast milk and plasma.

Breast milk and blood will be collected merely to study excretion of prednisolone into breastmilk and transferal to her child. Participation in the trial will not decide or in any other way interfere with patients' treatment as prescribed by their physician. Only patients that already have been assigned treatment with prednisolone by their physician and made the choice to breastfeed, will be approached and asked for participation. All procedures for blood collection will follow established routines at the clinical sites.

The sampling will take place \approx 6-8 weeks after birth at the designated clinic. At this time point it is estimated that there is nothing left from medication taken during pregnancy.

Women willing to participate in the study will be provided with detailed information about what this entails and provided with a written informed consent form, that they will sign and also ask their partners (the other care giver) to sign. They will bring the signed informed consent form with them to the sampling center.

Breast milk will be collected once during the visit, using an electric breast milk pump. Venous blood will be collected from the woman and from the infant. After centrifugation, plasma samples and the breast milk sample will be shipped to Uppsala Biobank where it will be frozen and stored. Samples will be analysed for pharmacokinetic properties using mass spectrometry at the platform UDOPP, Department of Pharmacy, Uppsala University.

5.2. Procedures and flow chart

Overview sampling procedure

5.3. Biological sampling procedures

Women accepting participation are scheduled for breastmilk sampling. Sampling takes place after development of mature milk, at least six weeks postpartum. The sampling will take place after achieving steady state; after having been on prednisolone without any dosage changes for a minimum of 7 days. All sampling takes place the same day at any of the clinical sites. The mother brings her own prednisolone medication to the clinic.

Following FDA recommendations, lactation studies should preferentially not be initiated earlier than 6 weeks after delivery, to allow the mother to go back to a normal physiology and also to not interfere with establishment of breast-feeding and mother-child bonding. Participation starts with offering the mother something to eat, before prednisolone intake. Participants are expected to participate in the study until they have taken their dose of prednisolone (0h), provided a blood sample (1h), a breast milk sample (1h), followed by feeding their child breast milk, and responded to online-questionnaires (1 and 3h). Blood sampling from the child is done 2h after breastfeeding (3h after maternal dose).

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The whole procedure is taking place in the morning, before lunch. As prednisolone is normally taken during or after having a meal, the mother should be offered something to eat before dose intake. Maternal blood sample is taken once; 1h after dose and at same time infant is fed.

Sampling is performed according to local routines and manufacturer instructions. At sampling, 2 LiHep tubes (à 7ml) are filled. If the participant already has a venous catheter she prefers to use, an additional slush tube (7 ml) with blood is drawn. In total, 1x2x7 ml (14 ml) is drawn from each adult participant (21 ml if an existing catheter is used).

Breast milk is sampled at one timepoint: 1h after maternal prednisolone intake. The breast milk sampling is carried out by the mother using an electric pump she receives from the project. The electric pump is of the same brand and model for all participants. Full milk expression from at least one of the breasts is mixed well and a 10- 20 ml sample is taken. After expression the mother feeds the infant the remaining milk that was expressed (and the milk from the other breast if only one is expressed by the pump for sampling).

A venous blood sample of the back of the hand is drawn from the child once, 3h after maternal dose intake. According to the scientific evidence and the clinical experiences this is the least painful type of blood drawn from infants (Shah & Ohlsson, Cochrane Library 2011). At sampling, 0.8 ml are drawn. 0.2 ml of the sample will be used for cortisol analysis. These sampling procedures follow established local clinical routines with adding of *emla* and/or sugar solution.

Sampling details (every sampling) and health-related details concerning herself and her child (every sampling) are collected using a questionnaire.

5.3.1. Handling, storage, and destruction of biological samples

The blood samples are transported to the local lab (in a temperature that is consistent with the stability conditions) for centrifugation and aliquoting. The aliquots are frozen at -20 C° and then shipped on wet ice to Uppsala Biobank.

The collected breast milk sample is immediately put in the freezer and stored at -20 C° before being shipped to Uppsala Biobank on wet ice for aliquoting. The aliquots are stored at -80 C° prior to analyses being performed.

5.3.2. Total volume of blood per subject

The total volume of blood taken from each subject during the trial is a maximum of 14 ml from the woman and 0.8 ml from the child.

5.3.3. Biobank

All samples taken in this trial are registered in at Uppsala Biobank (IVO no. 827) and handled according to the current biobank laws and regulations. The samples are coded/pseudonymized to protect the subject's identity. All samples and the identification/code list are stored securely and separately to prevent access by unauthorized persons.

5.4. End of Trial

The trial will be completed after 30 women have completed their participation in the study.

The trial may be prematurely terminated if it is necessary for safety reasons affecting the risk-benefit balance or if the recruitment of subjects cannot be met within reasonable time limits. The Swedish Medical Products Agency will be informed as soon as possible via CTIS, but no later than 15 days after trial termination.

Decisions on premature termination are taken by the sponsor.

6. Subject selection

Lactating women treated with prednisolone and their breastfed infants.

6.1. Inclusion criteria

To be included in the trial, subjects must meet all of the following criteria:

- Breastfeeding women treated with prednisolone with doses up to 50 mg/day for any condition. Only women of 18 years of age and older will be asked for participation.
- Breastfeeding children of women that have consented to participate in the study. The guardians of the child are asked for participation. Informed consent is also obtained from the father.

6.2. Exclusion criteria

Subjects must not be included in this trial if any of the following criteria are met:

- Women not able to read and communicate in Swedish or English.
- Women with infant born prior to 37 weeks gestation (premature).
- Women with multiple births.

6.3. Selection of subjects

Collection of samples will be made at three clinical sites, The Specialist maternity Clinic in Umeå, The maternity department at Södra Älvsborgs Hospital and the Specialist Clinic for Children and Young, at Liljeholmen/Astrid Lindgrens Barnsjukhus/Karolinska institutet.

General information about the project will be provided through a network of health care professionals via *Janusmed* at Region Stockholm and through information in social media. In collaboration with *the Rheumatism Association* and specialist antenatal care, patients treated with prednisolone, regardless of diagnosis (e.g., rheumatoid arthritis, SLE, myositis, psoriatic arthritis, inflammatory bowel disease) will be informed about the study with written information as well as a video describing the project. A link will be provided to the project webpage for more information.

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Women willing to participate in the study will be provided with detailed information about what this entails and provided with a written informed consent form, that they will sign and also ask their partners (the other care giver) to sign. They will bring the signed informed consent form with them to the medical doctor at the sampling center.

6.4. Withdrawal criteria

Discontinuation for individual subjects is based on withdrawal of consent. Withdrawal is made by notifying the local clinical staff or via the study website. Samples will be destroyed upon withdrawal. Pharmacokinetic data will be stored and part of further analysis together with data from those remaining in the study.

Subjects can discontinue their participation in the trial at any time without any consequence to his/her continued treatment. The investigator/sponsor can at any time terminate the trial for a subject due to, e.g., unacceptable adverse events/adverse reactions or because the subject cannot follow procedures in the clinical trial protocol. If the subject discontinues the trial, follow-up of this subject will be performed according to the clinic's routine.

7. Trial treatments

No treatment or medical prescriptions will be part of the trial. The project has thus a low intervention trial design in the sense that breast milk and blood will be collected merely to study excretion of prednisolone into breastmilk and transferal to her child. Participation in the study will not decide or in any other way interfere with patients' treatment as prescribed by their physician. Only patients that already have been assigned treatment with prednisolone by their physician will be approached and asked for participation.

7.1. Description of investigational medicinal product(s)

Not applicable.

7.2. Dose and administration

Prednisolone is dosed through several administration routes (oral, inhalation, intramuscular injection, intravenous, ophthalmic). The study will focus on oral administration and will not alter the route of administration, the dosage or the dosage regimen for prednisolone but the participants will continue their treatment as prescribed by their physician.

7.3. Drug accountability and treatment compliance

It will be assumed that the drug prescribed by the doctor is the correct drug. Women taking drugs administered by a pharmacy will self-report their use of medicines in online questionnaires.

Participants self-register the medicines they are using adjacent to sampling of breast milk and blood.

7.4. Randomization and blinding

No randomization or blinding will be performed.

7.5. Concomitant use of other medicinal products and treatments

Not applicable

7.6. Treatment after trial end

Not applicable, the study will not influence choice of treatment or dosage. The patients will continue with their prednisolone treatment, as prescribed by their physician.

8. Methods for measurement of endpoints for clinical efficacy and safety

8.1. Methods for measurement of endpoints for clinical efficacy

The project will only measure pharmacokinetic data of breast milk and blood related to a medicine that is already approved and administered in accordance with standard clinical care outside the protocol of this project. The project will not do any assessment of efficacy related to the treatment itself.

8.2. Methods for measurement of endpoints for clinical safety

For pharmacological safety the project will measure pharmacokinetic data of breast milk and blood related to a medicine that is already approved and administered in accordance with standard clinical procedures for women outside the protocol of this project. Adverse events that may impact on breastfeeding and/or breastmilk, e.g., mastitis, will be documented.

8.2.1. Specification of pharmacological safety parameters

Dosage of infant as Average Daily Infant Dose (ADID) in mg/kg/day will be estimated by using 200 mL/kg/day as a standard for daily milk intake in accordance with FDA guidelines for lactation studies (FDA Clinical Lactation Studies May 2019): "While a 150 mL/kg/day estimated milk intake is a reasonable assumption to estimate daily infant dosage, greater volumes do occur in early infancy and often correlate to the time of most reported infant adverse drug events. Additional consideration should be given to estimates of infant risk based on a 200 mL/kg/day milk intake in early infancy".

Relative infant dose (RID) will be calculated by dividing infant dosage (ADID) in mg/kg/day with maternal dosage in mg/kg/day, multiplied with 100 in order to get the percentage. It is estimated that a RID < 10% is considered safe for the infant (Bennet PN, Use of the monographs on drugs, Drugs and Human Lactation, 1996:67-74.).

The maternal prednisolone/prednisone milk to plasma ratio will be calculated by dividing drug concentration in the mother's milk with the drug concentration of the mother's plasma.

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Prednisolone concentration in infant blood will be reported.

Cortisol concentration in infant blood will be reported.

9. Handling of Adverse Events

Only serious adverse events (SAEs) and, for the women, signs of mastitis related to the breast milk sampling will be monitored and documented in a protocol. Other adverse events (AEs) related to blood and milk sampling will not be collected, e.g., pain or bruising at the injection site, as these are expected during sampling procedures.

Because all subjects included in the trial have started the prednisolone treatment before trial enrollment and the treatment is performed according to clinical praxis, no adverse events related to the medicinal product will be collected during the trial and the Sponsor will not perform SUSAR assessments.

9.1. Definitions

9.1.1. Adverse Event (AE)

Adverse Event (AE): Any untoward medical occurrence in a subject to whom a medicinal product is administered and which does not necessarily have a causal relationship with this treatment.

9.1.2. Adverse Reaction (AR)

In the pre-approval clinical experience with a new medicinal product or new use of a medicinal product, and particularly as the therapeutic dose(s) may not be established, all noxious and unintended reactions to the medicinal product related to any dose should be considered an adverse reaction (AR). The phrase “reaction” to a medicinal product means that the causal relationship between the medical product and an adverse event is at least a reasonable possibility, that is the relationship cannot be ruled out.

No investigational medicinal product will be administered during the study. Thus, no ARs will be reported.

9.1.3. Serious Adverse Event (SAE)

Serious adverse event (SAE): Any untoward medical occurrence that at any dose requires inpatient hospitalization or prolongation of existing hospitalisation, results in persistent or significant disability or incapacity, results in a congenital anomaly or birth defect, is life-threatening, or results in death.

Medical and scientific assessment will be made to determine if an event is serious and whether it would prompt reporting in other situations, for example important medical events that may not be directly life-threatening or result in death or hospitalization but may compromise the subject or may require intervention to prevent one of the other results set forth in the definitions above. These should also normally be considered as SAEs.

9.1.4. Suspected Unexpected Serious Adverse Reaction (SUSAR)

SUSAR: A reaction/event that is unexpected, serious, and suspected to be caused by the treatment, i.e. adverse reactions that are not included in the Investigator's Brochure (IB) or SPC.

No investigational medicinal product will be administered during the study. Thus, no SUSARs will be reported.

9.2. Assessment of Adverse Events (AE)

9.2.1. Assessment of seriousness

The investigator is responsible for assessing the seriousness (serious or non-serious). If the adverse event is considered serious, this should be reported as a serious adverse event (SAE) by the investigator to the sponsor. See also section 1.1.9.3.1, Reporting of Serious Adverse Events (SAE).

9.3. Reporting and registration of Adverse Events

9.3.1. Reporting of Serious Adverse Events (SAE)

It is considered highly unlikely that a serious adverse events (SAE) would occur during collection of samples from the participating women and children. The blood samples are drawn at the study site by experienced staff and all subjects are carefully monitored.

If the investigator assesses an event that occurred during sampling as serious, they should contact the sponsor as soon as possible by phone or email (see contact information below). An SAE report should also be filled out. Follow-up information describing the outcome and handling of the SAE is reported as soon as this information is available.

Sponsor representative: Mats Hansson
Email: mats.hansson@crb.uu.se
Phone: 018-4716197

9.3.2. Reporting of Suspected Unexpected Serious Adverse Reactions (SUSAR)

Not applicable.

9.4. Follow-up of Adverse Events

Signs of mastitis occurring in association with breast milk sampling will be monitored and documented at the sampling location and referral be made to an ordinary care unit.

If an SAE occurs during sampling, the subject will be monitored until the SAE is resolved.

9.5. Independent Data Monitoring Committee

Not applicable.

9.6. Annual Safety Report (ASR)

An annual safety report will be submitted in CTIS.

9.7. Procedures in case of emergencies, overdose or pregnancy

Not applicable. See reporting of SAEs 9.3.2.

10. Statistics

In general, summary statistics (n [number of available measurements], arithmetic mean, standard deviation [SD], median, minimum, and maximum) for quantitative variables and frequency tables for qualitative data will be presented. For prednisolone/prednisone concentrations, summary statistics will include geometric mean, geometric coefficient of variation (CV), 95% confidence intervals, arithmetic mean, arithmetic SD, median, minimum, and maximum. Any deviations from this general approach will be outlined in the SAP.

Values that are below the limit of quantification (BLQ) will be set to half the lower limit of quantification (LLOQ) for the calculation of descriptive statistics. Descriptive statistics will be calculated if at least 2/3 of the values are above the LLOQ. If this is not the case, only median, minimum, and maximum will be presented.

The concentration of prednisolone in the breastfeeding child's plasma 3 hr after maternal dose intake including ADID and RID will be summarized descriptively. The concentration of cortisol in the infant blood will also be summarized.

The concentration of prednisolone/prednisone in breast milk at 1h after maternal dose intake, the maternal plasma concentration of prednisolone/prednisone at 1h after maternal dose intake, and the milk to plasma ratio of the mother will be summarized descriptively.

10.1. Analysis population

All subjects included

10.2. Statistical analyses

10.2.1. Statistical methods

In general, summary statistics (n [number of available measurements], arithmetic mean, standard deviation [SD], median, minimum, and maximum) for quantitative variables and frequency tables for qualitative data will be presented. For prednisolone/prednisone concentrations, summary statistics will include geometric mean, geometric coefficient of variation (CV), 95% confidence intervals, arithmetic mean, arithmetic SD, median, minimum, and maximum. Any deviations from this general approach will be outlined in the SAP.

10.2.2. Drop-outs

All data regarding sampling with information on missing or spurious data, e.g., due to effect of other medications, will be recorded at sampling and stored at a secure dataportal (Allvis) at Uppsala University.

10.3. Sample size calculations

No formal sample size calculations have been performed as there are no statistical hypotheses being tested. The planned sample size for this study is 30 subjects. This sample size should provide sufficient data to assess the primary objective of the study.

10.4. Interim analysis

No interim analysis is planned for this study.

11. Quality Control and Quality Assurance

11.1. Quality Assurance and Sponsor oversight

Sampling follows established clinical routines at each site and is performed by specially trained staff. Biobanking and pharmacokinetic analyses follow qualified procedures.

The involved investigators and institutions will permit trial-related monitoring, audits, IRB/IEC review, and regulatory inspections, providing direct access to source data/documents.

Meetings with investigators, biobanking staff and sponsor representatives will be held at regular intervals in order to monitor that sampling, biobanking and analyses follow the protocol. Follow up of each sampling procedure will be made through the filled in report forms and trial specific documentation from each clinical site.

11.2. Monitoring

Sponsor representatives will monitor the trial in order to ensure that the subjects' safety and integrity are satisfied and check that reported data is reliable and of high quality.

Quality control will be attained through monitoring:

- that subjects exist
- that informed consent has been signed prior to execution of any trial-specific actions
- that subjects are included according to the protocol's inclusion and exclusion criteria
- that the trial's main parameters and safety reporting are handled correctly

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11.3. Source data

Data collected when sampling breast milk

Data collected from mother

Gestational age for most recent birth (self-reported)
Age (self-reported)
Medical condition that motivates treatment with prednisolone (self-reported)
Height (self-reported)
Weight (self-reported)
Any medication(s), and the doses, she is currently using (self-reported)
Any traditional medicinal products, and doses, she is currently using (self-reported)
Dosage of prednisolone (self-reported)
Information on whether the woman can remember missing a dose of prednisolone in the last three days
Time-point for dose intake (0h)
Age of infant (self-reported)
Infant height (self-reported)
Infant weight (self-reported)
Infant medicine use (self-reported)
Any traditional medicinal products the infant is using (self-reported)
Time for last breastfeeding/ bottle feeding of the expressed breast milk
Time for starting breast milk expression (self-reported)
Information whether the woman is exclusively breast-feeding or if the infant is getting supplemental food

Data collected at maternal blood sampling and infant breastfeeding at 1 hr

Data collected by personnel immediately after drawing blood from mother

Time-point for blood sampling
Venipuncture site selection
How blood was drawn (e.g., venipuncture, peripheral venous catheter, port-à-cath)
Tube type used for blood drawing
Any venipuncture equipment used to draw blood (self-reported)
Time-point for breast milk sampling (reported by health care professional)

Data collected at infant blood sampling at 3h

Time-point for blood sampling
Site selection
How blood was drawn (e.g., back of hand)
Tube type used for blood drawing
Collected data will be pseudonymized and encoded. Data and key to the code will be kept separately. Study participants will be given a Study-ID when enrolled and consented.

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Source data, SOPs, master protocols and templates will be stored at Uppsala Biobank. Bioanalytical data (validation, stability, and measured drug concentration values from clinical samples) will be stored at UDOPP.

11.4. Deviations, serious breaches and other reporting obligations

The investigators at each clinical site will, without delay, report to the sponsor any serious breaches and deviations from the trial protocol, ICH-GCP and other regulations that significantly and directly affect, or with high likelihood could affect, the subjects' safety and integrity or the reliability and robustness of the data generated in the trial. The sponsor will assess the suspected serious breach and the consequences of deviations that have occurred, and, without undue delay but no later than 7 days (from knowledge) report these to the Swedish Medical Products Agency via CTIS.

Other unexpected events that may affect the benefit/risk relationship will be reported via CTIS without undue delay, but no later than 15 days after the sponsor becomes aware of the event.

Minor deviations that do not affect subjects' integrity or safety, nor significantly affect the trial's scientific value, are documented in the trial documentation of the principal investigator and the sponsor and appropriate measures will be taken. The deviations will be recorded in the clinical trial report.

11.5. Audits and inspections

Authorized representatives for the sponsor and Competent Authorities (CA) may carry out audits or inspections at the trial site, including source data verification. The investigator will ensure that all source documents are available for audits and inspections.

12. Ethics

12.1. Compliance to the protocol, ICH-GCP and regulations

The trial will be performed in compliance with the EU regulation on low-intervention clinical trials on medicinal products for human use (536/2014), the Declaration of Helsinki, ICH-GCP standards applicable to the trial procedures, and current national regulations governing this clinical trial. This is to ensure the safety and integrity of the trial subjects as well as the quality of the data collected.

12.2. Ethical review of the trial

The final protocol for clinical trials on medicinal products will be approved, as a part of the application for a permit for clinical trials via CTIS, by both the Swedish Ethical Review Authority and the Swedish Medical Products Agency before the trial will be conducted. The authority will be informed via CTIS of any changes in the trial protocol in accordance with current requirements.

12.3. Procedure for obtaining informed consent

The principal investigator at each site will ensure that the subject is given full and adequate oral and written information about the trial, its purpose, any risks and benefits as well as inclusion and exclusion criteria. Subjects will also be informed that they are free to discontinue their participation in the trial at any time without having to provide a reason. Subjects will be given the opportunity to ask questions and be allowed time to consider the provided information.

If the person chooses to participate, both the subject and the investigator shall sign the informed consent form. The women participating in the trial will also ask their partners (the other care giver) to sign). They will bring the signed informed consent form with them to the medical doctor at the sampling center who will sign the form. A copy of the subject information as well as the informed consent form will be provided to the woman. The subject's signed and dated informed consent will be obtained before any trial-specific activity is performed. Each subject who participates in the trial will be identified by a subject number on a subject identification list.

12.4. Data protection

In the information provided to subjects, subjects will be fully informed about how their trial data will be collected, used and disclosed. The content of the informed consent form complies with relevant integrity and data protection legislation. The subject information and the informed consent form will explain how trial data are stored to maintain confidentiality in accordance with national data legislation (see section 14). All information processed by the sponsor will be pseudonymized and coded.

The informed consent form will also explain that for verification of the data, representatives delegated by the sponsor, as well as relevant authorities, may require access to parts of medical records or trial records that are relevant to the trial, including the subject's medical history.

12.5. Insurances

No insurance except the ordinary Patient damage insurance.

13. Substantial changes to the trial

Substantial changes to the signed clinical trial protocol are only possible through approved protocol amendments.

In the event that substantial changes to the protocol which may affect the safety, rights of subjects or the reliability and robustness of data generated need to be implemented during the course of the trial, permission from the relevant authority via application in CTIS will be obtained before implementing the change. This includes the addition of a new trial site or a change of the principal investigator at the trial site.

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Non-substantial amendments are entered into the CTIS in the next substantial amendment application concerning the same part. If the non-substantial change is relevant to the Authority's oversight (e.g. contact details), the CTIS will be updated on an ongoing basis.

14. Collection, handling, and archiving of data

Sampling details and health-related details will be collected using a paper questionnaire and then registered in the program REDCAP (Research Electronic Data Capture). Informed consent forms are sent by registered mail to Uppsala University and stored in a locked cabinet only accessible by authorised personnel. Data will be uploaded in an encrypted format which then will be hosted at a locked and secure server of Uppsala University (Dataportal Allvis) and Region Uppsala in accordance with an established process approved by the Swedish Ethical Review Authority. Collected data will be pseudonymized and encoded. Data and key to the code will be kept separately. Study participants will be given a Study-ID when enrolled and consented.

The complete Trial Master File with essential documents will be archived for at least 25 years. Source data in the medical records system are stored and archived in accordance with national regulations.

14.1. Case Report Form

A Case Report Form (CRF) is used for data collection. It includes three separate paper forms filled in at sampling (See attachments). The investigator will ensure that data is registered and any corrections in the CRF are made as stated in the clinical trial protocol and in accordance with the instructions. The investigator will ensure that the registered data is correct, complete, and that reporting takes place according to the timelines that have been predefined and agreed. The principal investigator signs the completed forms. A copy of the completed forms will be archived at the site.

15. Notification of trial completion, reporting, and publication

End of the trial is reported in CTIS at the latest 15 days after completion.

Within one year of trial completion, a clinical study report is completed, and a summary of the clinical trial results will be reported in CTIS, including a summary for lay people.

Scientific publications based on the study results will adhere to Vancouver guidelines.

16. References

- Bermas BL. Lactation and Management of Postpartum Disease. *Rheum Dis Clin N Am* 43 (2017) 249–262.
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- Greenberger PA, Odeh YK, Frederiksen MC, et al. Pharmacokinetics of prednisolone transfer to breast milk. *Clin Pharmacol Ther.* 1993;53:324–8.

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- Katz FH, Duncan BR. Entry of prednisone into human milk [letter]. *N Engl J Med* 1975;293:1154.
- Ost L, Wettrell G, Bjorkhem I, et al. Prednisolone excretion in human milk. *J Pediatr* 1985;106:1008–11.

17. Attachments

Frågeformulär 1-3

Frågeformulär 1 (fylls i av deltagare vid provtillfället för bröstmjolk)

Studie: Läkemedelsbehandling med Prednisolon i samband med amning

Deltagares studie-ID:

Datum: ____/____/____ (t. ex. 20/01/2012)

Tid: _____

Instruktion:

Detta frågeformulär syftar till att samla in information som skall användas vid analys av dina prover. Informationen kommer att behandlas så att inte obehöriga kan ta del av den. *Detta frågeformulär fylls i efter bröstmjölksprovet.*

Information om dig

1. Hur gammal är du? _____ år

2. Hur lång är du? _____ cm

3. Hur mycket väger du? _____kg

4. För vilken diagnos tar du Prednisolon?

[Fritext:] _____

5. Använder du några andra mediciner?

Nej Ja

Om ja, ange namn: _____

6. Använder du något/några naturläkemedel?

Nej Ja

Om ja, ange namn: _____

7. Vilken dos av Prednisolon tar du? (till exempel 1 tablett á 20 mg per dag)?

[Fritext:] _____

8. Ange när du tog din senaste dos av Prednisolon:

Datum: ____/____/____ (t. ex. 20/01/2012)

Tid: _____

9. Ange om du kan minnas att du har missat en dos under de senaste tre dagarna:

- Jag har inte missat en dos under den tiden
- Jag missade en dos igår
- Jag har missat en dos i förrgår
- Jag är osäker

Information om ditt barn

10. Hur gammalt är ditt barn? [Fritext:] _____

11. I vilken graviditetsvecka föddes ditt barn? I vecka _____ och dag _____

12. Hur lång är ditt barn? _____ cm

13. Vad väger ditt barn? _____ g

14. Vilken mat får ditt barn?

- Mitt barn ammas enbart
- Mitt barn delammas och får bröstmjölksersättning

15. Ges ditt barn för närvarande läkemedel/örter/vitaminer/mineraler?

- Nej
- Ja

Om ja, ange namn på preparatet: _____

Information om provtagning av bröstmjolk

16. Ange när du senast ammade/gav ditt barn urpumpad bröstmjolk:

Datum: ____/____/____ (t. ex. 20/01/2012)

Tid: _____

17. Vid vilken tidpunkt började du pumpa ur bröstmjolk?

Datum: ____/____/____ (t. ex. 20/01/2012)

Tid: _____

Frågeformulär 2 (fylls i av personal efter blodprov)

Studie: Läkemedelsbehandling med Prednisolon i samband med amning

Deltagares studie-ID:

Datum: ____/____/____ (t. ex. 20/01/2012)

Tid: _____

Instruktion:

Detta frågeformulär syftar till att samla in information som skall användas vid analys av deltagarens prover. Informationen kommer att behandlas så att inte obehöriga kan ta del av den. *Detta frågeformulär fylls i efter blodprovstagningsstillfället.*

Information om blodprovstagning

1. Ange datum och tidpunkt för blodprovtagning:

Datum: ____/____/____ (t. ex. 20/01/2012)

Tid: _____

2. Ange vart blodprovet togs:

vänster arm höger arm bägge sidor annan lokalisation

3. Hur togs blodprovet:

Genom venpunktion

Från en perifer venkateter (PVK)

Från en port-a-cath (subkutan venport, SVP)

Från en PICC-line

Från en annan typ av kateter: _____

4. Ange vilken typ av provrör som användes:

5. Ange vilken typ av utrustning som användes för venöst blodprov:

6. Ange datum och tidpunkt för lämnande av bröstmjölksprov:

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Datum: ____/____/____ (t. ex. 20/01/2012)

Tid: _____

7. Övrig information:

[Fritext:] _____

Frågeformulär 3 (fylls i av personal efter blodprov på barnet)

Studie: Läkemedelsbehandling med Prednisolon i samband med amning

Deltagares studie-ID:

Datum: ____/____/____ (t. ex. 20/01/2012)

Tid: _____

Instruktion:

Detta frågeformulär syftar till att samla in information som skall användas vid analys av blodprovet som tagits på deltagarens barn. Informationen kommer att behandlas så att inte obehöriga kan ta del av den. *Detta frågeformulär skall fyllas i en gång, efter att blodprov tagits på barnet.*

Information om blodprovstagning

18) Ange datum och tidpunkt för blodprovtagning av barnet:

Datum: ____/____/____ (t. ex. 20/01/2012)

Tid: _____

19) Ange vart blodprovet togs (t. ex häl, handrygg osv):

20) Ange vilken typ av provrör som användes:

21) Övrig information:

[Fritext:] _____

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CLINICAL TRIAL PROTOCOL

Transfer of metformin into human breast milk and the plasma of breastfeeding children - A low intervention trial with biobanking of breast milk and plasma in Västra Götalandsregionen and Region Örebro

EU Trial number: 2022-501693-19-00

Version number: 3.0

Date: 2023-12-18

Sponsor: Uppsala University
Centre for Research Ethics & Bioethics,
Department of Public Health and Caring Sciences,
Uppsala University, Box 564,
SE-751 22 Uppsala, Sweden

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Description of changes in the trial protocol

Protocol version	Summary of changes <i>Describe all changes since the first final protocol.</i>
v.2.0	<u>New sections were added:</u> Sections 1, 3, 5.3.1-3, 9, 11.2, 11.3, 12.4, 13-15 <u>Some sections were clarified:</u> Sections 5.4 and 6.4 Section 9.4 Follow-up of Adverse Events was changed to include follow-up of subjects who experience an SAE

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Signature page

Sponsor

I am responsible for ensuring that this protocol includes all essential information to be able to conduct this trial. I will submit the protocol and all other important trial-related information to the responsible investigator(s) so that they can conduct the trial correctly. I am aware that it is my responsibility to hold the staff members who work with this trial informed and trained.

Sponsor's signature

Date

Mats Hansson
Senior Professor

Principal Investigator

I have read this protocol and agree that it includes all essential information to be able to conduct the trial. By signing my name below, I agree to conduct the trial in compliance with this clinical trial protocol, the EU Regulation on clinical trials of medicinal products for human use (EU 536/2014), the Declaration of Helsinki, ICH-GCP (Good Clinical Practice) guidelines and the current national regulations governing the conduct of this clinical trial.

I will submit this protocol and all other important trial-related information to the staff members and investigators who participate in this trial, so that they can conduct the trial correctly. I am aware of my responsibility to continuously keep the staff members and investigators who work with this trial informed and trained.

I am aware that quality control of this trial will be performed in the form of monitoring and eventual audit and inspection.

Principal Investigator's signature

Date

Jarl Hellman,
Consultant Physician, Associate Professor

Contact information

Responsibility in the clinical trial	
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Principal Investigators	<p>Jarl Hellman, Consultant Physician, Associate Professor</p> <p>Address: Uppsala University Hospital, ing. 40, 5tr, SE-751 85 Uppsala, Sweden</p> <p>Phone: 018-6114341</p> <p>Helena Backman, Överläkare, docent. Obstetrik och gynekologi</p> <p>Universitetssjukhuset</p> <p>701 85 Örebro</p> <p>Phone: 072-7121258</p> <p>Email: helena.backman@regionorebrolan.se</p> <p>Linda Englund-Ögge, Överläkare. Obstetrikheten</p> <p>Östra sjukhuset</p> <p>416 85 Göteborg</p> <p>Phone: 031-343 41 74</p> <p>Email: linda.englund-ogge@vgregion.se</p>
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	<p>Address: Sahlgrenska Universitetssjukhuset, Biobank Väst, 413 45 Göteborg Email: biobankvast@vgregion.se</p> <p>Örebro Biobank (454) Kliniskt forskningscentrum (KFC) Address: Campus-USÖ, X-huset (vån 4), Örebro Universitetssjukhus, 701 85 Örebro Email: biobanksupplysningen@regionorebrolan.se</p>
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List of used acronyms and abbreviations

Abbreviation	Term/Explanation
ADID	Average Daily Infant Dose
Adverse Event (AE)	Any untoward medical occurrence in a subject to whom a medicinal product is administered and which does not necessarily have a causal relationship with this treatment.
AR	Adverse Reaction = any unfavorable and unexpected reaction to an investigational medicinal product, regardless of dose
ASR	Annual Safety Report = the annual safety report for reporting to authorities. In Sweden this is the Swedish Medical Products Agency via CTIS.
BLQ	Below the limit of quantification
CA	Competent Authorities
CRF	Case Report Form
CTIS	Clinical Trials Information System = Centralized EU database/portal for application and communication with authorities concerning clinical trials. In Sweden this includes the Swedish Medical Products Agency and the Swedish Ethical Review Authority.
ENTIS	the European Network of Teratology Information Services
ICH-GCP	International Council for Harmonization Good Clinical Practice
LLOQ	lower limit of quantification
NMBR	the National Medical Birth Register
NPDR	the National Prescribed Drug Register
REDCAP	Research Electronic Data Capture
RID	Relative infant dose

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Serious Adverse Event (SAE)	Any untoward medical occurrence that at any dose requires inpatient hospitalisation or prolongation of existing hospitalisation, results in persistent or significant disability or incapacity, results in a congenital anomaly or birth defect, is life-threatening, or results in death
SD	Standard deviation
SUSAR	Suspected Unexpected Serious Adverse Reaction. This is an event that is likely related to the investigational medicinal product but with unexpected occurrence. An adverse reaction is unexpected if its nature or seriousness is not consistent with the information on the product in the RSI.

1. Swedish synopsis

EU prövningsnummer:	2022-501693-19-00
Titel:	Överföring av metformin till bröstmjolk och plasma från ammande barn - En låginterventionsstudie med biobanking av bröstmjolk och plasma i Västra Götalandsregionen och Örebroregionen
Kort bakgrund/ Rational/Syfte:	För många läkemedel saknas idag tillräckliga underlag för hur läkemedlet kan påverka barnet som ammas. Det har i många fall inneburit att man av försiktighetsskäl sätter ut läkemedlet eller rekommenderar mamman att inte amma. Samtidigt har mamman bäst nytta av det förskrivna läkemedlet och man vet att amning är bra både för det nyfödda barnet och för mamman. Syftet med studien är att undersöka om och hur mycket av metformin som går över via bröstmjölken till barnet från mamman som har fått läkemedlet förskrivet.
Primärt syfte:	Det primära syftet är att bestämma koncentrationen av metformin i plasman hos ammade spädbarn till ammande kvinnor som behandlas för typ 2 diabetes.
Sekundärt syfte:	Sekundärt mål är att bestämma koncentrationen av metformin i bröstmjölken och moderns plasma och mjölk-till-plasmaförhållandet hos mödrarna och att beräkna den genomsnittliga dagliga spädbarnsdosen (ADID) och relativ spädbarnsdos (RID).
Primärt utfallsmått:	Det primära utfallsmåttet är koncentrationen av metformin i det ammande barnets plasma 4 timmar efter moderns dosintag.
Sekundärt utfallsmått:	De sekundära effektmåtten är koncentrationen av metformin i bröstmjolk 2 timmar efter moderns dosintag och moderns plasmakoncentration av metformin 2 timmar efter metforminintag.
Prövningsdesign:	Studien har en låg interventionell design i den meningen att bröstmjolk och blod samlas in enbart för att studera utsöndringen av metformin i bröstmjölken och överföring till det ammade barnet.
Prövningspopulation:	Ammande kvinnor över 18 år som behandlas med metformin och deras nyfödda barn (6-8 veckor efter födseln)

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Antal försökspersoner:	30
Inklusionskriterier:	Ammande kvinnor som behandlas med metformin med doser upp till 1000 mg/dag. Endast kvinnor från 18 år och äldre kommer att tillfrågas om att delta. Ammande barn till kvinnor som har samtyckt till att delta i studien. Vårdnadshavare till barnet tillfrågas och informerats om samtycke inhämtas också från fadern
Exklusionskriterier:	Kvinnor som redan deltagit i studien. Kvinnor med spädbarn födda före 37 veckors graviditet (för tidig). Kvinnor med flerbörd.
Intervention:	Ingen behandling förekommer i studien, se ovan.
Prövningsläkemedel, dosering, administrering:	Metformin med doser upp till 1000mg/dag i enlighet med förskrivning av läkare.
Etiska överväganden, nytta/risk:	Risk-nytta-balansen avseende metformin påverkas inte av att delta i studien. Provtagningen görs enligt etablerade kliniska rutiner. Man känner ett lätt stick när man tar ett blodprov. Man kan få ett blåmärke och det finns alltid en liten risk att påverka en nerv, vilket kan uttryckas som smärta eller domningar. Vid blodprov tas totalt 14 ml blod vid ett tillfälle. Detta kan jämföras med de 450 ml blod som tas under en normal blodgivning. Försökspersonerna förväntas inte ha någon direkt nytta av att delta i studien. Studieresultaten kommer dock att kunna bidra med information som i framtiden kan hjälpa ammande kvinnor att fatta ett välgrundat beslut om användning av metformin i samband med amning. Sådan information kommer också att hjälpa vårdpersonal att ge evidensbaserade råd till ammande kvinnor om användningen av metformin.
Prövningsperiod:	Q1 2024-Q4 2024, Publicering inom ett år efter studiens avslut.

2. Background and rationale

More than 5 million women get pregnant in the EU every year and a majority take at least one medication during pregnancy. As few as 5% of available medications have been adequately monitored, tested and labelled with safety information for use in pregnant and breastfeeding women. The field, while inherently difficult to study, has suffered from a lack of systematically gathered insights that could lead to more effective data generation methodologies. Fragmentation and misinformation results in confusing and contradictory communication and perception of risks by both health professionals and women and their families.

In clinical settings doctors often take a precautionary approach and discontinue the prescription of a given drug during pregnancy and breast feeding, or recommend to stop breast feeding. There is a cost of this approach, both for the woman and for her child. The woman is in need of the drug, which may not be replaceable by another drug, and one knows that breast feeding is good, both for the mother and for the child. The lack of evidence regarding transfer of drug to the breastfeeding infant may thus impose both women and their children to increased risks.

Anecdotal evidence from doctors in Sweden indicate that clinical practice differs, some withdraw the drug, others continue. In order to get reliable data on prescription The National Board of Health and Welfare did a cross match of the National Prescribed Drug Register (NPDR) and the National Medical Birth Register (NMBR) for 45 different drugs that according to the European Network of Teratology Information Services (ENTIS) lacked sufficient scientific evidence for use during pregnancy and breastfeeding. A threshold of 500 prescriptions/year for entire Sweden was set. Among the 12 drugs that so were identified was *metformin*.

There are limited data on how much metformin is transferred to the human breastmilk and any effects on breastfeeding children. We have identified five clinical publications, covering six studies, which have measured excretion of metformin in maternal blood and breast milk and health-related aspects of the breastfeeding children.

Five studies have estimated the concentration of metformin in plasma or serum after recruiting three to seven lactating women respectively (Hale et al., 2002; Gardiner et al., 2003; Briggs et al., 2005; and Eyal et al., 2010). The participants have been treated with metformin for preexisting diabetes, GDM, or PCOS and had reached steady state, with exception from one study where healthy women were given single doses of metformin (Gardiner et al., 2003, study II). Their metformin intake have ranged from 500 mg to 3000 mg per day and a few participants have been on extended release tablets. The lowest reported maternal peak plasma concentrations have been 0.5-0.7 mg/L (Gardiner et al., 2003), and the highest 1.61 mg/L (SD +-0.83 mg/L; Eyal et al., 2010). The peak concentration in plasma or serum have occurred at 1.8-4 h after intake and the reported half-life in serum/plasma has varied between 2 h and 6.3 h (Hale et al., 2002; Gardiner et al., 2003; Briggs et al., 2005; Eyal et al., 2010).

All previous studies have detected low concentrations of metformin in expressed breast milk. Sampling have taken place 4 days to 15 months postpartum (Hale et al., 2002; Gardiner et al., 2003; Briggs et al., 2005; Eyal et al., 2010). Mean or median concentrations have been between 0.17 mg/L and 0.41 mg/L (Hale et al., 2002; Gardiner et al., 2003; Briggs et al., 2005; Eyal et al., 2010). One study has reported a mean peak concentration of 0.42 mg/L (0.38mg/L to 0.46mg/L; Briggs et al., 2005). The concentration graphs in milk have shown to be relatively flat; Briggs et al. (2005) have reported a mean difference in concentrations between trough and peak of 21%. The half-life in breast milk has been estimated to be about 14-15 h (Gardiner et al., 2003, study II). The reported milk-to-plasma (area under the curve) ratios have varied among participants, from 0.27 to 0.71, with study means of 0.37-0.54 (Hale et al., 2002; Gardiner et al., 2003; Briggs et al., 2005; Eyal et al., 2010).

Six studies have reported health data concerning breastfeeding children of women using metformin. The children have been between 4 days and 15 months old and have weighed between 2.8 kg and 15 kg. The infant plasma concentrations have been measured for six children in total, of which metformin has not been detected for four of them (Hale et al., 2002; Gardiner et al., 2003). The two children who have had detectable levels have had plasma concentrations of 0.08 mg/L and 0.05 mg/L at 5.3 and 6 h respectively, after maternal dose intake (Hale et al., 2002). The estimated child doses per day have been between 0.014 mg/kg/day and 0.070 mf/kg/day with means between 0.030 and 0.040 mg/kg/day (Hale et al., 2002; Gardiner et al., 2003; Briggs et al., 2005). The mean relative infant doses, normalized to maternal weight, have ranged from 0,18% to 0,65% (Hale et al., 2002; Gardiner et al., 2003; Briggs et at., 2005; and Eyal et al., 2010). Briggs et al. (2005) have measured Blood glucose of three breastfeeding infants showing normal levels, 47-77mg/dl.

Breastfeeding children with maternal use of metformin (n=61) have been reported to show normal development (Hale et al., 2002) with no differences in length, weight, and motor-social development during their first 18 months, in comparison to children that have not breastfed (Glueck et al., 2006). Studies report no evidence of adverse effects among participating children (Gardiner et al., 2003; Briggs et al., 2005).

Until today then, only a handful of publications have studied how maternal metformin treatment affects breastfeeding and the breastfeeding child. To better understand any risks that the breastfeeding child is exposed to, it is important to study the excretion of metformin in breast milk and the levels of metformin in the plasma of the breastfeeding child (Hale et al., 2002; Gardiner et al., 2003; Briggs et al., 2005; Glueck et al., 2006; and Eyal et al., 2010).

3. Benefit-risk evaluation

The project will not change the woman's treatment in any way, therefore participation will not expose her to additional risks. When taking a blood sample, you usually feel a slight sting. You can get a bruise and there is always a small risk of nerve damage, which can be expressed as pain or numbness. When taking a blood sample, a total of 28 ml of blood will be collected divided into two occasions. This can be compared to the 450 ml of blood taken

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during a normal blood donation. Only data relating to the sampling procedure is collected, as well as any information about other medicines the woman is taking. However, the integrity risk associated with this is minimized by pseudonymizing the data and by storing the data and code key separately.

The research subjects are not expected to receive any direct benefit from participating in the study.

There is no change regarding the prescription of metformin, but this is done according to the doctor's regular prescription. The risk-benefit balance regarding metformin is thus not affected by participating in the project. The sampling is done according to established clinical routines. As stated in the research subject information, you usually feel a slight sting when taking a blood sample. You can get a bruise and there is always a small risk of nerve damage, which can be expressed as pain or numbness. When taking a blood sample, a total of 28 ml of blood will be collected divided into two occasions. This can be compared to the 450 ml of blood taken during a normal blood donation.

The research subjects are not expected to benefit directly from participating in the study. However, the study results will be able to contribute information that in the future can help breastfeeding women to make an informed decision about using Metformin in connection with breastfeeding. Such information will also help healthcare professionals to provide evidence-based advice to breastfeeding women about the use of Metformin.

An alternative to obtain data regarding the transfer of drugs during breastfeeding is to only collect breast milk. However, it is only when you also take a blood sample from the breastfed child that you get reliable data on how much of the medicine is actually transferred to the child. This is also the "golden standard" that applies to lactation studies internationally. Blood sampling in children is associated with a pain problem. The clinical scientifically supported routine that the project follows is to take a venous blood sample on the back of the hand. In connection with this, emla and/or sugar solution is given. This blood sampling is done by experienced healthcare personnel. Only data associated with the sampling procedure and which other drugs the woman is on are documented. Privacy risks are further minimized by pseudonymisation.

The project is intended to demonstrate how biobanking and sampling of breast milk and blood plasma should be done in order for the obtained analysis results to meet regulatory requirements from the EMA and FDA respectively. This can be of great benefit for all other situations where there is currently not sufficient evidence regarding the transfer of a medicine to the child during breastfeeding, something that applies to almost all medicines. By establishing a biobank with breast milk and associated samples of blood plasma for research, there is also an opportunity to investigate in the future how e.g., genetic factors can affect drug transfer. In the future, you can also get data to follow up the effects on the children.

Side-effects shown in trials and reported after marketing, according to the product information of Metformin:

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Metabolism and nutrition disorders

Very rare (<1/10 000): Lactic acidosis, decrease of vitamin B12 absorption with decrease of serum levels during long term use of metformin. Consideration of such aetiology is recommended if a patient presents with megaloblastic anaemia

Nervous system disorders

Common ($\geq 1/100$, < 1/10): Taste disturbance

Gastrointestinal disorders

Very common ($\geq 1/10$): Gastrointestinal disorders such as nausea, vomiting, diarrhoea, abdominal pain and loss of appetite. These undesirable effects occur most frequently during initiation of therapy and resolve spontaneously in most cases. To prevent them, it is recommended that Metformin be taken in 2 or 3 daily doses during or after meals. A slow increase of the dose may also improve gastrointestinal tolerability.

Hepatobiliary disorders

Very rare (< 1/10 000): Isolated reports of liver function tests abnormalities or hepatitis resolving upon metformin hydrochloride discontinuation.

Skin and subcutaneous tissue disorders

Very rare (< 1/10 000): Skin reactions such as erythema, pruritus, urticarial

Pediatric population

In published and post marketing data and in controlled clinical studies in a limited paediatric population aged 10-16 years treated during 1 year, adverse event reporting was similar in nature and severity to that reported in adults.

4. Trial objectives

4.1. Primary objective

The primary trial objective is to determine the concentration of metformin in plasma of breastfed infants of lactating women treated for GDM and T2D.

4.2. Secondary objective(s)

Secondary objectives are to:

1. Determine the milk-to-plasma ratio in the women, and;
2. Based on absolute infant dose (AID) and dosage of mother, the relative infant dose will be calculated.

4.3. Primary endpoint

The primary endpoint is the concentration of metformin in the breastfeeding child's plasma 4h after maternal dose intake.

4.4. Secondary endpoint

The secondary endpoints are:

1. The concentration of metformin in breast milk at 0h (through) and 2h after intake.
2. The maternal plasma concentration of metformin at 0h (trough) and 2h after intake.

5. Trial design and procedures

5.1. Overall trial design

Low intervention trial with biobanking of breast milk and plasma

Collection of samples will be made at two clinical sites, the Breast-feeding Center, Department of Obstetrics, Sahlgrenska University Hospital, Östra, in Göteborg and the Breast-feeding Center, Department of Obstetrics, Örebro University Hospital.

General information about the project will be provided in Swedish, Arabic, Persian, Somali and English via a Facebook group of patients with Diabetes hosted by the Swedish patient organisation Diabetesförbundet, through a network of health care professionals via Janusmed at Region Stockholm, to Swedish physicians in Diabetes care, and through information in social media, posters at obstetric clinics, maternity clinics and endocrinology clinics in Sweden. A video will be distributed through these channels. A link will be provided to the project webpage for more information.

Specific information about the study will be provided via the obstetric departments and associated maternity clinics, childcare centers and breast-feeding centers. Leaflets, posters and video presentations will be available at the clinical sites. The video will also be distributed via social media, e.g., instagram.

In total 30 women, 15 from the region of Örebro and 15 from the region of Göteborg, who are breastfeeding and also taking metformin will be included in the cohort. The project will not alter the route of administration, the dosage or the dosage regimen for metformin but the participants will continue their treatment as prescribed by their physician.

The project has thus a low intervention trial design in the sense that breast milk and blood will be collected merely to study excretion of metformin into breastmilk and transferal to her child. Participation in the study will not decide or in any other way interfere with patients' treatment as prescribed by their physician. Only patients that already have been assigned treatment with metformin by their physician will be approached and asked for participation. All procedures for blood collection will follow established clinical routines at the clinical sites. The sampling will take place \approx 6-8 weeks postpartum.

All information will be available in Swedish, English, Arabic, Persian and Somali. Interpretation assistance will be available at the clinical sites for sampling.

Request for participation and informed consent

Women willing to participate in the study will be provided with detailed information about what this entails and provided with a written informed consent form, that they will sign and also ask their partners (the other care giver) to sign. They will bring the signed informed consent form with them to the medical doctor at the sampling center.

Breast milk will be collected at two times during the visit, using an electric breast milk pump. Venous blood will be collected from the woman and from the infant. After centrifugation, plasma samples and breast milk sample will be aliquotated, frozen at -80 degrees and stored at Biobank Väst and Örebro Biobank, respectively. When all samples have been collected, they will be transferred to Uppsala Biobank. Samples will be analysed for pharmacokinetic properties using mass spectrometry at the UDOPP Platform (Uppsala Drug Optimization and Pharmaceutical Profiling) at the Department of Pharmacy, Uppsala University.

5.2. Procedures and flow chart

Trial diagram

5.3 Biological sampling procedures

Following FDA recommendations, lactation studies should preferentially not be initiated earlier than 6 weeks after delivery, to allow the mother to go back to a normal physiology (and also to not interfere with mother-child bonding). Thus, sampling takes place after development of mature milk, ≈ six-eight weeks postpartum. The sampling will take place after achieving steady state; after having been on metformin without any dosage changes for a minimum of two weeks. All sampling takes place the same day at the neonatal clinic in Göteborg, or at the breastfeeding clinic in Örebro. The mother brings her own metformin medications to the clinic.

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As metformin is normally taken during or after having a meal, the mother will be offered something to eat before trough sampling and dose intake. Infant is breastfed at 1 h after maternal medicine intake, and whenever the mother wants after that. Maternal blood samples are taken twice; before first dose of the day, and after 2h (peak). Sampling is performed according to local clinical routines and manufacturer instructions. At each sampling, 2 LiHep tubes (à 7ml) are filled. If the participant already has a venous catheter she prefers to use, an additional slush tube (7 ml) with blood is drawn. In total, 2x2x7 ml (28 ml) is drawn from each participant (43 ml if an existing catheter is used).

Breast milk is sampled at two occasions; a trough sample and then at 2h after metformin intake. The breast milk sampling is carried out by the mother using an electric pump she receives from the project. The electric pump is of the same brand and model for all participants. Full milk expressions from one of the breasts are homogenized and 20 ml samples are taken at each sampling. In total, 40 ml are sampled from each participant. The mother documents the time point of the most recent breast/bottle feeding and decides what to do with the remaining milk, if she wants to give it to her baby or not. The samples are transferred to respective biobanks for aliquotation. The aliquots are stored at -80 C° in waiting to be shipped to Uppsala, and there for analyses to be performed.

A venous blood sample of the back of the hand is drawn from the child once, 4h after maternal dose intake, if the parents have agreed to. According to the scientific evidence and the clinical experiences this is the least painful type of blood drawn from infants (Shah & Ohlsson, Cochrane Library 2011). At sampling, 0.8 ml are drawn. These sampling procedures follows established local clinical routines with adding of emla and/or sugar solution.

Sampling details (every sampling) and health-related details are collected using a paper questionnaire. Associated LIMS data are sent in an established encrypted form. Informed consent forms are sent by registered mail to Uppsala University and stored in a locked cabinet only accessible by authorised personnel.

5.3.1. Handling, storage, and destruction of biological samples

The blood samples are transported to the local lab (in a temperature that is consistent with the stability conditions) for centrifugation and aliquoting. The aliquots are frozen at -20 C° and then shipped on wet ice to Uppsala Biobank.

The collected breast milk sample is immediately put in the freezer and stored at -20 C° before being shipped to Uppsala Biobank on wet ice for aliquoting. The aliquots are stored at -80 C° prior to analyses being performed.

5.3.2. Total volume of blood per subject

The total volume of blood taken from each subject during the trial is a maximum of 28 ml from the woman and 0.8 ml from the child.

5.3.3. Biobank

All samples taken in this trial are registered in at Uppsala Biobank (IVO no. 827) and handled according to the current biobank laws and regulations. The samples are coded/pseudonymized to protect the subject's identity. All samples and the identification/code list are stored securely and separately to prevent access by unauthorized persons.

5.3. End of Trial

The trial is expected to continue until a total of 30 women have been included.

The trial may be prematurely terminated if it this is necessary for safety reasons affecting the risk-benefit balance or if the recruitment of subjects cannot be met within reasonable time limits. The Swedish Medical Products Agency will be informed as soon as possible via CTIS, but no later than 15 days after trial termination.

Decisions on premature termination are taken by the sponsor.

6. Subject selection

Lactating women treated with metformin for diagnosed T2DM, and their breastfed infants.

6.1. Inclusion criteria

To be included in the trial, subjects must meet all of the following criteria:

- Breastfeeding women treated with metformin for suspected or diagnosed type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). Only women of 18 years of age and older will be asked for participation.
- Breastfeeding children of women that have consented to participate in the study. The guardians of the child are asked for participation and consent.

6.2. Exclusion criteria

Subjects must not be included in this trial if any of the following criteria are met:

- Previous participation in the study.
- Premature children.
- Women with multiple births.

6.3. Selection of subjects

General information about the project will be provided in Swedish, Arabic, Persian, Somali and English via a Facebook group of patients with Diabetes hosted by the Swedish patient organisation Diabetesförbundet, through a network of health care professionals via Janusmed at Region Stockholm, to Swedish physicians in Diabetes care, and through information in social media, posters at obstetric clinics, maternity clinics and endocrinology

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clinics in Sweden. A video will be distributed through these channels. A link will be provided to the project webpage for more information.

Specific information about the study will be provided via the obstetric departments and associated maternity clinics, childcare centers and breast-feeding centers. Leaflets, posters and video presentations will be available at the clinical sites. The video will also be distributed via social media, e.g., instagram.

Women willing to participate in the study will be provided with detailed information about what this entails and provided with a written informed consent form, that they will sign and also ask their partners (the other care giver) to sign. They will bring the signed informed consent form with them to the medical doctor at the sampling center.

6.4. Withdrawal criteria

Discontinuation for individual subjects is based on withdrawal of consent. Any participants wanting to withdraw from the study are asked to contact the study coordinator using the contact details that are provided in the consent form. Samples will be destroyed upon withdrawal. Pharmacokinetic data will be stored and part of further analysis together with data from those remaining in the study.

Subjects can discontinue their participation in the trial at any time without any consequence to his/her continued treatment. The investigator/sponsor can at any time terminate the trial for a subject due to, e.g., unacceptable adverse events/adverse reactions or because the subject cannot follow procedures in the clinical trial protocol. If the subject discontinues the trial, follow-up of this subject will be performed according to the clinic's routine.

7. Trial treatments

No treatment or medical prescriptions will be part of the trial. The project has thus a low intervention trial design in the sense that breast milk and blood will be collected merely to study excretion of metformin into breastmilk and transferal to her child. Participation in the study will not decide or in any other way interfere with patients' treatment as prescribed by their physician. Only patients that already have been assigned treatment with metformin by their physician will be approached and asked for participation.

7.1. Description of investigational medicinal product(s)

Not applicable.

7.2. Dose and administration

Metformin is normally administered as filmcoated tablets. The study will not alter the route of administration, the dosage or the dosage regimen for metformin but the participants will continue their treatment as prescribed by their physician.

7.3. Drug accountability and treatment compliance

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It will be assumed that the drug prescribed by the doctor is the correct drug. Women taking drugs administered by a pharmacy will self-report their use of medicines in online questionnaires.

Participants self-register the medicines they are using adjacent to sampling of breast milk and blood.

7.4. Randomization and blinding

No randomization or blinding will be performed.

7.5. Concomitant use of other medicinal products and treatments

Any other concomitant use of medicines or herbal medicines will be documented at sampling sites.

7.6. Treatment after trial end

Not applicable, the study will not influence choice of treatment or dosage. The patients will continue with their metformin treatment, as prescribed by their physician.

8. Methods for measurement of endpoints for clinical efficacy and safety

8.1. Methods for measurement of endpoints for clinical efficacy

The project will only measure pharmacokinetic data of breast milk and blood related to a medicine that is already approved and administered in accordance with standard clinical procedures outside the protocol of this project. The project will not do any assessment of efficacy related to the treatment itself.

8.2. Methods for measurement of endpoints for clinical safety

Regarding pharmacological safety the project will measure pharmacokinetic data of breast milk and blood related to a medicine that is already approved and administered in accordance with standard clinical procedures for women outside the protocol of this project. Adverse events that may impact on breastfeeding and/or breastmilk, e.g., mastitis, will be documented.

8.2.1. Specification of safety parameters

Dosage of mother (mg/kg/day) will be calculated. Dosage of infant as Absolute Infant Dose (AID) in mg/kg/day will be estimated by using 200 mL/kg/day as a standard for daily milk intake in accordance with FDA guidelines for lactation studies (FDA Clinical Lactation Studies May 2019): "While a 150 mL/kg/day estimated milk intake is a reasonable assumption to estimate daily infant dosage, greater volumes do occur in early infancy and often correlate to the time of most reported infant adverse drug events. Additional

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consideration should be given to estimates of infant risk based on a 200 mL/kg/day milk intake in early infancy”.

Relative infant dose (RID) will be calculated by dividing infant dosage (AID) in mg/kg/day with woman dosage in mg/kg/day, multiplied with 100 in order to get the percentage. It is estimated that a RID < 10% is considered safe for the infant (Bennet PN, 1996).

The maternal metformin milk to plasma ratio will be calculated by dividing drug concentration in the mother’s milk with the drug concentration of the mother’s plasma.

Metformin concentration in infant blood will be reported.

8.2.2. The methods and timing for assessing, recording, and analysing safety parameters

The quantification of metformin concentrations in human milk and plasma will be made using LC-MS/MS bioanalytical method in accordance with a standard operating procedure. Measurement of metformin levels in milk and plasma will be carried out using a validated method consisting of high-performance liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS/MS). The method will be developed and validated prior to the analysis by the Department of Pharmacy, Drug Delivery, Uppsala University, Sweden. For the women, signs of mastitis, will be monitored and documented in a protocol up to 24 hours after sampling

9. Handling of Adverse Events

Only serious adverse events (SAEs) and, for the women, signs of mastitis, effects on milk production and effects of milk composition will be monitored and documented in a protocol. Given the short length of the visit, mastitis is unlikely to develop in the 4 hrs and we presume that women will not likely want to enter the study if they have active mastitis, so we expect not to see any cases, but if either of those situations occur, it would be good to follow the mastitis for the 24-hour period. Another reason for documenting mastitis is that there is a possibility that it's presence may change duct physiology such that drug transfer levels could be affected. Other adverse events (AEs) related to blood and milk sampling will not be collected, e.g., pain or bruising at the injection site, as these are expected during sampling procedures.

Because all subjects included in the trial have started the metformin treatment before trial enrollment and the treatment is performed according to clinical praxis, no adverse events related to the medicinal product will be collected during the trial and the Sponsor will not perform SUSAR assessments.

9.1. Definitions

9.1.1. Adverse Event (AE)

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Adverse Event (AE): Any untoward medical occurrence in a subject to whom a medicinal product is administered and which does not necessarily have a causal relationship with this treatment.

9.1.2. Adverse Reaction (AR)

In the pre-approval clinical experience with a new medicinal product or new use of a medicinal product, and particularly as the therapeutic dose(s) may not be established, all noxious and unintended reactions to the medicinal product related to any dose should be considered an adverse reaction (AR). The phrase “reaction” to a medicinal product means that the causal relationship between the medical product and an adverse event is at least a reasonable possibility, that is the relationship cannot be ruled out.

No investigational medicinal product will be administered during the study. Thus, no ARs will be reported.

9.1.3. Serious Adverse Event (SAE)

Serious adverse event (SAE): Any untoward medical occurrence that at any dose requires inpatient hospitalization or prolongation of existing hospitalisation, results in persistent or significant disability or incapacity, results in a congenital anomaly or birth defect, is life-threatening, or results in death.

Medical and scientific assessment will be made to determine if an event is serious and whether it would prompt reporting in other situations, for example important medical events that may not be directly life-threatening or result in death or hospitalization but may compromise the subject or may require intervention to prevent one of the other results set forth in the definitions above. These should also normally be considered as SAEs.

9.1.4. Suspected Unexpected Serious Adverse Reaction (SUSAR)

SUSAR: A reaction/event that is unexpected, serious, and suspected to be caused by the treatment, i.e. adverse reactions that are not included in the Investigator’s Brochure (IB) or SPC.

No investigational medicinal product will be administered during the study. Thus, no SUSARs will be reported.

9.2. Assessment of Adverse Events (AE)

9.2.1. Assessment of seriousness

The investigator is responsible for assessing the seriousness (serious or non-serious). If the adverse event is considered serious, this should be reported as a serious adverse event (SAE) by the investigator to the sponsor. See also section 1.1.9.3.1, Reporting of Serious Adverse Events (SAE).

9.3. Reporting and registration of Adverse Events

9.3.1. Reporting of Serious Adverse Events (SAE)

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It is considered highly unlikely that a serious adverse events (SAEs) would occur during collection of samples from the participating women and children. The blood samples are drawn at the study site by experienced staff and all subjects are carefully monitored.

If the investigator assesses an event that occurred during sampling as serious, they will contact the sponsor as soon as possible by phone or email (see contact information below). An SAE report will also be filled out. Follow-up information describing the outcome and handling of the SAE is reported as soon as this information is available.

Sponsor representative: Mats Hansson
Email: mats.hansson@crb.uu.se
Phone: 018-4716197

9.3.2. Reporting of Suspected Unexpected Serious Adverse Reactions (SUSAR)

Not applicable.

9.4. Follow-up of Adverse Events

Signs of mastitis occurring in association with breast milk sampling will be monitored and documented at the sampling location and referral be made to an ordinary care unit.

If an SAE occurs during sampling, the subject will be monitored until the SAE is resolved.

9.5. Independent Data Monitoring Committee

Not applicable.

9.6. Annual Safety Report (ASR)

An annual safety report will be submitted in CTIS.

9.7. Procedures in case of emergencies, overdose or pregnancy

Not applicable. See reporting of SAEs 9.3.2.

10. Statistics

In general, summary statistics (n [number of available measurements], arithmetic mean, standard deviation [SD], median, minimum, and maximum) for quantitative variables and frequency tables for qualitative data will be presented.

10.1. Analysis population

All subjects included.

10.2. Statistical analyses

10.2.1. Statistical methods

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For metformin concentrations, summary statistics will include geometric mean, geometric coefficient of variation (CV), 95% confidence intervals, arithmetic mean, arithmetic SD, median, minimum, and maximum.

Values that are below the limit of quantification (BLQ) will be set to half the lower limit of quantification (LLOQ) for the calculation of descriptive statistics. Descriptive statistics will be calculated if at least 2/3 of the values are above the LLOQ. If this is not the case, only median, minimum, and maximum will be presented.

The concentration of metformin in the breastfeeding child's plasma 4 hr after maternal dose intake including ADID and RID will be summarized descriptively.

The concentration of metformin in breast milk at 2h after maternal dose intake, the maternal plasma concentration of metformin at 2h after maternal dose intake, and the milk to plasma ratio of the mother will be summarized descriptively.

10.2.2. Drop-outs

All data regarding sampling with information on missing or spurious data, e.g., due to effect of other medications, will be recorded at sampling and stored at a secure dataportal at Uppsala University.

10.3. Sample size calculations

No formal sample size calculations have been performed as there are no statistical hypotheses being tested. The planned sample size for this study is 30 subjects. This sample size should provide sufficient data to assess the primary objective of the study.

10.4. Interim analysis

No interim analysis is planned for this study.

11. Quality Control and Quality Assurance

11.1. Quality Assurance and Sponsor oversight

Sampling follows established clinical routines at each site and is performed by specially trained staff. Biobanking and pharmacokinetic analyses follow qualified procedures.

The involved investigators and institutions will permit trial-related monitoring, audits, IRB/IEC review, and regulatory inspections, providing direct access to source data/documents.

Meetings with investigators, biobanking staff and sponsor representatives will be held at regular intervals in order to monitor that sampling, biobanking and analyses follow the protocol. Follow up of each sampling procedure will be made through the filled in report forms and trial specific documentation from each clinical site.

11.2. Monitoring

Sponsor representatives will monitor the trial in order to ensure that the subjects' safety and integrity are satisfied and check that reported data is reliable and of high quality.

Quality control will be attained through monitoring:

- that subjects exist
- that informed consent has been signed prior to execution of any trial-specific actions
- that subjects are included according to the protocol's inclusion and exclusion criteria
- that the trial's main parameters and safety reporting are handled correctly

Any discrepancies of data will be documented and explained in the monitoring reports.

The Investigator and other responsible personnel will be available during the monitoring visits and will devote sufficient time to these processes.

The Investigator will provide a curriculum vitae (CV) or equivalent documentation of suitability to be responsible for the trial. All Investigators and other responsible personnel will be listed together with their function in the trial on the signature list.

11.3. Source data

Data collected from mother via the project web portal

At 0h

Contact information, including name, postal address, email address and telephone number (self-reported)

Gestational age at last birth (self-reported)

Age (self-reported)

Medical condition that motivates treatment with metformin (self-reported)

Height (self-reported)

Weight (self-reported)

Any medication(s) she is currently using (self-reported)

Any traditional medicinal products she is currently using (self-reported)

Dosage of metformin (self-reported)

Time-point for last dose of metformin and dosing history (self-reported)

Time-point for last breastfeeding (self-reported)

Age of infant (self-reported)

Infant height (self-reported)

Infant weight (self-reported)

Infant medicine use (self-reported)

Any traditional medicinal products the infant is using (self-reported)

Time-point for breast milk sampling

Time-point for dose intake (0h)

Data collected at blood and breastmilk sampling at 2h

Time-point for breast milk sampling (self-reported)

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Data collected by personnel immediately after drawing blood from mother

Time-point for blood sampling

Venipuncture site selection

How blood was drawn (e.g., venipuncture, peripheral venous catheter, port-à-cath)

Tube type used for blood drawing

Any venipuncture equipment used to draw blood

Data collected by personnel immediately after drawing blood from infant

Time-point for blood sampling

Tube type used for blood drawing

Collected data will be pseudonymized so that each participant gets a unique code with the help of a random number generator (generating a number between 1 and 1000). Study participants will be given a Study-ID using this random number when enrolled and consented. Informed consent will also be obtained from the father. Data and key to the code will be kept separately. The biobank will be able to connect the Study-ID with the personal number in order to be able to retrieve samples for analysis.

Source data, SOPs, master protocols and templates will be stored at Uppsala Biobank. Bioanalytical data (validation, stability, and measured drug concentration values from clinical samples) will be stored at UDOPP.

The involved investigators and institutions will permit trial-related monitoring, audits, ethical review, and regulatory inspections, providing direct access to source data/documents.

Samples will be stored at Uppsala Biobank according the following:

- Name of site
- Study Donor Id
- Sample Id
- Sampling date and time of sample collection
- SPREC code (type of sample and sample handling)
- All biobank data will be in LIMS and traceability of samples and shipments will be managed in the LIMS

Bioanalytical data will be stored at UDOPP

- Drug concentration value in breast milk
- Drug concentration value in plasma from mother
- Drug concentration value in plasma/blood from infant
- Analytical methods validation results
- Quality data
- Cmax: Maximum observed drug concentration
- tmax: Time of the maximum observed concentration

11.4. Deviations, serious breaches and other reporting obligations

The investigators at each clinical site will, without delay, report to the sponsor any serious breaches and deviations from the trial protocol, ICH-GCP and other regulations that significantly and directly affect, or with high likelihood could affect, the subjects' safety and

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integrity or the reliability and robustness of the data generated in the trial. The sponsor will assess the suspected serious breach and the consequences of deviations that have occurred, and, without undue delay but no later than 7 days (from knowledge) report these to the Swedish Medical Products Agency via CTIS.

Other unexpected events that may affect the benefit/risk relationship will be reported via CTIS without undue delay, but no later than 15 days after the sponsor becomes aware of the event.

Minor deviations that do not affect subjects' integrity or safety, nor significantly affect the trial's scientific value, are documented in the trial documentation of the principal investigator and the sponsor and appropriate measures will be taken. The deviations will be recorded in the clinical trial report.

11.5. Audits and inspections

Authorized representatives for the sponsor and Competent Authorities (CA) may carry out audits or inspections at the trial site, including source data verification. The investigator will ensure that all source documents are available for audits and inspections.

12. Ethics

12.1. Compliance to the protocol, ICH-GCP and regulations

The trial will be performed in compliance with the EU regulation on low-intervention clinical trials on medicinal products for human use (536/2014), the Declaration of Helsinki, ICH-GCP standards applicable to the trial procedures, and current national regulations governing this clinical trial. This is to ensure the safety and integrity of the trial subjects as well as the quality of the data collected.

12.2. Ethical review of the trial

The final protocol for clinical trials on medicinal products will be approved, as a part of the application for a permit for clinical trials via CTIS, by both the Swedish Ethical Review Authority and the Swedish Medical Products Agency before start of trial. The authority will be informed via CTIS of any changes in the trial protocol in accordance with current requirements.

12.3. Procedure for obtaining informed consent

The principal investigator at each site will ensure that the subject is given full and adequate oral and written information about the trial, its purpose, any risks and benefits as well as inclusion and exclusion criteria. Subjects will also be informed that they are free to discontinue their participation in the trial at any time without having to provide a reason. Subjects will be given the opportunity to ask questions and be allowed time to consider the provided information.

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If the person chooses to participate, the subject shall sign the informed consent form. The women participating in the trial will also ask their partners (the other care giver) to sign. They will bring the signed informed consent form with them to the medical doctor at the sampling center who will sign the form. A copy of the subject information as well as the informed consent form will be provided to the woman. The subject's signed and dated informed consent will be obtained before any trial-specific activity is performed. Each subject who participates in the trial will be identified by a subject number on a subject identification list.

12.4. Data protection

In the information provided to subjects, subjects will be fully informed about how their trial data will be collected, used and disclosed. The content of the informed consent form complies with relevant integrity and data protection legislation, including the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR). The subject information and the informed consent form will explain how trial data are stored to maintain confidentiality in accordance with national data legislation and GDPR (see section 14). All information processed by the sponsor will be pseudonymized and coded.

The informed consent form will also explain that for verification of the data, representatives delegated by the sponsor, as well as relevant authorities, may require access to parts of medical records or trial records that are relevant to the trial, including the subject's medical history.

12.5. Insurances

No insurance except the ordinary Patient damage insurance.

13. Substantial changes to the trial

Substantial changes to the signed clinical trial protocol are only possible through approved protocol amendments.

In the event that substantial changes to the protocol which may affect the safety, rights of subjects or the reliability and robustness of data generated need to be implemented during the course of the trial, permission from the relevant authority via application in CTIS will be obtained before implementing the change. This includes the addition of a new trial site or a change of the principal investigator at the trial site.

Non-substantial amendments are entered into the CTIS in the next substantial amendment application concerning the same part. If the non-substantial change is relevant to the

Authority's oversight (e.g. contact details), the CTIS will be updated on an ongoing basis.

14. Collection, handling, and archiving of data

Sampling details and health-related details will be collected using a paper questionnaire and then registered in the program REDCAP (Research Electronic Data Capture). Informed consent forms are sent by registered mail to Uppsala University and stored in a locked cabinet only accessible by authorised personnel. Data will be uploaded in an encrypted format which then will be hosted at a locked and secure server of Uppsala University (Dataportal ALLVIS) and Region Uppsala in accordance with an established process approved by the Swedish Ethical Review Authority. At ALLVIS data is physically stored in two separate data centers according to ISO 27001 guidelines. Both data centers are equipped with business-class networks, servers and hard drives with high availability and security. All data centers are equipped with access controls, cooling systems, backup power and surge protection. They are protected against common threats such as fire, water damage, burglary and theft. Access is limited to technical staff and strictly logged. All data is encrypted in transit (https) and at rest (through database encryption). ALLVIS is configured with file versioning, saving up to 500 versions of a single file. A recycle bin saves deleted files for up to 30 days.

Content databases are configured with transaction logging, limiting potential data loss to 1 hour during critical failures. Databases are backed up incrementally, daily, weekly, monthly and annually using a TSM-based backup system located in the same data center. Network traffic is protected by a robust firewall and servers hosting file content are not directly connected to the Internet. Access to the data is limited to authorized researchers

Collected data will be pseudonymized and encoded. Data and key to the code will be kept separately. Study participants will be given a Study-ID when enrolled and consented.

The complete Trial Master File with essential documents will be archived for at least 25 years. Source data in the medical records system are stored and archived in accordance with national regulations.

14.1. Case Report Form

A Case Report Form (CRF) is used for data collection. It includes three separate paper forms filled in at sampling (See attachments). The investigator will ensure that data is registered and any corrections in the CRF are made as stated in the clinical trial protocol and in accordance with the instructions. The investigator will ensure that the registered data is correct, complete, and that reporting takes place according to the timelines that have been predefined and agreed. The principal investigator signs the completed forms. A copy of the completed forms will be archived at the site.

15. Notification of trial completion, reporting, and publication

End of the trial is reported in CTIS at the latest 15 days after completion.

Within one year of trial completion, a clinical study report is completed, and a summary of the clinical trial results will be reported in CTIS, including a summary for lay people.

Scientific publications based on the study results will adhere to Vancouver guidelines.

16. References

- Hale, T., Kristensen, J., Hackett, L., Kohan, R., & Ilett, K. (2002). Transfer of metformin into human milk. *Diabetologia*, 45(11), 1509-1514.
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- Briggs, G. G., Ambrose, P. J., Nageotte, M. P., Padilla, G., & Wan, S. (2005). Excretion of metformin into breast milk and the effect on nursing infants. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 105(6), 1437-1441.
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17. Attachments

Questionnaire 1-4

Frågeformulär 1 (fylls i av deltagare vid första provtillfället)

Studie: Läkemedelsbehandling med Metformin i samband med amning

Deltagares ID:

Datum: ____/____/____ (t. ex. 20/01/2012)

Tid: _____

Instruktion:

Detta frågeformulär syftar till att samla in information som skall användas vid analys av dina prover. Informationen kommer att behandlas så att inte obehöriga kan ta del av den. **Detta frågeformulär fylls i efter det första bröstmjölksprovet.**

Information om dig

1. Hur gammal är du? ____ år
2. Hur lång är du? ____ cm
3. Hur mycket väger du? ____ kg
4. För vilken diagnos tar du Metformin?

[Fritext:] _____

5. Vilka andra mediciner tar du?

[Fritext:] _____

6. Använder du något/några naturläkemedel?

” Nej ” Ja

Om ja, ange namn: _____

7. Vilken dos av Metformin tar du? (till exempel 2 tabletter á 500 mg per dag)?

[Fritext:] _____

8. Ange när du tog din senaste dos av Metformin:

Datum: ____/____/____ (t. ex. 20/01/2012)

Tid: _____

Frågeformulär 2 (fylls i av personal efter blodprov)

Studie: Läkemedelsbehandling med Metformin i samband med amning

Deltagares ID:

Datum: ____ / ____ / ____ (t. ex. 20/01/2012)

Tid: _____

Instruktion:

Detta frågeformulär syftar till att samla in information som skall användas vid analys av deltagarens prover. Informationen kommer att behandlas så att inte obehöriga kan ta del av den. *Detta frågeformulär fylls i efter vardera blodprovstagningsstillfälle.*

Information om blodprovstagnning

1. Ange datum och tidpunkt för blodprovtagning:

Datum: ____ / ____ / ____ (t. ex. 20/01/2012)

Tid: _____

2. Ange vart blodprovet togs:

” vänster arm ” höger arm ” bägge sidor ” annan lokalisation

3. Hur togs blodprovet:

- Genom venpunktion
- Från en perifer venkateter (PVK)
- Från en port-a-cath (subkutan venport, SVP)
- Från en PICC-line
- Från en annan typ av kateter: _____

4. Ange vilken typ av provrör som användes:

5. Ange vilken typ av utrustning som användes för venöst blodprov:

Frågeformulär 3

(fylls i av deltagare efter det andra bröstmjölksprovet)

Studie: Läkemedelsbehandling med Metformin i samband med amning

Deltagares ID:

Datum: ____/____/____ (t. ex. 20/01/2012)

Tid: _____

Instruktion:

Detta frågeformulär syftar till att samla in information som skall användas vid analys av dina prover. Informationen kommer att behandlas så att inte obehöriga kan ta del av den. **Detta frågeformulär fylls i efter det andra bröstmjölksprovet.**

Information om provtagning av bröstmjolk

1. Ange när du senast ammade:

Datum: ____/____/____ (t. ex. 20/01/2012)

Tid: _____

2. Vid vilken tidpunkt började du pumpa ur bröstmjolk?

Datum: ____/____/____ (t. ex. 20/01/2012)

Tid: _____

Frågeformulär 4 (fylls i av personal efter blodprov på barnet)

Studie: Läkemedelsbehandling med Metformin i samband med amning

Deltagares ID:

Datum: ____/____/____ (t. ex. 20/01/2012)

Tid: _____

Instruktion:

Detta frågeformulär syftar till att samla in information som skall användas vid analys av blodprovet som tagits på deltagarens barn. Informationen kommer att behandlas så att inte obehöriga kan ta del av den. *Detta frågeformulär skall fyllas i en gång, efter att blodprov tagits på barnet.*

Information om blodprovstaging

1) Ange datum och tidpunkt för blodprovtagning av barnet:

Datum: ____/____/____ (t. ex. 20/01/2012)

Tid: _____

2) Ange vart blodprovet togs (t. ex häl, handrygg osv):

3) Ange vilken typ av provrör som användes:

4. Övrig information:

[Fritext:] _____
